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“Innovation in Education Raising Scientific Literacy”

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Paper 1

CONSTRUCTION AND VALIDATION OF “ABISUS SCALE”: A TOOL FOR ASSESSING EXAMINATION FEAR AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we aimed to construct and validate the "Abisus scale", a new tool for assessing exam fear among university students. A set of questions addressed the physical, emotional, behavioral, and cognitive symptoms of exam fear. The first draft of the questionnaire contained 12 questions. Following evaluation by a panel of experts, two questions were deleted, and the second draft included ten questions with a 5-point Likert scale as the scoring key. Following a pilot study, the questionnaire was administered to 115 students, and we discovered that removing the tenth question enhanced Cronbach's alpha. So, we omitted the tenth question and the alpha value increased from 0.781 to 0.811. All calculated coefficients (r) are greater than the critical value (.195), confirming the validity of the exam fear Scale. The developed scale was retested on the same students 6 months later, and the test-retest reliability was calculated using Cronbach's Alpha. The results showed that the exam fear scale is reliable, with Cronbach's Alpha values of .811 [first response] and .767 [second response]. The calculated coefficients (r) are greater than the critical value (.195), indicating the validity of the exam fear scale and demonstrating the consistency of the questionnaire over time. The severity of exam fear is classified as low (20 or a lower raw score), medium (21-32 raw score), or high (33 or above raw score) using Z score calculation and interpretation. Exam fear was evaluated among participants, and 13% of students were in the low e, 71% in the medium, and 16% in the high exam fear categories respectively. The evolving demands of the modern education system necessitate the development of a novel exam fear scale to effectively assess exam fear among students in modern educational environments, with universities able to utilize the newly developed "Abisus scale" to create stress reduction programs accessible to all students.

Keywords: Abisus scale, Exam fear, Scale Construction, Scale Validation, University Students.

1.INTRODUCTION:

The academic achievement of students is crucial for the development of any country, as it ensures the availability of skilled graduates¹. Numerous studies have been carried out to examine the different factors that influence students' academic performance. These factors encompass elements such as students' effort, learning preferences, entry qualifications, class attendance², anxiety levels³, motivation, educational supervision⁴, and study habits⁵. Generally, students often experience a great deal of fear when it comes to exams. This fear stems from their anticipation of performing poorly and failing, which leads to what is known as examination anxiety. Examination fear is essentially an unpredictable worry about the outcome of one's performance, a fear of being evaluated, and apprehension about the results

It is characterized by irrational thoughts, unnecessary demands and expectations, and even catastrophic predictions. In fact, examination fear is considered to be a significant factor that contributes to a variety of negative outcomes, including psychological distress, academic underachievement, academic failure, and a general sense of insecurity⁶. Examination fear or anxiety can lead to many problems, which can be physical, emotional, behavioral, and cognitive (Shukla, 2013)⁷.

Table I. Exam fear symptoms and its manifestations⁷

Physical symptoms	Increased Heart rate, nausea, stomach upset, sweating, etc.
Emotional symptoms	excess fear of failing, disappointment, etc.
Behavioral symptoms	procrastination, difficulty in sleeping, etc.
Cognitive symptoms	Difficulty in concentration, mental blocks, etc.

Mandler and Sarason developed the initial measurement tool for assessing examination anxiety in 1952 with 42 items in the questionnaire. Followed by questionnaire developed by Sarason (1958)⁸ with 21 items, Sarason (1972) with 37 items, Suinn (1969)⁹, Spielberger¹⁰ and its Associates (1980) which consists of 20 items. Many tools can be found in the global perspective with more items to answer, which is actually time-consuming. Here comes the importance of constructing and validating a tool with fewer items, but that covers physical, emotional, behavioral, and cognitive aspects that can assess examination fear among university students in the modern educational environment. So, this research aims at developing and validating a scale that measures the examination fear of university students.

2.OBJECTIVES

- To construct and validate the "Abisus scale"
- To assess the internal consistency
- To establish the test-retest reliability
- To classify the severity of exam fear

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- To propose the newly introduced scale to universities

3.MATERIAL AND METHODS:

POPULATION:

The study was conducted among health university students with the objective of generating and validating a new scale for measuring exam fear among students.

SAMPLING:

The initial phase of the study involved 115 students who were scheduled for exams.

To verify the consistency and accuracy of the responses, the same students' responses are collected in the second phase. It is important to note that students' moods can affect how they respond to questions. Thus, obtaining two answers may mitigate the effect that variations have on the data.

QUESTIONNAIRE GENERATION:

The first step involved creating a questionnaire with fewer questions to reduce the burden on respondents. This will increase participation and help respondents finish the questionnaire faster, but it also needs to have a better focus to effectively capture the key components of exam fear.

A pool of questions was developed that addressed the physical, emotional, behavioral, and cognitive symptoms of exam fear.

The first draft of the questionnaire consisted of 12 questions

EXPERT REVIEW:

A panel of experts, comprising college professors, counsellors, and psychologists, reviewed the questionnaires to ensure that they were pertinent and complete and that each question directly addressed the intended construct to be measured. As per expert opinion, 2 questions were removed and the second draft consisted of 10 questions.

The constructed questionnaire pattern consisted of 10 questions and the scoring key consisted of a 5-point Likert Scale.

The five options include

Table II. Likert scale scoring key

Rating	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Score	1	2	3	4	5

PILOT SAMPLING:

A small sample of participants, including 30 students, were administered the developed questionnaire to evaluate its clarity, comprehension, and redundancy. The students' responses stated that the questions are simple, clear, and easy to understand.

ADMINISTRATION OF SCALE:

The constructed questionnaire pattern of 10 questions was administered to a group of 115 students who were scheduled for exams. The objective of the study of validating a new exam fear scale was presented to the students before their consent to participate was obtained.

4.RESULTS:

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 20

While examining the “Scale of Item deleted” score, we found that Cronbach’s alpha value can be improved by deleting the 10th question. Thus, we improved the alpha value from 0.781 to 0.811.

RELIABILITY:

Reliability is the measure of the internal consistency of the constructs in the study. A construct is reliable if the Alpha value is greater than .70 (Hair et al.,2013)¹¹. Construct reliability was assessed using Cronbach’s Alpha. The result revealed that the Exam fear scale with Cronbach’s Alpha value = .811(>.70) is found reliable.

VALIDITY:

Validity refers to how accurately a method measures what it is intended to measure. Validity was assessed using Pearson’s correlation coefficient. A scale is valid if the calculated coefficient is greater than the critical value. The calculated coefficients (r) are given below;

Table III. Calculated Coefficients(r)

Question.no	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9
r	.564	.647	.667	.682	.675	.614	.569	.625	.642
Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115	115	115

The critical value with 113(N-2) degrees of freedom and 5% level of significance is .195. All calculated coefficients (r) are greater than the critical value, so the validity of the Exam fear scale was established.

RETESTING:

After deleting one question from the constructed 10 questionnaire,9 question pattern was administered to the same group of students after six months who were scheduled to appear in exams.

RETEST RELIABILITY:

Construct reliability was assessed using Cronbach’s Alpha. The result revealed that the Exam fear scale with Cronbach’s Alpha value = .811[first response] and .767[second response] are found reliable.

RETEST VALIDITY:

Validity was assessed using Pearson’s correlation coefficient. A scale is valid if the calculated coefficient is greater than the critical value. The calculated coefficients (r) for the first (r¹) and second (r²) responses are given below;

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Table IV. The calculated coefficients (r) for the first (r¹) and second (r²) responses

Question.No	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9
r ¹	.564	.647	.667	.682	.675	.614	.569	.625	.642
r ²	.683	.577	.669	.659	.710	.753	.627	.657	.677
Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
N	115	115	115	115	115	115	115	115	115

The coefficient critical value with 113(N-2) degrees of freedom and 5% level of significance is .195. All calculated coefficients (r) are greater than the critical value, so the validity of exam fear scale was established.

EXAM FEAR SCALE STANDARDIZATION:

From the total respondents, Z scores were calculated for each raw score

Table V. Raw Score Vs Z Score

Raw Score	Z score
9	-3.025
12	-2.512
14	-2.169
15	-1.998
16	-1.827
17	-1.655
18	-1.484
19	-1.313
20	-1.142
21	-0.970
22	-0.799
23	-0.628
24	-0.457
25	-0.285
26	-0.114
27	0.057
28	0.228
29	0.400
30	0.571
31	0.742
32	0.913
33	1.085
34	1.256
35	1.427
36	1.598
38	1.941
41	2.455
43	2.797

After calculating the raw score, the range of Z scores was divided into 3 categories

1. Low Exam Fear
2. Medium Exam Fear
3. High Exam fear

Table VI. The Categorization of Exam Fear Based on the Z Score Calculation

Raw Score Range	Z Score Range	Category
20 or below	Below -1	Low Exam Fear
21-32	-1 to +1	Medium Exam Fear
33 or above	Above +1	High Exam Fear

After checking the reliability and validity of “**Abisus scale**”, we categorized the exam fear level based on Z score and concluded that the level of exam fear among 13% of students was in low,71% in medium, and 16% in high exam fear categories respectively.

5.DISCUSSION:

Multiple research investigations have consistently found a negative correlation between exam anxiety and educational outcomes¹². University students rarely come across examination-oriented research studies, particularly on validating and measuring exam fear among them. Our research aimed to measure exam fear among university students by constructing and validating the "**Abisus scale**," a new tool to measure the exam fear of university students, providing useful information categorizing the level of exam fear and supporting universities in working on stress reduction programs for students.

The modern education system demands a novel updated exam fear scale to measure exam fear among students in modern learning environments. By testing the validity of the “**Abisus scale**” it is proved that the questionnaire measures what it is intended to measure ie; the exam fear, which ensures the usefulness and credibility of the questionnaire in getting accurate results from the data collected. A high Cronbach’s alpha value above 0.70(0.811) [first response] and .767[second response] suggests that the constructed new exam fear scale termed as “**Abisus scale**” is consistent and reliable and can be used for research and assessment purposes. By doing the testing and retesting of the constructed scale, the results proved the consistency and validity of the questionnaire over time.

By using Z score calculation and interpretation the severity of exam fear is categorized into low (20 or below raw score), medium (21-32 raw score), and high (33 or above) raw score) categories. Using the Abisus scale, exam fear was evaluated among the respondents and 13% of students were on low exam fear category,71% on medium exam fear and 16% had high exam fear. The newly developed “**Abisus exam fear scale**’ has good consistency, reliability, and validity and contains fewer number of questions (9 questions only), which helps to reduce respondent burden, helps to increase participation and respondents can complete the questionnaire in lesser time.

6.LIMITATIONS:

Despite being a questionnaire with fewer questions reducing the burden of respondents ,it may not necessarily cover all the aspects of exam fear comprehensively, and may lack the power to discriminate between respondents (students) of varying levels of exam fear. The questionnaire is developed from the responses of university students and may not be appropriate for school students or other populations without validation or reconstruction of the questionnaire.

7.CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, the **Abisus scale** is a promising tool for evaluating exam fear, providing useful information for targeted interventions. The **Abisus scale** comprises of fewer questions (9 items), which reduces respondent burden, increases participation, and allows respondents to complete the questionnaire in lesser time. Universities can assess exam fear in students using our newly developed “**Abisus scale**” and must work to guarantee that stress reduction programs are available to all students while also refining initiatives that effectively address the unique needs and concerns of various student populations.

COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

This manuscript has been prepared in complying with the ethical standards and relevant research guidelines.

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10.DECLARATION OF CONFLICTS OF INTEREST:

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11.APPENDIX

The standardized English version of the exam fear scale with 9 questions for university students

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ABISUS EXAM FEAR SCALE QUESTIONNAIRE

1. I feel tensed or worry excessively when thinking about upcoming exams.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

2. I feel any of the physical symptoms, such as sweating, an increased heart rate, stomach upset, or nausea, either before or during an exam.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

3. I'm afraid of failing examinations or not performing well enough.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

4. I am worried of disappointing others or felt under pressure from them, especially my family members.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

5. I am not confident about my preparation for the exam

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

6. I experience mental blocks find it challenging to concentrate on the exam

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

7. I avoid study because of fear or anxiety

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

8. I often delay or postpone my exam preparation tasks due to procrastination.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

9. I find difficulty in sleeping prior to exams

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

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Paper 2

EDUCATIONAL INNOVATION AND RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

Innovation processes in the Spanish and international educational models have evolved, especially over the last 40 years. Technological expansion and development have been integrated, into the field of education. There have been changes to the educational model: school practices have been modified so that, while not entailing a completely generalised impact, significant advances have been introduced. This has led to a change in the spaces, times and ways in which these practices are implemented, thus paving the way for a complete shift in the model. Yet this has not led to a systematic and organised reflection on the processes of change, nor on how to approach evaluation and research in education. This paper aims to provide some ideas about the correct targets of these transformations, and it does so by presenting several examples.

Keywords: Educative Innovation, evaluation/research, mixed method designs, technology

Introduction

Innovation in educational systems is vital to improving the school's efficiency and productivity in the 21st century. The implementation of innovation in education will ensure that the existing educational system will produce skilled and knowledgeable students to fulfil existing and future industrial needs. However, the implementation of these concepts is still debated among scholars nowadays as it still blurs in concept, definition, and applications. Therefore, this paper tried to provide a single and suitable definition for innovation in educational purposes. It also aimed to give a slight view on the type of innovations in education, identified the differences between the concepts of innovation in education with technological advancements, and to identify the barriers for the implementation in innovation in educations. This paper will contribute to the development of the innovation concept in educational settings and advancement.

Definition of Innovation in Education

The discussion on the definition of innovation sometimes mixed with the concept of the invention, change, and reformation in education. Some scholars also define innovation in

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fig 1.1 Innovation

education as a process, and some even explain it according to innovation theories in business development as mentioned in the above fig 1.1. These various definitions of innovation in education are very confusing when we try to discuss innovation in education. The most well-known definition of innovation in education nowadays came from the Oslo Manual (OECD/Eurostat, 2005). Innovation defined as the realization of new or enhanced products, services, products, marketing strategies, or new organisational strategies, external relations, or workplace organisation. According to OECD (2016), this definition can be applied in the educational sector with a small modification. Thus, OECD (2016) defined innovation in education as the introduction of an improved or new process, products, services, new ways of managing activities, or new marketing approaches. However, according to a few scholars in education, this definition of innovation cannot adequately describe innovation in education. Technological development has conditioned and will continue to condition the processes of change in schools since, from a social perspective, it causes the transformation of social uses and of the very concept of society. Within the framework of human development, the technological revolution has shaped the actions, behaviours and profiles of all of us who participate in the technological environment, an influence which, as the latter author points out, permeates all our vital actions in a fluid and liquid manner. We are surrounded by a huge number of actions, facts and relational and communicative processes that take place over the internet. Education is one of those fields of human action that is subject to such influences. In fact, we are generating innovation when we transform educational processes through the use of technology, even if sometimes the way we use the latter is not entirely positive. In fact, the transformation of educational and innovation-gearred processes by means of technology has also involved a procedural makeover as well as a change in our approach to evaluating/researching the benefits that these processes bring about. To talk about how educational innovation has developed over the last 40 years is to associate educational changes with teaching methodologies and technology integration. Basic ideas, such as those proposed by Carbonell when he defines the concept of innovation in relation to the school setting, construe these changes as a series of intentional and systematic interventions, decisions, and processes aimed at modifying attitudes,

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ideas, cultures, contents, models and pedagogical practices. Currently, understanding this process involves rethinking the school model as a whole so that it meets the needs of both the knowledge society and the students who are immersed daily in new technologies and new forms of communication and learning, as well as in the creative construction of knowledge. Changes occur spontaneously, often because of the emergence of a new type of technology that facilitates a process or action that had not been possible before. In other cases, we witness the reuse of a specific technology that had originally been deployed for one type of human activity in different contexts, including school settings. There are many examples of this occurrence, but a case in point may well be the use of repositioning in the world of mobile learning as shown in below fig 1.2.

fig 1.2 Mobile learning

Furthermore, how are these changes caused by the integration of technology into the educational activities of a school from any level (primary schools, secondary schools or universities) evaluated and researched? The dynamics of evaluation and research, which in this paper are closely connected because of the need for both to plan actions and develop instruments for data collection, require procedures for data gathering and analysis that support an informed response to the issue or change under examination. From our point of view, if we evaluate or research these new processes with the aid of technologies, we must also rethink our designs. In this case, data sources, by the very nature of educational activities, are nourished by qualitative information, as well as by the perspective of the subjects who participate in it. However, it can also be nourished by the information provided by technological resources, usually quantitative or quantifiable. The answer to the question of how to plan evaluation and research around the current use of technology in education inevitably steers our focus in the direction of mixed designs and analyses. It is necessary to introduce research dynamics that go beyond classical educational inquiries based on either qualitative or quantitative methodologies. We need to move towards mixed designs: firstly, because the reasonable epistemology of this current of pragmatic thinking can help us break the dichotomous struggles between post-positivism and constructivism. Secondly, because when we introduce technology into educational innovation processes, it provides us with both quantitative and qualitative information that needs to be incorporated into our research designs. In this paper we want to present an overview of the incidence of educational innovation in terms of the incorporation of new methodologies, experiences and technologies,

which in turn will lead us to the search for their value as tools for improvement in research processes that combine data sources, mixed analyses and the construction of complex conclusions. In this way, this article attempts to provide an outline of how technology aided educational innovation is being understood at present. We will also provide examples of how such proposals for change are being designed, researched and implemented. We hope that this contribution can be helpful in guiding new styles of inquiry and bridging a long-standing gap in innovation dynamics: the absence of robust research into the value of what we propose as changes targeted at having an impact on processes and on individuals. Although much emphasis is placed on innovation, little attention is paid to the process of analysing its value as a driver of transformation. Perhaps because we are specialists in our educational disciplines, but we are not very experienced in research or evaluation processes.

Educational Innovation and the Integration of Technology

Innovation in education, as well as in all other fields of social development and knowledge, is important, but it is particularly relevant in this field of study, where it has largely become the groundwork for our research processes as educators. Educational innovation is what makes teaching action change and improve. The foundation of Educational Innovation in technology rests, as Mike Sharples et al. Argue, on the educational research actions and projects that academics undertake. This was made evident when members of the Open University in the UK, in collaboration with several tertiary education institutions worldwide, published one of the first annual reports on educational innovation. This work was particularly focused on educational technology, understood as a framework for methodological development, innovative experiences and the development of educational resources. Since then, a report on the orientations and outcomes of educational innovation has been published annually (<http://www.open.ac.uk/blogs/innovating/> (accessed on 20 November 2022)). From the time these reports were issued, and long before that, important work has been done in terms of promoting technology as a fundamental axis of innovation. All innovations should start by responding to some questions. First, we should make sure that what we are trying to change involves an approach that enables the individual and general extension of innovative school practices; innovation is not just “proof of concept”. An example of this was the initial use of resources such as VLEs, which originated in the previous century even though their introduction in schools in Castile and León only began in the academic year 2018-2019. Secondly, we must answer the question of whether people make structures or structures make people. In this case, we are in a situation where the social structure entails an important transformation in the school institution. It is not that there are changes in society that the school must take on board, but rather that the school is at a time of fundamental social change. Additionally, this has a critical impact on education, since traditionally

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the school incorporates many social processes by means of knowledge and information (it used to organise content in a static and analogue form, and now this is done in a dynamic and digital form); it employs society’s basic resources to interact through written communication (previously the classic reading-writing systems and now the digital systems). Therefore, educational institutions and the people who run them are pervaded by the sense of ongoing change: the teacher, formerly a repository of knowledge, is now a guide in a dynamic world. If we analyse the proposals put forward by the Open University report as trends in educational innovation in 2022, we see that they focus on the use of hybrid models. After the pandemic, we witness a combination of workspaces in the school timetable and those outside the classroom. The “new normal” that followed the COVID-19 pandemic has made it possible to understand the virtuality of this model, where many more people can participate in training, whether or not they are physically close, by relying on flexible processes. The report also highlights the importance of dual training jointly provided by schools and companies/industries. Another aspect it underlines is the pedagogies related to micro-credentials are a new type of qualification with specific characteristics oriented towards career, workplace, and professional competencies. Micro-credentials aim to open opportunities for new groups of learners so that people studying them are likely to have a different profile from those who sign up for other forms of traditional education or training. One other aspect worth mentioning is the construction of training in a self-regulated way. These approaches to training or education have a lot to do with the generation of learning autonomy in what some authors have termed learning ecologies. Essentially, this is so because each person has a specific environment that teaches them and shapes their own learning. The report likewise emphasises the support of video viewing in general, which leads to closed environments agreed upon by the teacher and the students, but which can also take place in autonomous settings strongly associated with learning processes-an aspect worth analysing when it comes to evaluation. Similarly, mention is made of the management of learning processes through the agency of “educational influencers”. Finally, the document discusses suggestive views on pedagogies for home education, critical pedagogies of contestation, or movement-based pedagogies. All the above issues reveal the impact of technology and the fundamental pillars that support its implementation. However, what does this mean in terms of the paradigm shift in education? Furthermore, how should the school be transformed on all educational levels? In this sense, the school has to readjust:

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fig 1.3 Interaction between a teacher and a student

- The role of the teacher, who is nowadays more of a guide and process manager as shown in the above fig 1.3.
- The way in which the school teaches because it must change its textbook-centred training models.
- The very substance of teaching, which should focus on students learning to navigate a networked society, rather than being the guarantor of stable content.
- Content, which is dynamic and therefore should not be taught for a static society, but for one that is diverse, ever-changing and participatory. Therefore, the school must focus on teaching life skills.

The ways of assessment, which are essentially not suitable for a changing society and must therefore perform a more complex role adapted to such social complexity. The above dynamics of education have been the object of study in the scientific community for a long time, especially since the technological revolution took shape, and even more so in the university environment and in view of the transformations that European higher education systems have undergone in recent decades.

Evaluation and research models for this type of experience: The mixed perspective

In order to carry out research or evaluation processes in new spaces of innovation, we need to define how they should be specifically implemented. Let us broadly define a framework for the analysis and assessment of what these processes contribute against the backdrop of innovative proposals in the field of education. Both in this and the following section, information about current developments in innovation led activities is characteristically nourished by quantitative and qualitative data. We can argue that innovative experiences involving technology require the use of both sources of information for evaluation and research purposes. Our attempt goes beyond defining an epistemological position for educational research and is instead supported by a series of methodological implications associated with the quantitative and qualitative traditions. In 1989, starting with, a new perspective began to take shape: the “mixed” conception of research processes. This perspective emerged as a response to the classic controversy between an extensive and generalising focus of research and an in-depth and comprehensive focus on the question under examination. When technology is carried over into the field of educational innovation, the data it collects about current practices provide real quantifiable information about educational activities. No doubt this information contributed evidence of the steps a user takes, but in the analysis of innovation practices, we can also incorporate qualitative data in the form of opinions, observations and reflections. By resorting to mixed methodologies, we can more easily ensure that in any research process five fundamental principles can be observed so as to secure the quality of analysis, one which is complex, yet also close to human situations, and supported by data that represent the various

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positions of participants. In this sense, we seek to improve by “triangulating” the information, which determines or corroborates the observations achieved by any method, but even more so if two contrasting methods are used. We also sometimes seek “complementarity” as a means of clarifying results when a single qualitative or quantitative perspective does not sufficiently help. Thus we “develop” a process of understanding by shifting from one method to the other. We may occasionally be interested in “expanding” and broadening the research outcomes by seeking to identify particular elements or collateral topics in connection with our research problem. Finally, we may “initiate” a process of extended search for contradictions or complex issues, sometimes simply by broadening our observational framework. These five principles, which Greene first developed in 1989, are fleshed out in her monograph on mixed methodologies published in 2007. Greene’s works, in addition to those signed by authors like Creswell and Creswell, or Tassacori and Teddly, provide a research framework in the area of the Social Sciences and Education that leads us to complex designs which combine quantitative and qualitative data and analytical processes and furnish us with a sound grounding for discussions of technological innovation. We can produce a number of simple arguments that underpin the importance of this kind of approach. In the first place, when we introduce technology in an educational environment, the processes that are set in motion involve people who participate in activities, form opinions, can be observed or can themselves engage in the observation of their own experiences. Moreover, through the use of technology, they also leave traces of their narrative creations, opinions, and qualitative contributions in technological formats that remain as evidence of their views. Social media, virtual learning environments, simple contributions in the form of school assignments, etc., are clear examples of this valuable input. In addition, the use of technology generates quantitative information that can be analysed: trajectories, systematic action processes, user profiles, interactions with other users, targeted actions, etc., all of which are stored in technological devices. Although this “digital footprint” often raises significant concern, voiced by authors like Marta Peirano, who denounced the misuse of data from telephone communications and social media, this does not refute the general benefits that may be drawn by research from processes that are already being implemented in the treatment of information in the global market and in the world at large. Thus, when planning research actions in technological environments and in educational contexts, we must bear in mind that as soon as we use technology, we start generating quantitative data in addition to the feedback we are able to collect from a qualitative perspective that these data cannot be ignored because the information on how learning takes place is enriched by additional inputs from the initial, intermediate and final steps of our inquiry as well as by other non-aligned sources (information about the retrieval of information itself from the Web). In this sense, we have to carefully consider how to draw up our research designs and what our general approach will be: do we mean to be extensive and explanatory, or do we

want instead to delve deeper into the analysis of the specific situation under examination? We likewise need to consider when and how to collect and analyse each piece of information, the sequence of data gathering, the evidence and the method that inform each step in that design. Finally, we must ensure that the results and conclusions obtained provide a truer picture of the facts and the object of our research. Because the integration of technological resources means that educational activities can be experienced at two different levels: one observable by the naked eye and another that is virtually accessed thanks to the technology that envelops the real world. In the following section, we will briefly present some cases to illustrate the basic typologies of this type of design where research that has generated an innovation proposal is also supported by mixed methodologies and where the research work itself involved not only the monitoring of innovation but also, and ultimately, its evaluation.

What experience tells us: Innovation initiatives for the use of technology in the classroom

In the research group where we have been working for more than two decades, investigative processes related to the use of technology and the evaluation of its potential uses in education have been carried out within the mixed methods framework. The latter findings have proved useful in constructing concepts for discussion and developing a theoretical framework for the analysis and implementation of standard or good practices to exemplify our conception of educational technology. First, it is necessary to make a clear definition of what is understood by good practices, sometimes understood as the space where traditional practices are developed with innovative elements that help improve their results or as Carrington, puts it, those spaces of educational development open the door to the inspiration of new ones. Our first example will focus on collaborative processes involving technology. Its context is the kind of research carried out during the first years of the 21st century, when the integration of technology helped to carry out analyses of collaboration as a didactic tool and the design of spaces for the development of digital environments: what at that time was called, and still is, CSCL, an approach that facilitated the integration into the educational experience of different types of technological environments, as well as collaborative processes based on the use of digital-platform technology. This study was based on a process of innovation in the Computer Architecture subject within the Telematics Engineering studies at the University of Valladolid, where students had to start working in groups and by means of the project technique. In this case, and by resorting to the BSCW platform, we developed instructional dynamics informed by face-to-face processes and technological aids. This innovative experience made it possible to show the importance of group processes for the development of professional knowledge in a collaborative dynamic in the training of computer engineers. The results of this action were researched and evaluated with a mixed enquiry design. The role that technology played in the follow-up and evaluation of such an innovative practice was crucial.

Additionally, above all, the shift in the educational research perspective involved in this approach allowed for qualitative and quantitative processes that enriched and enabled analysis from complementary perspectives

Consequences for the Conception of the new model

To conclude, the contributions of these three studies, which could be just a few examples of how this type of design can help, represent advances in the analysis of innovation experiences. It is worth highlighting the contributions made by the automatic information collection systems, which in some way show us students' unconscious actions, as well as processes that influence educational dynamics and which are not usually considered. Another aspect has to do with the possibilities of contrasting the participants' visions when they are confronted with what they think they have done, and what the information reports made by the technology show them. Finally, the possibilities of analysing all levels of reality, which is more complex with technology. The practical consequences of technology-based educational innovation models have been clear to us for a long time. There are basically two main impacts on the classroom and the teachers which are worth stating here because of their relevance. The first implies that the classroom doors are no longer closed, but instead, access is provided to as much content as possible content that is ethically acceptable and complies with the principle of human rights. However, alongside this, there is the possibility that, if the professionals, the school institution or the parents do not survey this process of content construction, schools could become ethically unacceptable spaces. This is a fundamental consequence that challenges the teaching staff, who must become guides in the selection of the school's content. Additionally, in this guiding role-in the development of active methodologies teachers must be conductors and not wells of wisdom. However, are we equally perceptive about the evaluation and research processes involved in these innovative experiences? From the point of view of innovation, research and evaluation, we believe that these processes do not generally include the analysis of their value for potential improvement. It is much more common to engage in analyses of satisfaction, performance, or educational change, but not of the in-depth consequences of innovation on the basis of all available data. The evaluation of initiatives does not, in many cases, consider the possibilities provided by the rich space provided by the learning analytic community. This article has attempted to steer the debate along that path and to promote real changes in evaluation, monitoring and research processes, which are currently dispersed in terms of their results and value.

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Paper 3

**TRANSGENDER EMPOWERMENT THROUGH EDUCATION: ROLE OF HEI'S
WITH REFERENCE TO NEP-2020**

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ABSTRACT

The recognition of transgender rights and identities has progressed significantly, yet transgender individuals, particularly students, continue to face unique challenges in education. The article discusses the educational challenges faced by transgender individuals in India, highlighting the historical context of their recognition and the low literacy rate. It highlights discrimination, stigma, and limited access, lack of gender-sensitive facilities, mental health issues, and bullying. The Indian National Education Policy 2020 aims to promote inclusivity and equity through multidisciplinary curricula, equitable access, special education programs, and diversity. Higher education institutions are urged to implement non-discrimination policies, offer affirmative action, and create a welcoming campus climate. Collaboration among institutions, policymakers, and communities is crucial for empowering transgender individuals.

Keywords: Transgender, Inclusive, Discrimination, NEP-2020, Sensitization, HEI(s)

❖ Introduction

The recognition of the rights and identities of transgender individuals has increased in recent years, but challenges persist, especially in the realm of education. The article discusses the educational status of transgender individuals, highlighting their unique challenges in higher education. It emphasizes the importance of higher educational institutions in fostering inclusivity and support. Transgender individuals, who often identify with a different gender, were included in the 2011 census as a third group. The goal is to encourage a deeper understanding of these barriers and advocate for necessary changes to make higher education more welcoming and equitable. The census included only male and female gender categories, with no option for a third gender. However, the Indian Supreme Court accepted transgender people as a third gender in 2014, confirming their inclusion in the population count (**Pallav Das, 2019**). India's transgender population is around 4, 87,803 with a literacy rate of 57.06%. In 2011, there were 54,854 transgender children below six. The NEP-2020 aims to empower transgender education and dismantle age-

old barriers. The national education policy draft, released in March 2019, was approved by the government on July 29, 2020. The revised policy aims to promote transformation and holistic growth in education, replacing the 34-year-old policy. **(Thakur, P., & Kumar, R. 2020)**. The Indian National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 recognizes the discrimination and special difficulties faced by transgender students and seek to advance their inclusion and assistance. It highlights how important it is to create a more equal and inclusive learning environment. The promotion of transgender empowerment through education is emphasized in this article by higher education establishments.

❖ Status of Transgender Education in India

The educational status of transgender students in India is a significant issue, as they lack understanding of their identity and are considered the third or new gender in the Indian Constitution. Their lack of social and cultural engagement restricts access to public spaces, healthcare, and education, violating their constitutional rights to equality and protection under the law. **(Ashok Raj, 2019)**.

The 2011 Indian census marked the first time transgender persons were included in the census, marking a significant shift in the classification of genders. Previously, only male and female were included in the census. However, in 2014, India's Supreme Court recognized transgender persons as a third gender. Despite this, transgender individuals continue to pursue education, demonstrating their right to education under the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. **(Vats, N.K 2017)**. Additionally, the census showed that the transgender community had a low literacy rate 46% compared to the general population's 74%. The low literacy rate among transgender is a result of their persecution and prosecution.

❖ Educational Status

Transgender people in India lack a preferred education system, leading to a loss of family and educational environment, resulting in discontinuation of education and putting future employment at risk. Despite being predominantly illiterate or undereducated, they may become reticent to seek higher education due to low enrolment rates and high dropout rates. **(Raj Kumar, 2016)**.

❖ Problems of Transgender students

In India, the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 seeks to address a number of systemic concerns, among them the acceptance and assistance of transgender students. The NEP highlights the need for a more inclusive and equitable learning environment while acknowledging the particular difficulties and discrimination experienced by transgender students. According to the NEP 2020, transgender students face a number of issues, including:

1. Discrimination and Stigma: Transgender students frequently experience prejudice and stigma from their peers as well as from educators and school officials. The NEP recognizes that schools and colleges need to foster an environment that is more inclusive and non-discriminatory.

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2. Lack of Access to Education: Bullying, harassment, and a lack of acceptance and support from educational institutions are major causes of school dropout for transgender students. The goal of the NEP is to make education more accessible to everyone, including transgender people.

3. Absence of Gender-Sensitive Facilities: Restrooms and changing areas those are transgender or gender-neutral are commonplace in educational institutions. The NEP places a strong emphasis on the development of inclusive facilities and infrastructure.

4. Mental Health and Well-Being: The stress of discrimination and social rejection causes transgender students to frequently experience mental health issues. The NEP acknowledges that educational institutions require mental health support services.

5. Bullying and Harassment: Transgender students who experience bullying and Harassment may experience a decline in their self-worth and academic achievement. Strict anti-bullying policies and enforcement are emphasized by the NEP-2020.

❖ Challenges of the transgender students

Recognizing the particular difficulties faced by transgender students, India's National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 seeks to address these problems in order to build a more welcoming and equal learning environment. According to the NEP 2020, transgender students encounter a number of difficulties, such as:

1. **Limited Access to Education:** Due to societal discrimination, a lack of understanding, or a fear of harassment, many transgender people may have limited access to education, which can lead to lower enrolment and higher dropout rates.
2. **Lack of Sensitivity and Awareness:** When it comes to transgender issues, teachers and staff may not be sensitive enough, which can result in misgendering, insensitivity, and a lack of support for transgender students.
3. **Bullying and Harassment:** Transgender students are more likely to face violence, harassment, and bullying both inside and outside of the school, which has a detrimental effect on their mental and emotional health.
4. **Absence of an Inclusive Curriculum:** Transgender students are further alienated when educational materials and curricula fail to address transgender issues, history, or contributions.
5. **Gender-Insensitive Facilities:** The absence of gender-neutral changing areas and restrooms in many schools can cause transgender students to feel uncomfortable and subject to discrimination.
6. **Legal and Policy Gaps:** Transgender students may face obstacles in the form of trouble obtaining documents of identification that correspond to their gender identity or trouble applying for financial aid or scholarships due to legal and policy gaps.
7. **Lack of empathy and need for advice:** Pervasive societal norms and prejudice denounce transgender people by teachers. This insensitivity of teachers towards the transgender community negatively affects them. Most

members of the educational fraternity lack knowledge and sensitivity to transgender issues and are hesitant to provide education (Prakasha C., Jagannath K. Dange, 2023).

- 8. Inclusion in Schools, Colleges, and Universities:** Including transgender students in high school and college may present challenges. It is very challenging to provide transgender students with the same educational opportunities as other students of the same gender because of the inclusion issue with both male and female students. (Prakasha C., Jagannath K. Dange, et.al, 2022).

❖ Role of Higher Education Institutions (HEI's)

- 1. Multidisciplinary and Flexibility:** NEP 2020 promotes the adoption of a multidisciplinary approach and increased course structure flexibility in higher education institutions. This aids in meeting the needs and interests of a wide spectrum of students. Programs should be created by institutions to accommodate a diverse range of students, including those from underrepresented groups and those with disabilities.
- 2. Equitable Access:** The goal of inclusive education is to give everyone, regardless of gender, physical ability, or socioeconomic background, equitable access to high-quality education. Institutions of higher learning should endeavour to remove obstacles to admission, such as cost, location, and discriminatory policies.
- 3. Special Education Programs:** In order to support students with disabilities, higher education institutions must create special education programs, according to NEP 2020. To guarantee that no one is left behind, this may entail offering support services, accessible infrastructure, and assistive technologies.
- 4. Local Language and Culture:** In higher education, the policy promotes the use of local languages and cultures. Through fostering a connection with students' backgrounds and improving accessibility, this can contribute to the inclusiveness of education.
- 5. Diversity and Inclusion:** Academic institutions should make a concerted effort to increase the diversity of their faculty, staff, and student body. In order to foster an environment that is welcoming to everyone, they should also put anti-discrimination policies and practices into place.
- 6. Mentoring and Support:** To assist students in meeting their needs and making educated decisions, NEP 2020 recommends the creation of academic and career Counselling centres. This holds special significance for students hailing from underprivileged backgrounds.
- 7. Research and Innovation:** In order to better meet the needs and styles of a diverse student body, higher education institutions are expected to conduct research and innovate in the areas of pedagogy, technology, and teaching practices.
- 8. Teacher Training:** In order to give educators the tools they need to successfully serve a diverse student body, NEP 2020 suggests improving teacher training initiatives. Training in inclusive teaching techniques and strategies may fall under this category.

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9. Technology Use: Using technology to its full potential can help create a more inclusive learning environment. To guarantee accessibility for all students, higher education institutions should make investments in digital resources, assistive technologies, and online learning environments.

10. Community Engagement: Working together with non-governmental organizations and local communities can assist higher education institutions in reaching out to marginalized groups and promoting inclusivity in education at the local level.

11. Curriculum Development: Topics and issues pertaining to transgender people should be included in university curricula. Courses on LGBTQ+ studies, gender studies, and other pertinent topics can fall under this category. Universities give students the chance to learn about transgender issues and experiences by offering these kinds of courses.

12. Training for Faculty and Staff: Educating faculty and staff about transgender issues and inclusivity is crucial. By ensuring that faculty and staff are aware of the particular needs and challenges faced by transgender people, this training can help foster a more supportive environment for transgender students.

13. Support Services: Educational institutions ought to set up transgender student-specific support services. Counselling services, gender-neutral restrooms, and housing options that honour transgender students' gender identities are a few examples of this. The goal of these services is to establish a welcoming and safe campus community.

14. Non-Discrimination and Inclusivity: Academic institutions ought to proactively foster a culture that is both non-discriminatory and inclusive. This entails establishing guidelines and procedures that forbid prejudice against transgender students and guaranteeing that every student is accorded respect and dignity.

15. Affirmative Action and Scholarships: Universities can use affirmative action policies to promote access to higher education for transgender people and address historical disadvantages. For transgender students, they can also offer financial aid and scholarships tailored to their needs in order to support their academic endeavours.

16. Campus Climate: It's critical to establish a friendly campus environment. Events, workshops, and support groups that encourage acceptance, diversity, and inclusion can be arranged by universities. These programs help to create a welcoming environment for transgender students as well as all other students.

17. Collaboration: In order to jointly work towards establishing a more inclusive educational system and society, universities can collaborate with LGBTQ+ organizations, governmental bodies, and other institutions. Cooperation can support policy changes and assist in addressing systemic issues.

18. Examination fee exemption: Examining bodies such as UGC, UPSC, SSC, KPSC, NTA, KEA, and others ought to waive examination costs for transgender individuals, enabling them to take more exams and gain enhanced trust in their careers.

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19. Reimagining Vocational Education: To fully realize India's demographic dividend, this policy aims to achieve skills developed among at least 50% of learners through the school and higher education system by 2025. Over the next ten years, vocational education will be gradually introduced into all educational institutions. The selection of focus areas will be determined by mapping local opportunities and conducting a skills gap analysis. Technical and vocational education will be integrated into a broader liberal education framework. This decision will be overseen by the National Committee for the Integration of Vocational Education (NCIVE). With the support of a distinct "Vocational Education Inclusion Fund for Integration," this shift will be aided by cooperation between academic institutions, technical institutions, and companies (Sagar Shankar Borate, 2023).

20. Separate study centre: Transgender students' accomplishments can be accelerated by higher education institutions, universities, by setting up study chairs to examine their achievement culture and way of life.

21. Holding conferences and workshops: Transgender students are able to accomplish more when universities host national and international conferences, seminars, and workshops on transgenderism at these levels.

Conclusion

The article highlighted the challenges faced by transgender individuals in India, particularly in pursuing higher education. It highlights the historical lack of recognition and social exclusion, as well as the challenges they face, such as limited access to education and healthcare. It emphasized the need for systemic changes to overcome these challenges. Strategies for fostering inclusivity and support for transgender students include multidisciplinary approaches, equitable access, special education programs, promotion of local language and culture, diversity and inclusion efforts, mentoring and support services, research and innovation, teacher training, technology use, community engagement, curriculum development, support services, non-discrimination policies, affirmative action, research and advocacy, campus climate improvement, collaboration, examination fee exemption, reimagining vocational education, establishment of separate study centres, and hosting conferences and workshops. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is crucial in addressing these issues, including discrimination, lack of access to education, gender-sensitive facilities, mental health challenges, bullying, and harassment. The article calls for a comprehensive approach to creating a more inclusive and supportive educational environment for transgender students, addressing systemic challenges, and promoting positive changes at various levels of the education system to empower transgender students.

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**TRENDS IN EDUCATIONAL INNOVATION
INNOVATION TO INNOVATIVE PRACTICES**

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ABSTRACT

Every system needs change if we want to safeguard it from the threat of being stagnant. If the change is innovative, it leads to the qualitative improvement of the system. Same is true in case of education system. To have equality education system, change through innovation has to be initiated from the core part of the system teacher education. All other parts of the system will get the momentum to change accordingly. Possessing a key role in teacher professional preparation it is essential for teacher education institutions to be a seed bed of innovative educational ideas and nurturing them through continuous research and experimentation which will ultimately contribute to the quality enhancement of the system. For prospective teachers the subject was fundamentals of ‘instruction and assessment’ and for in-service teachers to is Instructional Theory’ Basically the constructivist approach used in these two courses attempted to build a student- centered, inquiry oriented collaborative learning environment to help students actively engaged in personal instructional theory building. The driver and Oldham’s constructivist’ model for curriculum development was used. For prospective teachers more emphasis was given on discussion of methods, principles and strategies. For in service teachers, it is on reexamination of theories into practices. In short, the cause was designed with an attempt to stimulate inquiry reflection and construction and restructuring of prospective and in-service teacher’s knowledge base of teaching.

Key words: Education, Innovative practices, Approaches and learning theories.

Innovation and innovative practices: Innovation:

Innovation is about ideas and the transformation of those ideas into value creation outcomes-into products, processes and services. Innovations include break through ideas that lead to new products or services and incremental ideas which improve the way processes are undertaken or products are manufactured. Innovation is about the creation of new knowledge and the use of that knowledge (National innovation website 2006)

Innovative practices:

New and creative approaches in education involving all stake holders through self-regulated internal quality assurance system of higher education institution & adopting inclusive aimed to promote academic excellence & effective human resource development (Operational definition given by NAAC).

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Phases of innovation:

According to Cheng, the attempts of quality improvement in the system undergo through three phases.

1. Internal effectiveness
2. Interface effectiveness
3. Future Effectiveness.

It can be said that we are at present in the third phase of educational reforms. The prominent features of today's world i.e. the worldwide changes due to liberalization, privatization and globalization, the rise of ICT as a learning technology, shift of learning theories from behaviorism to constructivism etc. provide the relevant context for innovation.

At stage 3 and 4 the complexity of the system goes on increasing, thereby affecting the expected outcome of the innovation.

Below is a case of a research from Taiwan, in which theory and instructional strategies of constructivism were used for pre-service and in-service teacher education programmes.

Example of Chen Sharon's research:

Chen Sharon employed an action to explore the meaning and possibilities of implementing a constructivist teaching approach to professional development courses for teacher education in Taiwan. This study was conducted for two years (1995-97).

Objectives:

- To explore the meaning of infusing constructivist perspectives to professional development courses.
- To understand what the prospective and in-service teachers think about constructivist views on teaching and learning.
- To evaluate the impact of implementation of a constructivist teaching approach on prospective and in-service teachers.
- To clarify the embedded factors that may influence prospective and in-service teachers' practice of constructivist teaching approaches in elementary classrooms.

Programme Input:

For prospective teachers the subject was fundamentals of 'instruction and assessment' and for in-service teachers it is 'Instructional Theory'. Basically the constructivist approach used in these two courses attempted to build a student-centered, inquiry-oriented collaborative learning environment to help students actively engaged in personal instructional theory building. The Driver and Oldham's constructivist model for curriculum development was used. For prospective teachers more emphasis was given on discussion of methods, principles and strategies. For in-service teachers, it is on re-examination of theories into practices.

Findings:

- Many prospective teachers were found turning from passive information receivers to active knowledge inquirers from a perfunctory attitude to a more serious attitude toward learning.
- Infused with a constructivist perspective, the inquiry-oriented collaborative learning tasks applied in the course did challenge prospective teachers' learning habits.

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- The constructivist approach applied in the course not only helped shape prospective teachers knowledge about teaching and learning, but also helped increase their understanding of what would promote effective teaching and productive learning.
- Changes among in-service teachers were from uneasiness to awareness, adjustment reflection and self-growth.
- In-service teachers began to become aware of the strength of constructivist teaching and collaborative learning.
- In-service teachers started self-reflection.

According to him, factors influencing the practice of a constructivist approach in professional courses are instructional activities situated learning tasks supportive feedback and encouragement the climate in peer interactions degree of openness toward new things ideas. Contextual problems faced by him were student's ability and motivation school culture that treasures “Quietness”, large classroom size unified curricular plan and assessment.

Innovation id innovative practice through kaizen and reflection:

Why kaizen and reflection? Kaizen a Japanese way of improving a process. It includes continuous improvement and involving every one of the system in it. Reflection or reflective thinking leads us to think critically and creatively about any situation or problem. According to schoon, there are two kinds of reflection– reflection in action and reflection action. This reflection on action i.e. thinking after the situation (a proactive step of self–change) helps in providing a constructive feedback. Hence the author found it appropriate to introduce it before and after stage 3. This will increase the effectiveness of the innovative process thereby adding quality to the system with low energy (human and material resources) dissipation.

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Paper 5

ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗ: ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆ

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ಸಾರಾಂಶ:

ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಸ್ಥೂಲವಾಗಿ ಅರಿಯುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳು ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಮಟ್ಟದ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ಮತ್ತು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂದು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಲು, ಈ ಲೇಖನವು ಆಲೋಚನೆಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡುವ ವಿಧಾನವು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಪರಿಣಾಮವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಲು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ಬಳಸಬೇಕು ಮತ್ತು ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಈ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ಬೆಳೆಸಬೇಕು ಎಂಬ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗಬೇಕು. ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಪ್ರಧಾನ ಅಂಶಗಳು ಕೆಲವು ಮುಖ್ಯ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ಆವರಿಸಲ್ಪಡುತ್ತವೆ. ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವನ್ನು ಈ ಲೇಖನದ ಮೂಲಕ ನಾವು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ. ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಪರಿಣಾಮವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಲು ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳ ಉಪಯೋಗವನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಬಳಸಬೇಕು ಎಂಬ ವಿಚಾರಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಆಲೋಚನೆ ನಡೆಸಲಾಗಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಮತ್ತು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ಬೀರುವ ಪ್ರಭಾವಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಶೀಲಿಸಲು ಉಪಯುಕ್ತವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಕೀಲಿ ಪದಗಳು: ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ, ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗ, ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ.

ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಎಂದರೆ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಅರಿಯುವುದಲ್ಲದೆ, ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸಲು ಹೇಗೆ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಿಸಬೇಕು ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಅರಿತುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಕೌಶಲವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುತ್ತದೆ (ಸ್ಮಿತ್, ೨೦೨೩). ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳ ಅನುಸರಣೆಯಿಂದ, ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ವಿಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸುಲಭವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಯೋಗಿಸಬಹುದು ಮತ್ತು ಅವುಗಳ ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸಬಲ್ಲರು. ಇದು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ವಿಸ್ತಾರವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಸ್ವಾಗತಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಉನ್ನತ ಮಟ್ಟದ ಸಾಧನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರದರ್ಶಿಸುತ್ತದೆ (ಜೋನ್ಸ್, ೨೦೨೨). ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮತ್ತು ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ಮುಖ್ಯ ದಾಯಿತ್ವವಾಗಿದೆ. ಅವರು ಸಂಶೋಧನಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಪ್ರಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ಹೊರತುಪಡಿಸಿ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ಕುರಿತು ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಅರಿವಿಗೆ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿ ಸಾಮಗ್ರಿಗಳನ್ನು ಉಪಯೋಗಿಸಿ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸಬಹುದು, ಇದು ಅವರ ಅಭಿರುಚಿಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುವ ವಿಧಾನವಾಗಿದೆ (ಬ್ರೌನ್, ೨೦೨೧). ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳ ಅನುಸರಣೆ ಮತ್ತು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಹೊಂದಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯ ಅಗತ್ಯವಾದ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲೊಂದಾಗಿವೆ. ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಸಮರ್ಥವಾದ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕೊಡಲು ಬರುವ ಸುವರ್ಣ ಅವಕಾಶವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಪ್ರಯತ್ನಗಳು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ತರಬೇತಿಗೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಭವಿಷ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಅವರು ಕಲ್ಪಿಸಿದ ಸಾಧನೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಸಿದ್ಧತೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಬಹುದು.

ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಎಂದರೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನದ ಹೊರತು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಸಂಗ್ರಹಣೆ ಮಾತ್ರವಲ್ಲ; ಅದು ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಯ ನಿರ್ವಹಣೆ, ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಣೆ, ಮತ್ತು ವಿಮರ್ಶೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ತಕ್ಕಡಿಯಾದ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯ ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತದೆ (ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಆಕಾಡೆಮಿ, ೨೦೨೦). ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮತ್ತು ಅನುಭವದ ಹೊರತು, ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಸ್ವರೂಪ ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿರುವುದು. ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ವಿವಿಧ ಪ್ರಯೋಗಾಲಯಗಳ ಪರಿಶೀಲನೆ, ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಕಲಿಕೆಯು ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಅಭಿಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ವೃದ್ಧಿಸುತ್ತವೆ (ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರ ಪ್ರಮುಖರು, ೨೦೧೧).

ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗ:

ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ "ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗ" ಎಂದರೆ ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಟೆಕ್ನಾಲಜಿಗಳ ವಿಸ್ತಾರವಾದ ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಕಾಲವನ್ನು ಸೂಚಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದು ಕಂಪ್ಯೂಟರ್‌ಗಳು, ಇಂಟರ್‌ನೆಟ್, ಮತ್ತು ಮೊಬೈಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ಹಾಗೂ ಅವುಗಳ ಸಹಾಯದಿಂದ ಸಮಾಜದ ವಿವಿಧ ಹಂತಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಆಳವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಭಾವಿಸುವ ಕಾಲದ ಅರ್ಥವನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿದೆ (ಭಾಟ್, ೨೦೧೮). ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿ, ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗ ಅನ್ನು ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಹೇಗೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ವ್ಯತ್ಯಾಸಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಹೇಗೆ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಹೊಂದಿದ ಅನುಭವಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಪ್ರಭಾವಶಾಲಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಅನುಭವಗಳನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ ಎಂಬುದು ಹೊರತುಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾದ ಪ್ರಯೋಜನಗಳನ್ನು ಕುರಿತು ಮಾಹಿತಿ ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ (ವಿಜಯಲಕ್ಷ್ಮಿ, ೨೦೨೦). ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹತ್ವದ ವಿಷಯವನ್ನು ಚರ್ಚಿಸುವಾಗ ಶಾಸ್ತ್ರೀಯ ಆಧಾರದ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆಯಿದೆ. ಇದನ್ನು ಸಮರ್ಥಿಸಲು ಕೆಲವು ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಂದರ್ಭಗಳ ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಗಳನ್ನು ನೀಡಬಹುದು:

- **ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರವೃತ್ತಿಗಳ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆ:** ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನೇಕ ಅವಕಾಶಗಳನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತವೆ, ಹೆಚ್ಚು ರಚನಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಭ್ಯಾಸ ಮಾಡಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ನೀಡುತ್ತವೆ.
- **ಸಹಕಾರಿತ್ವ ಮತ್ತು ಸಹಭಾಗಿತ್ವ:** ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ಸಹಕಾರಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಹಭಾಗಿತ್ವದ ಭಾವನೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುತ್ತವೆ, ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಸಹ ತಮ್ಮ ಜ್ಞಾನಾಧಾರವನ್ನು ವೃದ್ಧಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮೊದಲಿನಿಂದಲೂ ಪಾಲ್ಗೊಳ್ಳುವುದು.
- **ಸಾಂಕೇತಿಕ ಜ್ಞಾನದ ಅಭ್ಯಾಸ:** ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಾಂಕೇತಿಕ ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಅಭ್ಯಾಸ ಮಾಡುವ ಅವಕಾಶ ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತವೆ, ಇದು ಅವರ ತಿಳಿವಳಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ವೃದ್ಧಿಸುವುದು.
- **ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕೀಕರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರತಿಸ್ಪಂದನಶೀಲ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ:** ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕೀಕರಣವನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತವೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರ ಹೊಸ ಕಲೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕಂಡುಹಿಡಿಯುವಲ್ಲಿ ಅನುಭವದ ಸಾಧ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತವೆ.
- **ಹೊಸ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಪದ್ಧತಿಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳು:** ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ಹೊಸ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಪದ್ಧತಿಗಳ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳ ಅನ್ವಯನದಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸುತ್ತವೆ.
- **ಹೊಸ ಜ್ಞಾನ ಮತ್ತು ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನದ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ:** ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಹೊಸ ಜ್ಞಾನ ಮತ್ತು ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತವೆ.
- **ವೈಶಿಷ್ಟ್ಯಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಪ್ರತಿಸ್ಪಂದಿಸುವ ಕ್ಷಮತೆ:** ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ವೈಶಿಷ್ಟ್ಯಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಪ್ರತಿಸ್ಪಂದಿಸುವ ಕ್ಷಮತೆಯನ್ನು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಸುತ್ತವೆ.

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- **ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರತೆ:** ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಗಳಕ್ಷರಗಳ ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಮತ್ತು ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರತೆಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತವೆ, ಅವರ ತಮ್ಮ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಸ್ಯಾಪರಿಹಾರ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯವಾಗಿ ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಒದಗಿಸುತ್ತವೆ.

ಈ ಅಂಶಗಳು ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುವ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡುತ್ತವೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಅನುಭವವನ್ನು ವೃದ್ಧಿಸುತ್ತವೆ.

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ವಿಕಾಸ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದಲ್ಲಿ:

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಬೆಳೆಯುತ್ತಿರುವ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆಯು ಕೇವಲ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನದ ಸುಲಭವಾದ ಅರಿವಿನ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಅಲ್ಲ, ಅದು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಅರಿವು ಹೊಂದಲು ಬದ್ಧವಾದ ಕೌಶಲವನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆ ಹಿಂದಿನಿಂದ ಹೊರಹೊಮ್ಮಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಅದು ಹೆಚ್ಚಾಗಿ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಲೇಖನದಲ್ಲಿ, ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ವಿಕಾಸದ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಹಂತಗಳನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಈ ಹಂತಗಳು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಗೆ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಉಂಟುಮಾಡಿದೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟಪಡಿಸಲಾಗಿದೆ;

- **ಅಂಶಗಳ ಪರಿಚಯ:** ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಕೇಂದ್ರಿತಗೊಳಿಸಲು ಮೊದಲ ಹಂತಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಾರಂಭಿಸುವುದು ಅಗತ್ಯ. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ವಿಜ್ಞಾನದ ಅನೇಕ ಮೌಲಿಕ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಅರಿಯುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವುದು ಅವರ ವಿಕಾಸಕ್ಕೆ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ (ಶೆಟ್ಟಿ, ೨೦೨೨).
- **ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹ:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಪ್ರವೃತ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಲು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹ ನೀಡುವ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು ಮುಖ್ಯ. ಅವರು ತಮ್ಮ ಸ್ವಂತ ಆಲೋಚನಾ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ಅನ್ವೇಷಿಸಬೇಕು ಎಂಬುದರ ಮೂಲಕ ಅವರು ತಮ್ಮ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯನ್ನು ಮುಂದುವರಿಸಬಹುದು (ಕುಮಾರ್, ೨೦೨೦).
- **ಅನ್ವೇಷಣೆಯ ಸಾಧನಗಳ ಉಪಯೋಗ:** ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಅನ್ವೇಷಣೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುವುದು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಅಗತ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಆಧುನಿಕ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ತಂತ್ರಾಂಶಗಳ ಬಳಕೆಯಿಂದ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ವಿಜ್ಞಾನದ ನೂತನ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳನ್ನು ಅನ್ವೇಷಿಸಬಹುದು ಹಾಗೂ ತಮ್ಮ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಮೇಲೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಹೊಣೆಯಬಹುದು (ಗೋವಿಂದ, ೨೦೨೩).
- **ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ಪಾತ್ರ:** ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ಪಾತ್ರ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಮುಖ್ಯ. ಅವರು ಉತ್ತಮ ಸಾಧನಗಳನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ಕುರಿತು ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸುವ ಉಪಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ಕಲಿಸಬಹುದು (ರಾಜು, ೨೦೨೧).
- **ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ವಿಧಾನ:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಗೆ ಸುಲಭವಾದ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕವಾಗಿ ಹೊಂದಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಮುಖ್ಯ. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಹೊಸ ಅನ್ವೇಷಣೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಆಳವಾಗಿ ಹೋಗಬಹುದು ಮತ್ತು ಅವುಗಳ ಪ್ರಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸಬಹುದು (ಶರ್ಮಾ, ೨೦೨೨).

ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವುದು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾದ ಕೆಲಸವಾಗಿದೆ. ಆದರೆ ಈ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹಲವಾರು ಸವಾಲುಗಳು ಎದುರಾಗುತ್ತಿವೆ.

ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಸವಾಲುಗಳು:

- **ತಪ್ಪು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ಹರಡುವಿಕೆ:** ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಮಾಧ್ಯಮ ಮತ್ತು ಇಂಟರ್‌ನೆಟ್‌ನಲ್ಲಿ ತಪ್ಪು ಮಾಹಿತಿ ವೈರಲ್ ಆಗುವುದು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕವಾಗಿ ಸಾಬೀತಾಗಿಲ್ಲದ ಹಲವಾರು ವಿಷಯಗಳು ಸತ್ಯವೆಂದು ಪರಿಗಣಿಸಲ್ಪಡುತ್ತಿವೆ. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಚಿಂತನೆ ಬೆಳೆಯುವುದು ಕಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತಿದೆ.

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- **ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನದ ಅತಿಯಾದ ಬಳಕೆ:** ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನವು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದು ಉಪಕರಣವಾಗಿದ್ದರೂ, ಅದರ ಅತಿಯಾದ ಬಳಕೆ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ನಿಷ್ಕ್ರಿಯಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಅವರು ಸ್ವತಃ ಯೋಚಿಸುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸುವುದನ್ನು ಕಡಿಮೆ ಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ.
- **ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಪದಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತಗಳನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಲ್ಲಿನ ತೊಂದರೆ:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಪದಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತಗಳು ಸಾಮಾನ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಜಟಿಲವಾಗಿರುತ್ತವೆ. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಇವುಗಳನ್ನು ಸರಳವಾಗಿ ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಕಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.
- **ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿನ ಕೊರತೆ:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ವಿಧಾನವು ಒಂದು ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥಿತವಾದ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಯಾಗಿದೆ. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಈ ವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸುವುದು ಹೇಗೆ ಎಂದು ಕಲಿಸುವುದು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಮುಖ್ಯ. ಆದರೆ ಇದು ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರಿಗೆ ಸವಾಲಾಗಿರುತ್ತದೆ.
- **ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಜಾಗೃತಿಯ ಕೊರತೆ:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯು ನಮ್ಮ ದೈನಂದಿನ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಎಷ್ಟು ಮುಖ್ಯ ಎಂಬುದರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಜನರಿಗೆ ಅರಿವಿಲ್ಲ. ಇದರಿಂದಾಗಿ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಜಿಜ್ಞಾಸೆ ಬೆಳೆಯುವುದು ಕಷ್ಟವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ.

ಈ ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ನಿಭಾಯಿಸಬಹುದು?

- **ತಪ್ಪು ಮಾಹಿತಿಯ ವಿರುದ್ಧ ಹೋರಾಟ:** ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸುವ ಮತ್ತು ಮೌಲ್ಯಮಾಪನ ಮಾಡುವ ಕೌಶಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಕಲಿಸಬೇಕು.
- **ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಸರಿಯಾಗಿ ಬಳಸುವುದು:** ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಕೇವಲ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯುವ ಸಾಧನವಾಗಿ ಮಾತ್ರ ಬಳಸದೆ, ಅದನ್ನು ಕಲಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಸುಧಾರಿಸಲು ಬಳಸಬೇಕು.
- **ಸರಳ ಭಾಷೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗಳನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸುವುದು:** ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸುಲಭವಾಗಿ ಅರ್ಥವಾಗುವ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಪದಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತಗಳನ್ನು ವಿವರಿಸಬೇಕು.
- **ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕವಾಗಿ ಕಲಿಸುವುದು:** ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ಅನುಸರಿಸುವುದನ್ನು ಕಲಿಸಲು ಪ್ರಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸಬೇಕು.
- **ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಜಾಗೃತಿ ಮೂಡಿಸುವುದು:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯು ನಮ್ಮ ದೈನಂದಿನ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಎಷ್ಟು ಮುಖ್ಯ ಎಂಬುದರ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಜನರಲ್ಲಿ ಜಾಗೃತಿ ಮೂಡಿಸಬೇಕು.

ಈ ಸವಾಲುಗಳನ್ನು ನಿಭಾಯಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ನಾವು ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸಬಹುದು ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತಮ ಭವಿಷ್ಯವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸಬಹುದು. ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯನ್ನು ಅನೇಕ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಗಳು ಒತ್ತಿಹೇಳಿವೆ. ಉದಾಹರಣೆಗೆ, OECD (೨೦೧೬) ನ ಪಿಐಎಸಿಎ ೨೦೧೫ ಫಲಿತಾಂಶಗಳು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಮತ್ತು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆ ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಯ ನಡುವಿನ ಸಂಬಂಧವನ್ನು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ತೋರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ಹಾಗೆಯೇ, National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (೨೦೧೭) ನ ವರದಿ, ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯನ್ನು ಕೇವಲ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಪಾಠಗಳಿಗೆ ಸೀಮಿತವಲ್ಲದೆ, ಎಲ್ಲಾ ವಿಷಯಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಂಯೋಜಿಸಬೇಕು ಎಂದು ಸೂಚಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ಬೆಳೆಸುವುದು?

- **ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕ ಕಲಿಕೆ:** ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುವುದು.
- **ಸಮಸ್ಯಾಧಾರಿತ ಕಲಿಕೆ:** ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ನಿಜ ಜೀವನದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುವುದು.
- **ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು:** ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದಲ್ಲಿ ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಕಲ್ಪನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸರಳವಾಗಿ ವಿವರಿಸುವುದು.

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- ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವನ್ನು ಓದುವುದು: ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಸಂಬಂಧಿತ ಪುಸ್ತಕಗಳು, ನಿಯತಕಾಲಿಕೆಗಳು ಇತ್ಯಾದಿಗಳನ್ನು ಓದಲು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುವುದು.
- ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಸಂಬಂಧಿತ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವುದು: ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಮೇಳಗಳು, ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಪ್ರದರ್ಶನಗಳು ಇತ್ಯಾದಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವುದು.

ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ:

ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆಯ ಸಾಧನೆಗೆ ಬಳಸಲಾಗುವ ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಮತ್ತು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಗಾಢ ಪ್ರಭಾವ ಬೀರುತ್ತವೆ. ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಈ ಸಾಧನಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯುವಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಆಸಕ್ತಿ ತೋರುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಇವರಿಗೆ ಅನುಕೂಲಕರ ವಾತಾವರಣವನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸಲು ಸಹಾಯಮಾಡುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಆದರೆ ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳ ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ಬಳಕೆಯ ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಮಾರ್ಗಗಳನ್ನು ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ತಿಳಿಯಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕ್ರಮದಲ್ಲಿ ಇವುಗಳನ್ನು ಸಾರ್ವಜನಿಕವಾಗಿ ಅಳವಡಿಸಲು ಅವರು ಸಿದ್ಧರಾಗಿರಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಈ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ, ನಾವು ಸೂಚಿಸುತ್ತೇವೆ ಕೊನೆಯ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಮಾಡಲು ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಕ್ರಮದಲ್ಲಿ ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳ ವಿನಿಮಯವನ್ನು ಬಲಪಡಿಸುವ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ಮೂಲಕ ಅನುಮೋದನೆಯಾಗುವುದು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಾಗಿದೆ.

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Paper 6

HAPPINESS IN LEARNING: ENHANCING THE LEARNING INTEREST

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ABSTRACT

In modern education, there is a growing recognition of the pivotal roles played by happiness and interest, which profoundly influence students' educational paths. Creating a positive and emotional environment within educational settings has been found to enhance motivation and academic achievement significantly. The paper entails the important theories like Barbara Fredrickson's broaden-and-build theory, which posits that positive emotions broaden individuals' thought-action repertoires, fostering creativity and problem-solving abilities. Furthermore, theories such as Deci and Ryan's self-determination theory highlights the importance of intrinsic motivation derived from personal satisfaction and fulfillment in educational pursuits. Conversely, environments lacking in positive emotional experiences, characterized by negative emotions like anxiety and boredom, can hinder cognitive processes and diminish learning outcomes. Understanding these dynamics is essential for educators and policymakers striving to create learning environments that not only optimize academic performance but also promote students' emotional well-being and lifelong learning skills.

Keywords: Happiness, Interest, Positive Emotions, Intrinsic Motivation, Broaden-And-Build Theory, Self-Determination Theory.

Introduction:

In the scenery of education, the concepts of happiness and interest are increasingly recognized as critical factors that significantly influence learning outcomes. Beyond the traditional metrics of grades and test scores, fostering a positive emotional environment within educational settings has been linked to enhanced motivation and academic achievement (Fredrickson, 2001). When students experience positive emotions, such as happiness and curiosity, during their learning journey, they are more likely to engage actively with the material, persist through challenges, and ultimately, achieve deeper understanding (Pekrun et al., 2002).

According to the broaden-and-build theory of positive emotions proposed by Barbara Fredrickson (2001),

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positive emotions broaden individuals' thought-action repertoires, allowing them to explore new ideas and concepts more freely. This theory suggests that by cultivating positive emotional experiences in educational contexts, educators can create an environment conducive to expansive learning and creative problem-solving (Fredrickson, 2001). Moreover, positive emotions are closely associated with increased cognitive flexibility and improved memory retention, facilitating a more effective learning process (Fredrickson, 2001). When students find happy and interest in what they are learning, they are more likely to take ownership of their learning journey, set higher goals, and persist in the face of setbacks (Deci & Ryan, 2008).

Conversely, environments lacking in positive emotional experiences can have detrimental effects on student engagement and achievement. Pekrun et al. (2002) emphasize that negative emotions, such as anxiety and boredom, can hinder cognitive processes and impede effective learning. When students feel stressed or disinterested, their ability to concentrate and retain information diminishes, leading to suboptimal learning outcomes (Pekrun et al., 2002).

Interest in Learning:

Interest plays a fundamental role in the learning process, shaping how individuals engage with knowledge and acquire new skills. Defined as a psychological state characterized by attention, curiosity, and a desire to learn more about a particular subject or activity (Hidi & Renninger, 2006), interest motivates learners to explore and delve deeper into topics, fostering meaningful and sustained engagement (Ainley, Hidi, & Berndorff, 2002). According to Renninger and Hidi (2016), interest is not merely a passive emotion but a dynamic cognitive and affective state that evolves through interactions with the learning environment.

Several factors influence individual interests, spanning personal, environmental, and educational domains. Personal factors include intrinsic motivation, prior knowledge, and individual preferences (Krapp, 2002). Learners are more likely to develop sustained interest in subjects that align with their personal passions and intrinsic motivations (Deci & Ryan, 2008). Environmental factors, such as family support, peer influence, and cultural norms, also shape individuals' interests by providing external sources of encouragement and validation (Hidi & Renninger, 2006). Furthermore, educational factors such as teaching methods, curriculum design, and classroom climate significantly impact students' interest development (Hidi & Renninger, 2006). Effective educators recognize the importance of creating learning environments that stimulate curiosity, encourage exploration, and cater to diverse interests and learning styles (Renninger & Hidi, 2016).

The Psychology of Happiness in Learning:

Happiness in learning is a complex phenomenon influenced by various psychological theories and

educational practices. Positive psychology emphasizes the role of positive emotions, engagement, and meaning in fostering happiness (Seligman, 2002). According to Seligman, when students experience positive emotions such as joy and satisfaction during their learning experiences, they are more likely to be motivated and engaged in their studies (Seligman, 2011). Self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985) provides further insights into how autonomy, competence, and relatedness contribute to students' intrinsic motivation and well-being in educational settings. Deci and Ryan argue that when students feel they have choices (autonomy), perceive themselves as capable of mastering tasks (competence), and have supportive relationships (relatedness), they are more likely to experience greater happiness and satisfaction in their learning endeavors (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Happy learning encompasses creating* a supportive and positive emotional environment where students feel valued and encouraged (Bhavya. R & Dange, J. K. 2020).

Flow theory, proposed by Csikszentmihalyi (1990), suggests that optimal learning occurs when students are fully immersed and deeply engaged in activities that challenge their skills. When tasks are sufficiently challenging yet within the learner's capabilities, they can experience a state of flow characterized by intense focus and enjoyment, leading to enhanced learning outcomes and feelings of happiness (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997). Constructivist theories of learning, such as those by Piaget (1952) and Vygotsky (1978), emphasize the active role of learners in constructing their understanding of knowledge through interaction with the environment and social interactions. By engaging in hands-on activities, collaborative projects, and reflective practices, students not only deepen their understanding but also experience a sense of accomplishment and satisfaction, contributing to their happiness in learning (Jonassen, 1991).

Happy teaching-learning components play a crucial role in both personal growth and academic achievement by fostering positive emotional experiences, intrinsic motivation, and a supportive learning environment (Bhavya. R & Dange, J. K. 2021).

Challenges to enhance interest in happy learning classrooms:

Challenges arise from navigating diverse student needs, managing classroom dynamics, and addressing institutional constraints while promoting engagement and well-being effectively as follows;

- **Curriculum Constraints:** Often, curriculum requirements and standardized testing can dictate the content and pace of instruction. This can sometimes limit opportunities for teachers to incorporate more creative and engaging activities that promote happiness and intrinsic motivation in teach (Darling-Hammond, 2007).
- **Time Constraints:** Teachers often face time constraints, needing to cover a vast amount of content within a limited timeframe. This pressure can make it challenging to allocate sufficient time for interactive and experiential learning activities that enhance engagement and happiness (OECD, 2019).

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- **Classroom Management:** Maintaining classroom discipline and managing behavior can be a significant challenge. Disruptions or a lack of order in the classroom can detract from the learning experience and hinder students' ability to engage fully and find joy in learning (Jones & Jones, 2016).
- **Student Motivation Levels:** Not all students may be equally motivated or interested in learning at all times. Factors such as personal interests, home environment, and socio-economic background can impact students' motivation levels and their receptiveness to engaging in learning activities (Pintrich & Schunk, 2002).
- **Teacher Training and Support:** Teachers frequently face inadequate training and support for implementing strategies that promote happiness and engagement in learning, with limited professional development opportunities focused on fostering positive emotions and intrinsic motivation (Guskey, 2002).

Collaboration among educators, administrators, policymakers, and communities is crucial for addressing challenges in creating happy learning environments. Ongoing professional development for teachers, supportive school environments, and flexible curricular frameworks are key components to foster academic success and student well-being.

Strategies to Enhance Learning Interest:

To enhance learning interest and promote a sense of happiness in the learning process, educators can employ several effective strategies. These strategies are rooted in principles from positive psychology, engagement theory, and cognitive psychology:

- **Create Positive Learning Environments:** Foster a classroom atmosphere that is supportive, encouraging, and inclusive. Positive relationships between teachers and students, as well as among peers, contribute to a sense of belonging and happiness (Seligman, 2011).
- **Personalize Learning Experiences:** Recognize and accommodate students' individual interests, learning styles, and strengths. (Deci & Ryan, 1985).
- **Promote Active Learning:** Encourage hands-on activities, collaborative projects, and discussions that stimulate curiosity and critical thinking. (Jonassen, 1991).
- **Set Clear Goals and Provide Feedback:** Clearly communicate learning objectives and expectations. Regular feedback that is constructive and specific helps students track their progress and understand how they can improve, which boosts confidence and motivation (Hattie & Timperley, 2007).
- **Integrate Technology Thoughtfully:** Utilize technology tools and resources that enhance learning experiences and facilitate interactive and personalized learning. (Mishra & Koehler, 2006).

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- **Cultivate a Growth Mindset:** Encourage a belief that abilities and intelligence can be developed through effort and learning. (Dweck, 2006).

Implementing these strategies integrates positive psychology, engagement theory, and cognitive psychology to cultivate learning environments that enhance both academic achievement and student happiness and well-being. This holistic approach aims to make learning effective, enjoyable, and personally meaningful for students.

Conclusion:

Integrating happiness and interest into education enhances student engagement and academic success through insights from positive psychology, self-determination theory, and learning theories. Despite challenges like diverse learning preferences and curriculum constraints, supporting teachers and adapting practices can create classrooms where emotional well-being and academic achievement thrive, equipping students with skills that extend beyond academics.

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Paper 7

**LEADERSHIP SKILLS AND JOB PERFORMANCE OF HEADMASTERS IN
SECONDARY SCHOOLS OF KERALA**

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ABSTRACT

The present study intends to correlate the leadership skills and job performance of Headmasters in secondary schools of Kerala. The main objective of the present study is to find the relationship between leadership skills and job performance of Headmasters in secondary schools of Kerala. The tool used for the study was Leadership Skills Scale and Job Performance Scale developed and standardised by the investigator. The study discourses that leadership skill of headmasters is a powerful tool to meet the changing needs of education in the context of a global economy. The result of the study revealed that there is positive correlation between leadership skills and job performance of Headmasters at secondary school level. The study suggests that if headmasters are timely assisted with leadership training programmes, it will help to improve the job performance of them and thereby they can support student as well as teachers in academic success, and enhance the quality of school education.

Keywords: Leadership skills, Job performance, Headmaster, Secondary schools.

Introduction:

Leadership is a basic element of education. A great leader can inspire entire community. His influence radiates, and he exemplifies in his own life and ideas of education for the successful implementation of the educational programme. Leadership is a dynamic relationship based on mutual influence and common purpose between leaders and collaborators in which both are moved to higher levels of motivation and moral development as they affect real, intended change. The degree to which the individual exhibits leadership traits depends not only on his characteristics and personal abilities but also on the characteristics of the situation and environment in which he finds himself (Messick & Kramer, 2004). The headmasters, the supervisor, classroom teacher, and the administrator should assume leadership. The quality of leadership is one of those main criteria which helps in better job performance.

Autocratic, Democratic, and Laissez-Faire are the commonly practiced leadership styles by the principals in schools. In democratic leadership the principal is directly involved in decision making of the school.

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The headmaster will give all the directions and suggestions that the teachers and students must follow. Otherwise, it can be said that in autocratic leadership the headmasters are authoritative in nature, According to John (2002) autocratic leader merely gives instructions to group members on how to execute tasks in a given manner, and they avoid establishing obvious lines of communication between employees and followers. Furthermore, these executives never enable employees or other types of workers to participate in the development of organizational policies. If the principal is democratic in nature, he will give shared importance to teachers and other members in decision making concerned with the organisational structure of the institution. Participative leadership or shared leadership are terms used to describe this type of leadership. Any business, including educational institutions, can benefit from this sort of leadership. This approach emphasizes the importance of all members of the group participating in the decision-making process (Research Gate, 2018).

A headmaster with laissez-faire leadership style gives complete rights and powers to their teachers to make decisions to establish goals and work out the problems and hurdles. In this style, decision-making is passed on to the teachers. This style focuses on no interference in the affairs of others (Research Gate, 2018). This style was identified by Hackman and Johnson(2009) as having the most realistic style, especially when employees are mature and enthusiastic about their work. The laissez-faire leadership style allows for complete autonomy in group decision-making without the involvement of the leaders.

According to Hoy and Miskel (2001), the directive leadership style of principle is similar to the assignment-based method, in which the leader provides teachers with specific rules, standards, and directions for organizing, sorting, as well as completing tasks. When the subordinates' capacity is low and the task at hand is mind-boggling or ambiguous, these techniques are thought to be appropriate. When the boss delivers more directions, the workers are more satisfied. Since secondary schools are the foundation for higher education, the quality of leadership and job performance of Headmasters is an essential factor for the success of secondary schools which in turn influence teachers' performance to achieve the objectives of school education.

Need and significance of the study:

The 21st century is an era of severe modernization and so educational system has to cope with the changes and challenges. The knowledge society requires an advanced level of skills and knowledge which can only be accomplished through a paradigm shift in the educational scenario. The quality of leadership is one of those main criteria which helps in better job performance. Saleem et.al (2020) found that the directive leadership style had a significant effect on teacher job performance in the studied schools, followed by the supportive and achievement-oriented leadership styles. Contrariwise, though participative leadership was

identified as a significant predictor, it was not considered a favourable predictor of teacher job performance. The headmasters in an institution should perform better in their job for achieving the organization's goals and objectives.

The effectiveness in the functioning of a school not only depends upon the leadership ability of the head of the school but also his job performance. Everything in the school is controlled and organised by the principal. The efficiency of the secondary school depends on the efficiency of school management; ability, personality, interaction of headmasters with stakeholders. The main job of a of a head of the school is to assist in leading, directing, and coordinating various activities inside the school. Among these responsibilities, headmasters must give genuine and effective leadership, resulting in improved professional presentation among teachers. For that the primary responsibility of the head of the school is to create and sustain an excellent teaching-learning environment in the school so that the teachers will actively engage in their teaching learning process. Thus, headmasters have a critical role to play in achieving the institution's goals and objectives. In this sense, headmaster is one of the factors that makes the difference between changing in success and changing in failure of the school. Moreover, the headmaster’s job performance have a significant impact on teachers and students in the institution as he manages and controls the teachers and students in the teaching learning process, Thus the leadership styles and job performance of headmasters in the secondary schools can motivate, inspire to promote productivity of the institution. It is in this context the researcher decided to find out the relationship between leadership styles and job performance of headmasters at secondary school level.

Review of Related Literature:

Gamze Kasalak et.al (2022) study revealed that the overall effect size of the relationship between leadership in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and academic staff’s job satisfaction is positive and moderate. However, there is no significant difference between the effect sizes of the research examining the relationship between leadership styles in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and academic staff’s job satisfaction, according to continent, culture and Human Development Index (HDI) moderator variables. Loureen & Rawia (2020) examined the influence of each the three major leadership styles: transformational, rewarding and avoiding on teachers’ happiness. The findings of the study pointed to a positive impact of the transformational and to a less extent rewarding leadership styles on teachers’ happiness and self -efficacy. The correlation findings from the structural equation modelling revealed that the directive leadership style had a significant effect on teacher job performance in the studied schools, followed by the supportive and achievement-oriented leadership styles. Conversely, although participative leadership was identified as a significant predictor, it was not considered a promising predictor of teacher

job performance Atif Saleem (2020).

Elpisah Hartini (2019) in a research study revealed that the leadership style had a positive and significant effect on the teacher's performance, and the dominant leadership style that influenced the teacher's performance was delegative leadership style. Becti et.al ((2019) examined how transformational leadership influenced teacher performance. The results showed a significant relationship between transformational leadership and teacher teaching performance, which means the higher the level of transformational leadership the higher the teacher's performance, and vice versa the lower the level of transformational leadership of the principal, the lower the teacher's performance. Zia-Ur-Rehman, Nadia Nazir & Nazir Haider Shah (2019) conducted a study to assess the effect of heads' leadership styles on teachers' job satisfaction at the university level. 40 heads and 175 teachers were chosen by using random sampling technique as a sample. The study revealed that heads' leadership styles significantly contributed to teachers' job satisfaction levels. It is recommended that heads may know the levels of learning in their departments, job satisfaction level and ability to share leadership styles with faculty members so that maximum results from the academic process would be achieved.

Research Questions:

1. What will be the level of Leadership styles of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala?
2. What will be the level of job performance of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala?
3. Is there any relationship between Leadership style and job performance of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala?

Objectives of the Study:

1. To find out the level of Leadership style of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala
2. To find out the level of job performance of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala
3. To find out the relationship between Leadership style and job performance of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala.

Hypotheses:

1. The level of Leadership style of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala is at moderate level
2. The level of job performance of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala is at moderate level
3. There is no significant relationship between Leadership style and job performance of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala.

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Methodology:

I) Method: The method adopted in the present study is *Normative survey*.

II) Population: All the headmasters of secondary schools of Kerala were the population for the study

III) Sample: The sample selected for this study was 60 headmasters of secondary schools in Kerala

IV) Tools: The major tools used for the study were Headmaster’s Leadership Scale and Job performance Scale prepared and standardised by the investigator. The Headmaster’s Leadership Scale and Job performance Scale were administered to 60 headmasters in 60 secondary schools after getting permission for administering the tools. The collected data were subjected to further descriptive and inferential statistical analysis in order to verify the hypotheses.

VI) Statistical techniques for data analysis: The main statistical techniques used were: Mean, Standard deviation and Karl person Product Moment Correlation.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1

Details regarding the level of leadership skills of Headmasters at secondary school level

Leadership skills	No of Headmasters	Percentage
High	26	43.3
Moderate	23	38.3
Low	11	18.4
Total	60	100

From the Table 1 it is clear that 43.3% of Headmasters at secondary school level have high level leadership skills whereas 38.3 percent of Headmasters have moderate level leadership skills. The table also shows that 18.4% of Headmasters have leadership skill at low level. Since more number of Headmasters (43.3%) in secondary schools possess leadership skills at high level, the hypothesis formed in this context, *The level of Leadership skill of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala is at moderate level is rejected.*

Table 2

Details regarding the level of job performance of Headmasters at secondary school level

Job performance	No of Headmasters	Percentage
High	23	38.33
Moderate	29	48.34
Low	8	13.33
Total	60	100

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From the Table 2 it is clear that 48.34% of Headmasters at secondary school level have moderate level Job performance whereas 38.3 per cent of HM have high level job performance. The table also shows that 13.33% of HM have Job performance at low level. Since more number of HM (48.4%) in secondary schools possess Job performance at moderate level, the hypothesis formed in this context, The level of Job performance of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala is at moderate level is accepted.

Table 3

Correlation between leadership styles and job performance of headmasters in secondary schools

$\sum x$	$\sum y$	$\sum xy$	$\sum x^2$	$\sum y^2$	Calculated γ - value	table value at 5% level	Remarks at 5% level
14258	14449	515630	524250	535827	0.4199	0.098	Significant

It is found that the result obtained for Coefficient of Correlation for the leadership styles and job performance of secondary school headmasters is 0.41 which is significant at 0.05 level. From this, it is clear that there is positive and substantial correlation between leadership styles and job performance of headmasters in secondary school and hence the hypothesis framed in this context i.e., *There is no significant relationship between Leadership styles and job performance of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala in is rejected.*

Major Findings:

The following are the major findings of the study:

- 43.3% of Headmasters at secondary school level have high level leadership styles whereas 38.3 per cent of HM have moderate level leadership styles. The table also shows that 18.4% of HM have leadership styles at low level the study revealed that 48.34% of Headmasters at secondary school level have moderate level Job performance whereas 38.3 per cent of HM have high level job performance and 13.33% of HM have Job performance at low level.
- There is significant relationship between Leadership style and job performance of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala.

Implication of the study

The present study revealed that there is significant relationship between leadership styles and job performance of headmasters in the secondary schools of Kerala. A clear understanding of the leadership styles and job performance of headmasters in the secondary schools may contribute to the success and

improvement of school education. The best style for the effectiveness of the organisation is, when the headmaster possesses them both, high leadership skills and job performance. Burns (1978) claims that real leadership not only creates change and achieves goals within the environment, but changing people involved in the actions necessary but even better: both followers and leaders are ennobled. Effective leadership and job performance of head of the school brings up a positive climate increased job satisfaction among teachers and quality of the school.

Conclusion and Suggestions

Since the leadership styles and job performance address concerns relating to the operation, success and support of such schools it is necessary to enhance the leadership styles and job performance of headmasters at different levels of school education. This in turn may help to assist at-risk students, support student academic success, and improve the high school graduation rate. Headmasters are timely assisted with leadership training programmes, so that they can improve the job performance which in turn will helps in the wholistic development of secondary school education.

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Paper 8

IMPORTANT OF TRENDS IN EDUCATIONAL INNOVATION

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ABSTRACT

“Education is the most powerful weapon, which you can use to change the world”–Nelson Mandela. The pandemic has accelerated the pace of change in the modern education world. With digital transformation and the adoption of technology globally, future jobs will be contrary to the idea of “jobs for life.” The conventional process of learning is being replaced with the emergence and implementation of different technologies in the education sector to retain and get future jobs. But there is no need to worry because we are moving to an era, where education is a life-long asset. Digitalization and effective education are significant to develop a skilled workforce. We are entering the era of revolution with online education. Big Data, Machine Learning, and the Internet of Things (IoT) will help students to sharpen their skillset and fulfil industry requirements. The recent trends in innovative learning have reformed with a strong focus on connectivity, versatility, and student-centred learning. In the ever-changing field of education, it is now more important than ever to effectively plan for the future. This article undertakes a thorough examination of the current trends and advancements that are influencing modern education Video-assisted Learning.

Introduction

Innovation is defined as the process of bringing about new ideas, methods, products, services, or solutions that have a significant positive impact and value. It involves transforming creative concepts into tangible outcomes that improve efficiency, and effectiveness. The primary focus of educational innovations should be on teaching and learning theory and practice, as well as on the learner, parents, community, society, and its culture. Technology applications need a solid theoretical foundation based on purposeful, systemic research and a sound pedagogy. Innovation in education means solving a real problem in a new, simple way to promote equitable learning. Innovation in education is not a goal in itself, but a means to achieve other educational objectives improving learning outcomes, including students wellbeing, improving cost-effectiveness and cost-efficiency, closing the achievement gap, improving teachers learning and work satisfaction

While the COVID restrictions are lowering and students are returning to schools, they expect the same level of engagement as online classes. To ensure this, start-ups develop video-assisted learning solutions.

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They allow educators to augment curriculum-based content with publicly available videos or their own videos. This approach improves students’ comprehension and cognitive abilities. Video-based educational supplements also reinforce the ideas taught in classrooms. Additionally, video-assisted learning allows educators to improve the inclusivity of classrooms by sharing content on different cultures, enhancing awareness and understanding. The videos also become extra study materials, allowing students to quickly recall topics later.

Online Learning

During the height of the COVID-19 pandemic, online learning was a solution for many schools trying to balance education with public health safety. Although the vast majority of teens would prefer to learn in a classroom with their teacher, online learning can still be a positive experience when done right. Colleges and universities have offered online classes for decades, and many K-12 schools now offer more digital options. Some students who struggled socially or experienced bullying during in-person school preferred learning virtually. After some trial and error, teachers have developed strategies to make online learning more effective. One of the biggest complaints about online learning is the lack of student engagement. One way to solve this problem is to flip your typical lesson to spur greater engagement. Consider teaching a new lesson asynchronously through a pre-recorded video. Then, during the live session, have students briefly summarize what they learned before placing them into smaller breakout rooms to solve related problems. Another thing to consider when it comes to online learning is adapting in-person activities for the digital classroom. For instance, gallery walks are a popular way to teach students how to provide peer feedback. But virtual gallery walks can be just as productive. Students can present their projects through short screencasts, and peers can provide input through a shared Google doc. We also know that remote learning often falls short of its potential, leaving students feeling disconnected, unsupported, and behind on learning. That’s why it’s important to continue building relationships with your students and find ways to engage them in their learning. Make sure to include more opportunities for students to connect to avoid the solitary experience of online learning.

Hybrid Learning

Hybrid learning is an educational model that combines both in-person and virtual learning, giving students a choice of where they learn. It also has the potential to offer even more opportunities by expanding the boundaries of the classroom and connecting students with people and resources beyond the physical school environment. For example, students might work together in person on a project and meet virtually with an expert in the field to deepen their knowledge and understanding. Or, students might partner with organizations that offer virtual resources that can help students explore college or career options that

before might have seemed out of reach because of geographic restrictions. As with any learning model, it is important to monitor how hybrid learning works for your students, making adjustments when necessary. We’ve created a helpful remote and hybrid learning tool using XQ’s Design Principles to guide you in making informed decisions about improving and refining your approach.

Blended Learning

Greg Akai, an educational innovation researcher at Loyola Marymount University, defines blended learning as a model utilizing various learning approaches, including in-person, hybrid, and online, to enrich learning opportunities through flexible and adaptive models. One example of blended learning in action is the three-station rotation. This blended learning lesson begins with the teacher introducing the topic to the entire class. Then, students rotate through three stations:

- A small group, teacher-led station, where the teacher can differentiate instruction, pausing to fill in gaps or diving deeper into more complex concepts.
- A collaborative station, where students work together on a collaborative assignment.
- A technology station whereby students work independently with perhaps adaptive software or view an interactive video.

These stations might start in the morning and finish after lunch, or students might complete one station daily. It’s entirely up to the teacher and the unique needs of the class how their stations are constructed—offering students choices for pacing their learning.

Virtual Learning

Virtual learning is a prominent trend in the education sector as it offers flexibility and convenience to learners. The process of E-learning has been streamlined by the institutions with virtual learning tools. The video conferencing tools and online live interactions offer students and instructors a classroom experience. The growing awareness about technology and better competence in handling digital tools is making online education more feasible and efficient. It is a cost-effective way to deliver content and provide training. The blended technology and classroom instructions together will create a quality and personalized curriculum for the students.

Lifelong Learning and Skill Development

Now-a-days, you can pursue any course without the time and place foundation as education is no longer limited to any particular method like the traditional one. There are many ways/modes to complete your education like: executive education programmes, certificate courses, and online skill school/college.

Promoting Research and Development

India is investing majorly in research and development. Universities are playing a major role in this endeavour. The majority of students engage in inter-institutional cooperation and research initiatives. This kind of interdisciplinary study is crucial to advancing science and promoting innovation.

Personalized Learning

One of the most exciting trends in educational management is the move towards personalized learning. With the help of technology, educators can now tailor instruction to meet the individual needs and interests of each student. This means that students can learn at their own pace, in their own way, and on their own schedule. This personalized approach to learning is already being used in some classrooms, but as technology continues to evolve, we can expect to see more widespread adoption of this approach ([Keys & Wolfe, 1988](#)).

Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI) is already being used in some educational settings to help students learn. AI-powered tools can analyse student data to identify areas where students are struggling and provide personalized recommendations for how to improve. AI can also be used to create more interactive and engaging learning experiences, such as virtual reality simulations ([Lauwerys, 2002](#); [Mazzarol et al., 2003](#)).

Social and Emotional Learning

Finally, there is a growing emphasis on social and emotional learning (SEL) in educational management. SEL focuses on developing students' social and emotional skills, such as empathy, communication, and problem-solving. By focusing on these skills, schools can help students become more well-rounded individuals who are better equipped to navigate the complexities of the modern world ([Rajiani et al., 2019](#)).

E-Learning

The pandemic forced schools and other educational institutions to shut down for long periods, accelerating the adoption of distance learning. To facilitate this transition, education technology start-ups and other big companies, like Zoom and Google, develop customized online platforms. This eliminates the need for long-term, high-cost infrastructure development for educational institutions. Besides, e-learning enables students to access education through the internet, reducing knowledge gaps. Recorded lesson videos also offer flexibility for students to learn in their own time. Integrating immersive solutions and game-based learning into online platforms furthers the effectiveness of virtual learning.

Video-assisted Learning

While the COVID restrictions are lowering and students are returning to schools, they expect the same level of engagement as online classes. To ensure this, start-ups develop video-assisted learning solutions. They allow educators to augment curriculum-based content with publicly available videos or their own videos. This approach improves students’ comprehension and cognitive abilities. Video-based educational supplements also reinforce the ideas taught in classrooms. Additionally, video-assisted learning allows educators to improve the inclusivity of classrooms by sharing content on different cultures, enhancing awareness and understanding. The videos also become extra study materials, allowing students to quickly recall topics later.

Conclusion

The future of learning will be determined by the emerging technologies and innovative pedagogies in the education sector. Machine learning may play a dominant role in education systems that can become more scalable. In the next few years, all the critical data will be stored on Cloud. The abundant amount of data is already transforming the role of teachers from knowledge providers to knowledge facilitators, and this trend will continue in the years to come. These new trends in educational technology will develop social-emotional skills in students. The tools allow students to learn beyond the classroom irrespective of geographical boundaries. Moreover, big data analysis will help the education system to analyse the areas where students can do their best and where they lack. That will help teachers to provide better support for enhanced learning outcomes.

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Paper 9

**INVESTORS' AWARENESS ABOUT STOCK MARKET: A STUDY WITH
SPECIAL REFERENCE TO DAKSHINA KANNADA DISTRICT**

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ABSTRACT

Financial assets are needed for the firm to carry on its business. Most of the assets are financed through selling pieces of paper called financial assets, instrument and securities. They have value in exchange because they are claims on the firm's assets and to its future cash flow. Though it is initially for the benefit of the firm but it will also become beneficial to the investor. The investor will grow as the firm grows and simultaneously the economy is also benefited. Investment decisions of an individual depend on his income and the amount of risk he or she is willing to take. Investing in securities is the last option for some and for others they are not aware of share market. Regularity in investing, percentage of savings also has a major impact in choosing the investments. A study on investment awareness gives an idea about investor's choice and opinion about share market and their awareness about it. The researcher used convenient sampling technique and descriptive research design with an approximate sample size of 308 respondents. Area of sampling is limited to 'Dakshina Kannada'. Data collection has been done through questionnaire method. The finding of the research will be useful for the companies to understand the investors' awareness and add new strategies to make more investors to invest.

Keywords: *BSE, investment, investor awareness, NSE, stock market.*

INTRODUCTION:

Indian stock market is the fuel of Indian economy by providing much capital required. In world, our country's stock market is one of the well-developed stock markets and also it is a parameter of nations economy. It helps to the nation by way of procuring funds from various potential investors and these funds used for the purpose of industrial development. There are many stock exchanges in India, among many there are two stock exchanges deals most of the trading in the Indian stock market such as BSE (Bombay Stock Exchange) and NSE (National Stock Exchange). According to SEBI report, FY96 and FY17 annual

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turnover value in National Stock Exchange witnessed growth at a CAGR of 19.13% getting a worth of US\$ 790.21 billion in FY17. Nifty 50 and S&P Sensex rose 28.6% and 27.9% respectively in FY 2017, thus yielding the finest returns from 2014. The Bombay Stock Exchange total market capitalisation of all the companies touched a record Rs 150 lakh crore (US\$ 2.33 trillion). Retail investor awareness is a part of financial literacy. Investment awareness means the set of knowledge and skills which permit to an individual to take effective and informed decisions by way of understanding investment. Financial literacy and investment are essential to assist individuals meet up their objectives and prime goals and objectives. In the present era, investment awareness became the success mantra for everyone. The Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) is contributing in the programme of financial awareness among the common and young investors of the country.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Stock market movements are largely influenced by, broad money supply, inflation, C/D ratio and fiscal deficit apart from political stability (**Debjit Chakraborty 1997**). Deepening and strengthening the process of economic liberalization in the Asian developing countries is essential for minimizing the risks and maximizing the benefits from increased international capital market integration (**Redel 1997**). Individuals below 58 years i.e., before retirement are found to take ownership of risky assets in their portfolio which is influenced by the financial knowledge, marginal tax return and age. Individuals with financial knowledge which enhances as being older invest more and in high return, higher risk assets to file for higher tax return as they look the opportunity in investing risky assets (**R. R. Raja Mohan 2005**). There is significant difference between the various demographic variables and investor's knowledge of grievances, awareness of functions of redressal agencies, loading of complain and their satisfaction level (**Nayak 2010**). The wealthy population is more likely to invest in the stock market. The wealthier households are willing to invests in the riskier assets (**Dmitry S. Makarov Astrid V. Schornick 2010**). Identified the interdependence and co-movement of covariates for banking stability to the satisfaction of economic logic. The Indian banking sector has largely defied the global system (**Vighneswara Swamy 2011**). Any adjustment in the price of gold will have no detrimental impact on financial stability. In fact, the empirical results of the study support the counterintuitive view that any gold price correction will have a stabilizing effect on the Indian financial system's financial indicators (**Rabi N. Mishra and G. Jagan Mohan 2012**). The behaviour of the investor to identify the better investment avenues available in India. By increasing personal wealth, investing can contribute to higher, overall economic growth and prosperity. The Indian investors are very much aware about the concept of portfolio allotments and risk and return of the investment (**S. Suriya Murithi, B. Narayanan, M. Arivazhagan 2012**). 60% of the sample population

said that there is change in the investment behaviour in the last 5 years. The major reason for change in investment pattern is change in income and change in Government policies. More individuals are willing to invest money but the scope of investment is not long-term (**Aparna Samudra Et Al 2012**). In total 60 variables which may affect the stock market, major 5 factors which affect the stock market are Flow of Foreign Institutional Investor (FII), Political Stability, Inflation, Govt. Policies, GDP Growth (**Mrunal joshi 2013**). Many people are not aware about investment in share market on equity. According to researcher investors cannot avoid risk but they can manage risk by investing in various types of investment avenues so that they can get a moderate profit (**Ashly Lynn Joseph and M. Prakash 2014**). The study reveals the fact that investors are aware about investment avenues but they considered safety as important factor while making investment, that's why they prefer making investment in gold, bank deposits, real estate etc. and ignore other investment avenues (**Sonali Patil, Kalpana Nandawar 2014**). Demographic factors like income, age and qualification effect the investors level of risk tolerance (**C. M. Shinde, Priyanka Zanvar 2015**). The study has shown many sociodemographic variables that are correlated with an individual's financial conduct. The testing of the hypotheses clearly indicates that six socio-demographic variables are substantially correlated (**Shalini Gautam and Mitu Matta,2016**). Study of determinants of investment decision which are the most dominating factor affecting the investment decision. They found that the most influential factors are under “Firm’s Image” with the highest loading, followed up by ethics that a particular firm follows (**Gunjan Sharma et al 2017**). Most of the people invest their money in stable platform with low return perspective due to lack of awareness of the share market, mutual funds. The investors who preferred bank deposit for investment because of purchasing home and long-term growth eventually leads to lower returns and higher stability (**U M Gopal Krishna et al 2019**). Investors are mostly influenced by the family members. And comparing men and women, women invest less than men. The knowledge about financial product and market directly affects decision or rate of risk and return (**Abhinandan Kulal et al 2019**). It has been found out possessing positive FA is best to equip youth with sufficient knowledge, information and life skills to assist them to make right financial judgment, to improve their financial behaviour (**Mohd Zamri Abu Bakar, Saridan Abu Bakar 2020**).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To know the influence of Demographic Factors on Investment Behaviour.
- To study the awareness of retail investors about stock market.
- To examine the opinion of retail investors towards regulatory framework of stock market.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H₀: There is no significant association between the demographic factors of respondents and their stock market awareness.

H₁: There is a significant association between the demographic factors of respondents and their stock market awareness.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The research has taken only individual investors and does not consider the institutional investors of the stock market. The research is carried out in Dakshina Kannada district. The study is completely focused on awareness level of the retail investors on Indian stock market. The research is very handy for any researcher in the field of stock market or investment.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

It is an empirical study. The study is based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data was collected using well designed and structured questionnaire. Google form was used to collect the data from the sample respondents. Likert 5 scale was used to collect the information about awareness level of respondents with regard to stock market. The secondary data was collected from books and websites. The sample size of the study is 308 investors from Dakshina Kannada District and used Microsoft Excel and SPSS for the analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 1: Gender of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	161	52.27
Male	147	47.72
Total	308	100

Source: Primary data

Table 1 shows that out of total sample population of 308 respondents, 52.27% respondents are female and 47.72% respondents are male. The majority (52.27%) of the respondents in the study are female.

Table 2: Age of the respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 25	108	35.06
25 to 30 years	113	36.68
30 to 40years	74	24.02
40 years and above	13	4.22
Total	308	100

Source: Primary data

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From the above table, it is clear that 35.06% respondents are in the age group of below 25 years, 36.68% are between the age group of 25 to 30 years, 24.02% are in the age group between 30 to 40 years and 4.22% are in the age group of above 40 years.

Table 3: Marital Status of the Respondents

Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	149	48.37
Un Married	159	51.63
Total	308	100

Source: Primary data

From table 3, it is found that 48.37% of the respondents are married and 51.63% of the respondents are unmarried.

Table 4: Employment Status of the respondents

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage
Self -employee	149	48.37
Government employee	59	19.15
Private employee	100	32.46
Total	308	100

Source: Primary data

Table 4, shows that, 48.37% of the respondents are self-employed, 19.15% of the respondents are government employees and 32.46% of the respondents are private employees.

Table 5: Area of domicile of the respondents

Area of domicile	Frequency	Percentage
Rural	159	51.62
Urban	104	33.76
Semi-urban	45	14.61
Total	308	100

Source: Primary data

From the above table, it is clear that 51.62% of the respondents are living in rural area, 33.76% of the respondents are living in urban area and 14.61% of the respondents are living in semi urban area.

Table 6: Regularity in investment

Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
No	33	10.7
Yes	275	89.3
Total	308	100.0

Source: Primary data

It is fact from the above table that 89% of the respondents regularly invests in stock market and 10.7% of the respondents are opined that they are not invests regularly.

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Table 7: Factors influencing stock prices

Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	288	93.5
No	20	6.5
Total	308	100

Source: Primary data

It is found from table 7 that 93.5% of the respondents are aware about the factors which will influence the stock prices and 6.5% of the respondents opined that they are not aware about the factors.

Table 8: Study of Financial Statements before investing in stock Market

Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	287	93.2
No	21	6.8
Total	308	100

Source: Primary data

It is true from table 8 that 93.2% of the respondents have opined that they always study the company's financial statements before investing in stocks, 6.8% of the respondents have opined that they never study the company's financial statements before investing in stocks.

Table 9: Seeking financial experts' opinion while investing Stock market

Opinion	Frequency	Percentage
Always	188	61.0
Occasionally	67	21.8
Sometimes	37	12.0
Rarely	8	2.6
Never	8	2.6
Total	308	100

Source: Primary data

Table 9 reveals the fact that 61% of the respondents always seek advice from financial experts before making stock market investment decisions, 21.8% of the respondents seek advice from financial experts before making stock market investment decisions occasionally, 12% of the respondents opined that sometimes they seek advice from financial experts 2.6 of the respondents opined that they rarely seek advice from financial experts and remaining 2.6% of the respondents opined that they never seek advice from financial experts before making stock market investment decisions.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS

H₀: There is no significant association between the demographic factors of respondents and their stock

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market awareness.

H₁: There is a significant association between the demographic factors of respondents and their stock market awareness

Table 10: Chi-square values

Sl. No	Statement	Gender	Age	Marital Status	Employment Status	Area of The Domicile	Annual Income
1	Somewhat knowledge about stock market	5.045	31.693*	16.612*	8.909	12.887	36.887*
2	Follow the stock market through financial news on TV and news papers	2.755	33.619*	28.806*	20.59*	21.082*	27.615*
3	Trust in when trading on stock market	7.235	28.393*	20.289*	9.732	19.039*	34.333*
4	Buying decision based on future expectations rather than past performance	4.864	29.289*	15.6*	8.76	18.122*	34.669*
5	having positive perception towards stock market	2.8	27.392*	18.15*	7.911	15.607*	30.014*
6	Knowledge of stock market operation	10.497*	22.342*	14.527*	19.243*	11.082	28,402*
7	Aware of the risk associated with investing in stock market	2.634	37.92*	19.351*	9.142	16.672*	35.34*
8	Familiarity with different options available in stock market	6.742	43.127*	17.261*	27.621*	15.914*	44.623*
9	Knowledge to create diversified portfolio	4.476	49.443*	24.74*	7.677	13.762	39.587*
10	Regularly reviewing the performance of stock market	5.612	33.168*	17.261*	13.543	18.334*	35.155*
11	knowledge about the factors influencing the	5.53	45.066*	20.446*	14.219	29.832*	35.085*

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	stock prices						
12	Considering the historical performance of the company before investing in its stock	11.127*	39.302*	10.99*	18.249*	16.116*	31.847*
13	Aware of the potential tax implications related to stock trading	1.351	53.005*	25.865*	8.3	33.331*	40.466*
14	Confidence in the ability to analyse the Fundamentals of the company	11.073*	33.081*	12.515*	17.411*	17.585*	35.467*
15	Use technical analysis while trading on stock market	1.943	47.963*	17.145*	6.924	16.969*	36.342*
16	Comfortability while using online platforms for buying and selling stocks	7.122	33.546*	12.947*	13.381	14.855	33.453*
17	Knowledge about potential impact of industry trends on specific stock	4.62	50.795*	16.576*	13.182	20.771*	37.144*
18	Confidence in the ability to stick to a long-term investment strategy despite short term market fluctuations.	11.056*	38.472*	8.482	15.372	15.508	35.777*

Source: Primary data

The calculated Chi-square values for the gender of the respondents indicates that only 22.22% of the values are significant at 5% level of significance. Therefore it is a fact that there is no significant difference in the awareness level of male and female respondents.

With respect to the age factor, all the calculated values are significant @ 5% level of significance and hence concluded that there is a significant difference in the awareness level of respondents belongs to different age group.

With regards to marital status -94.4%, with regard to area of the domicile - 72.22%, with regards to annual

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income 100% of the calculated values are significant and hence found that significant difference is observed in the awareness level of the respondents belongs to different marital status, area of domicile and annual income.

With regards to the employment status of the respondents, 72.22%, calculated values are insignificant and hence it is understood that employment status of the respondents has no significant impact on the respondents' awareness level of stock market.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

It is found in study that majority (52.27%) of the respondents in the study are female, majority (36.68%) of the respondents are between the age group of 25 to 30 years, majority of the respondents (51.63%) are unmarried, majority (48.37%) are self-employed, the majority (51.62 %) of the respondents are living in rural area. It is also found in the study that 89% of the respondents regularly invest in stock market, 93.5% of the respondents opined that they are aware about the factors which will influence the stock prices, 93.2% of the respondents opined that they always study the company's financial statements before investing in stock market.

As most of the calculated Chi-Square values are insignificant at 5% level of significance it was also concluded that there is no significant association between the demographic factors of respondents and their stock market awareness.

SUGGESTIONS

According to the results of this study, investors in Dakshina Kannada have a decent knowledge of the Stock market in the overall aspect. However, there are some participants who are only aware of certain aspects. This can be improved significantly if they try to implement the aforementioned recommendations and suggestions.

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Paper 10

TRANSFORMING EDUCATION THROUGH INNOVATION

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ABSTRACT

Creativity is thinking up new things. Innovation is doing new things (Theodore Levitt). Education is vital to society's existence and advancement since it is a social institution that serves societal requirements. To meet the needs of the uncertain and quickly evolving globalized world, it must be great, sustainable, and comprehensive in addition to being dynamic. To innovate is to think beyond the box and create a fresh concept that enables us to carry out our work in a different way. Therefore, the goal of each invention is to produce something that differs from what we have been producing, whether in terms of quantity, quality, or both. For the innovation to have a significant, transformational impact, it needs to be put into practice, which calls for rapid dissemination and extensive application. Educational innovation is crucial to fulfilling the evolving needs of students in the twenty-first century. If this kind of study is promoted in schools, it will benefit society. High-quality education for all can be advanced by innovative research while also supporting a more prosperous and equitable educational system. This article deals with Educational innovation, obstacles and challenges to educational innovation, as well as the role of research in educational innovation.

Keywords: High Quality Education, Research, Creativity, Educational Innovation, Obstacles and challenges

Introduction

The world needs people who can use their critical and creative thinking abilities to work as a team to solve problems today and in the future. Technology has totally changed and modified the ways in which knowledge is created, acquired, and shared. It is debatable whether education can produce critical and imaginative thinkers who can meet the demands of the social and economic environments of the present and the future. On the other hand, because they weaken teacher authority in the classroom and alter the opinions of pupils of them, computers and smart devices pose a challenge to the integrity of knowledge and knowing. As a result, the phrases "teacher" and "guide," "facilitator," and "coach" have begun to have

similar meanings.

Innovation in education will guarantee that the current educational system produces knowledgeable and talented students to meet current and future industry needs. Global education systems are always under pressure to change and grow in order to satisfy the ever-evolving needs of society. In order to ensure that innovations in education are strong and effective, thorough research is applied in addition to the introduction of new technology and approaches. Lecturers, teachers, researchers, administrators, and policymakers must all enhance the philosophy and practices of teaching and learning, as well as other aspects of the process.

Technology Integration in Education

Modernization cannot exist without technology, which is also transforming the way that pupils learn. Platforms for education technology are improving the effectiveness, accessibility, and engagement of learning. Numerous online learning environments provide courses in specialised and developing disciplines, enabling students to advance their professional development and stay competitive.

The government, educators, and students have all acknowledged the importance of digital education since it provides so many advantages, including affordability, flexibility, and accessibility.

Higher education has long been offered in India, dating back to ancient times. There are several educational institutions across the nation that provide a wide range of courses covering distinct educational topics. The dearth of modernization in the Indian school system has drawn harsh criticism. To raise the standard of education in the nation, however, a lot of focus has been placed on research and development in recent years. To give students access to comprehensive education, educational institutions are implementing contemporary teaching strategies including blended learning, online learning, and virtual learning.

Information and communication technologies (ICT) have grown at an exponential rate, enabling its use in many industries, including education. The majority of technology use in education is still shallow, nevertheless, especially in light of the COVID-19 pandemic. While students utilise technology for learning, research, and performance evaluation, teachers use it to support their students in teaching, mentoring, and coaching.

It's a widely held belief that using technology to aid learning makes students more productive members of society and that they must acquire technology skills to do so. Because of this, delivering a high-quality education necessitates that educators teach their students how to use technology and employ instructional technologies in the classroom. The National Education Policy 2020 recognises both the possible risks and difficulties that come with using technology in the classroom in addition to its many advantages.

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This policy's dedication to supporting regional languages through the creation of virtual labs and e-courses is one noteworthy feature. Furthermore, work is also underway to establish the National Educational Technology Forum (NETF), which is anticipated to have a significant influence on how education is conducted in the nation in the future. One of the main focuses of NEP 2020 is the integration of technology into education with the aim of reaching 100% literacy. The strategy emphasises how technology may improve education while also acknowledging its significant impact on societal advancement. Significant work is needed to enable the seamless integration of technology and to accept the more significant changes in the current educational system in order to fully realise this vision.

Review of literature

The research was conducted in collaboration between Dickson Mdhlalose and Gloria Mlambo from the National Electronic Media Institute of South Africa and the Department of Education at the Basic Education Republic of South Africa. The study found that technology has had contradictory effects on education, with evidence suggesting that technology has improved classroom collaboration, broadened students' academic and intellectual horizons, and enabled remote learning. However, it also highlighted the challenges faced by students and teachers due to hardware failures, software incompatibilities, and outdated program versions. Additionally, the study highlighted the potential for dishonest students to gain an edge over their classmates due to technological advancements. The study also highlighted the potential negative effects of excessive technology usage on students' health. The history of technology in education dates back to the 1920s, with radio broadcasting being first used in teaching political science and history. The computer-based teaching system, PLATO, was developed in the 1950s, followed by audio and video cassettes in the 1960s. Personal computers in the 1970s and 1980s revolutionized education, and the internet in the 1990s made online courses and programs accessible. Innovations like AI and augmented reality are changing the way students learn, making education more personalized and effective. The Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) has led to increased investment in educational technology, including hardware, applications, and internet connectivity. This study aims to understand the effects of technology on education, teaching, and learning, and how students may become excessively dependent on technology, limiting their ability to learn and problem-solve independently.

Ghosh, Sonali Roy Chowdhury in her study "Integration of technology in education," says that in order to ensure inclusive and high-quality learning, technological integration is emphasised in India's National Education Policy 2020. It acknowledges the value of creating virtual labs, developing e-courses, and speaking regional languages. The utilisation of cutting-edge technology like 3D, simulation, robotics, and

artificial intelligence is encouraged by the policy. It promotes expanded digital learning platforms for public access as well as blended learning. Notwithstanding the advantages, there are still difficulties, such as the digital divide, problems with infrastructure, changing the paradigm of learning, teacher competency, and the accessibility of digital materials. The federal government and the state governments must work together for the programme to be implemented successfully.

However, e-learning has grown significantly in India, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. In a study conducted by Anjali Sharma, she showed how the pandemic has encouraged the use of e-learning to bridge the gap in education in India. She also observed that e-learning has become a necessity, not just an option, and that it has helped to reach students who live in remote areas with limited access to educational facilities. Another area of research has been the effectiveness of learning in India.

In a study by Priyanka Sharma and Raj Kumar, they found that e-learning was an effective educational method, and it had a positive impact on students' knowledge acquisition and retention. They also observed that e-learning offered more personalized learning and greater flexibility than traditional classrooms.

The study by M. Dinesh Kumar, a Department of Commerce with Computer Applications at Mannar Thirumalai Naicker College, focuses on the integration of technology into digital education in India. The study aims to evaluate the Digital Education System in India and examine the SWAYAM, or Study Webs of Active Learning for Young Aspiring Minds, in Tamilnadu. The research also examines the use of gamification and personalized learning techniques in digital education. Gamification, which integrates game-like elements into the learning process, makes learning interactive, fun, and stimulating. It has gained popularity in India, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, which has forced schools and colleges to adopt online learning. Personalized learning, which tailors learning content and instruction to meet individual educational goals, has great potential for improving student outcomes, enhancing the quality of education, and addressing learning gaps and inequalities. The emerging techniques in digital education in India have the potential to revolutionize the way students learn.

Challenges and Barriers to Educational Innovation

1. **Opposition to Change:** Teachers', administrators', and other stakeholders' reluctance to change is one of the main obstacles to educational innovation. Developing solutions to overcome this resistance requires an understanding of its underlying origins.
2. **Restrictions on Resources:** A lack of finance, infrastructure, or training, among other things, can make it difficult to put innovative techniques into effect. It will take investment and strategic planning to overcome these limitations.

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3. **Guaranteeing Access and Equity:** One major difficulty is making sure all students have access to innovative teaching methods. This entails addressing the differences in opportunities and resources between various Communities and schools.
4. **Access to technology.** It is essential that all students have access to gadgets like smartphones and PCs with internet connectivity in order to successfully incorporate technology into teaching. Sadly, poor children don't always have access to this, which makes it a big obstacle to overcome.
5. **Infrastructure Difficulties:** Power outages and network problems are common across the nation, particularly in rural areas. A solid and dependable digital infrastructure is necessary for technology integration to go smoothly.
6. **Ethical Concerns:** In order to preserve academic integrity, it is difficult to control unethical behaviours in the digital sphere, such as plagiarism and cheating.
7. **Change in Learning Paradigm:** Changing from a technology-driven, rote-learning system to one that stresses experimental learning and critical thinking would require a shift in the perspectives of different stakeholders. It will take constant work to comprehend and successfully apply this new worldview.
8. **Teacher Competence:** Digitally competent instructors are desperately needed to meet the demands of the changing educational landscape. It is important for educators to be proficient in the use of technology in the classroom.
9. **Digital Resources:** When it comes to teaching using digital resources, many subjects have restrictions. Creating thorough digital materials for every subject is a problem that has to be solved.

Conclusion

Educational innovation, supported by rigorous research, holds the potential to transform learning experiences and outcomes for students. By bridging the gap between research and practice, educators can implement evidence-based strategies that foster continuous improvement and adaptation in education.

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Paper 11

SCIENTIFIC LITERACY IN THE DIGITAL AGE

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ABSTRACT

In today's digital age, we are surrounded by a vast array of information that is readily accessible at our fingertips. With just a few clicks, we can access scientific studies, research papers, and discussions on a myriad of topics. However, with this abundance of information comes the challenge of discerning what is credible and what is not. This is where scientific literacy plays a critical role. Scientific literacy is the ability to understand, interpret, and apply scientific knowledge in various contexts. Scientific literacy is essential for participating in informed discussions about complex scientific issues, such as climate change or genetic engineering. Whether you are a doctor, engineer, or teacher, having a strong foundation in science will enhance your critical thinking skills and problem-solving abilities.

While there are challenges to achieving scientific literacy in the digital age, there are also opportunities to enhance it. One major opportunity is the wealth of resources available online for learning about science. Websites like Khan Academy, Coursera, and TED Talks offer free videos and courses on a wide range of scientific topics. By adopting a multi-faceted approach that includes critical thinking skills, science communication, lifelong learning, and combating misinformation, we can improve scientific literacy in society and foster a culture of curiosity and inquiry.

Key words:

Scientific literacy, digital age, Problem solving, online resources.

Introduction

In today's digital age, we are surrounded by a vast array of information that is readily accessible at our fingertips. With just a few clicks, we can access scientific studies, research papers, and discussions on a myriad of topics. However, with this abundance of information comes the challenge of discerning what is credible and what is not. This is where scientific literacy plays a critical role. Scientific literacy is the ability to understand, interpret, and apply scientific knowledge in various contexts. In this article, we will delve into the importance of scientific literacy in the digital age, explore the challenges and opportunities it presents, and discuss strategies to enhance scientific literacy in today's fast-paced world.

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The Importance of Scientific Literacy

Scientific literacy is crucial for several reasons. First and foremost, it empowers individuals to make informed decisions about their health, the environment, and other important issues. For example, a person who is scientifically literate will be able to critically evaluate the claims of a new diet or skincare product before deciding to try it. In addition, scientific literacy is essential for participating in informed discussions about complex scientific issues, such as climate change or genetic engineering.

Furthermore, scientific literacy is a key component of a well-rounded education. In today's knowledge-based economy, many professions require a basic understanding of scientific principles. Whether you are a doctor, engineer, or teacher, having a strong foundation in science will enhance your critical thinking skills and problem-solving abilities.

The digital age has revolutionized the way we access and consume information, making scientific literacy more important than ever. With the rise of fake news and misinformation, it is essential to be able to distinguish between reliable sources and unreliable ones. By being scientifically literate, we can better navigate the sea of information on the internet and make informed decisions based on evidence rather than hearsay.

Challenges in Achieving Scientific Literacy in the Digital Age

Despite the importance of scientific literacy, there are several challenges in achieving it in the digital age. One of the main challenges is the overwhelming amount of information available online. With so much content competing for our attention, it can be difficult to sift through it all and separate fact from fiction. In a study conducted by the Pew Research Center, it was found that 64% of Americans say fake news causes a great deal of confusion about basic facts of current events.

Another challenge is the prevalence of misinformation and pseudoscience on social media platforms. A study published in the journal *Science* found that false information spreads six times faster than accurate information on Twitter. This can lead to the spread of myths and misconceptions that can have detrimental effects on public health and safety.

In addition, the lack of scientific literacy education in schools and colleges is a major barrier to improving scientific literacy in society. A report by the National Center for Education Statistics found that only 36% of high school seniors in the United States are proficient in science. This lack of education can lead to a population that is ill-equipped to critically evaluate scientific information.

Opportunities for Enhancing Scientific Literacy in the Digital Age

While there are challenges to achieving scientific literacy in the digital age, there are also opportunities to enhance it. One major opportunity is the wealth of resources available online for learning about science.

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Websites like Khan Academy, Coursera, and TED Talks offer free videos and courses on a wide range of scientific topics. By taking advantage of these resources, individuals can enhance their scientific literacy and expand their knowledge base.

Another opportunity lies in the use of social media as a tool for science communication. Many scientists and science communicators use platforms like Twitter and Instagram to share their research and engage with the public. By following these accounts, individuals can learn about the latest scientific discoveries and engage in discussions with experts in the field.

Furthermore, citizen science projects offer a unique opportunity for individuals to participate in scientific research and contribute to our collective understanding of the world. Projects like Zooniverse and Foldit allow volunteers to help analyze data and solve scientific puzzles. By participating in these projects, individuals can gain hands-on experience with the scientific process and develop a deeper appreciation for the work of scientists.

Strategies for Enhancing Scientific Literacy in the Digital Age

To enhance scientific literacy in the digital age, it is important to adopt a multi-faceted approach that includes both individual and societal-level interventions. Here are some strategies for improving scientific literacy:

1. **Teach critical thinking skills:** One of the most important aspects of scientific literacy is the ability to think critically about information. Schools and colleges should emphasize critical thinking skills in their curriculum, teaching students how to evaluate sources, identify bias, and distinguish between fact and opinion.
2. **Promote science communication:** Scientists and science communicators should actively engage with the public through social media, podcasts, and other platforms. By making science more accessible and engaging, they can help demystify complex topics and foster a culture of curiosity and inquiry.
3. **Encourage lifelong learning:** Scientific literacy is not something that can be achieved in a single class or workshop. It is a lifelong journey of learning and discovery. Individuals should seek out opportunities to expand their knowledge of science, whether through online courses, books, or community events.
4. **Support science education:** Schools and colleges should prioritize science education and ensure that students receive a strong foundation in scientific principles. Teachers should be provided with professional development opportunities to enhance their science teaching skills and keep up-to-date with the latest research and developments in the field.
5. **Combat misinformation:** In an age of fake news and misinformation, it is essential to teach individuals

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how to spot and debunk false information. Fact-checking websites like Scopes and Political can help individuals verify the accuracy of claims before sharing them with others.

Conclusion

Scientific literacy is more important than ever in the digital age. By being scientifically literate, we can make informed decisions about our health, the environment, and other important issues. While there are challenges to achieving scientific literacy, there are also opportunities to enhance it through online resources, science communication, citizen science projects, and other initiatives. By adopting a multi-faceted approach that includes critical thinking skills, science communication, lifelong learning, and combating misinformation, we can improve scientific literacy in society and foster a culture of curiosity and inquiry. It is up to each of us to take responsibility for our own scientific literacy and contribute to a more informed and enlightened world.

**SCIENTIFIC LITERACY AND ATTITUDE: A STUDY OF THEIR
INTERDEPENDENT EFFECTS ON SCIENCE EDUCATION SUCCESS**

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ABSTRACT

Scientific literacy and scientific attitudes are two conceptual foundations for students academic pursuit. This study aimed to investigate the relationship between scientific Attitude and scientific literacy among secondary and higher secondary students. A sample of 450 students from the 9th, 10th, 11th, and 12th grades was randomly selected. Their attitudes and literacy about science were assessed and scored using a questionnaire. The instruments used were the Test of Scientific Literacy Skills and the Scientific Attitude Scale. The hypothesis test was conducted using the Pearson correlation test with the assistance of SPSS 29.0.2.0. The result shows that there is a strong positive relationship between scientific literacy skills and the scientific attitude among students of secondary and higher secondary schools in the Udupi district in Karnataka. There was a significant strong positive relationship between scientific attitude and scientific literacy, $r(450 - 2) = .700$, $p = [< .001]$. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. The regression analysis result indicated that both variables significantly predict each other, with substantial portions of variance explained by the models. The results of this study indicated that most of the respondents have positive opinions and attitudes about a range of aspects of science literacy. The implications of this research are related to improving students' scientific attitude and process skills aspects and teaching materials based on scientific literacy as a reference and consideration for learning on other subjects in science subjects.

Key Words: Science, attitude, correlation, literacy, Scientific.

Introduction:

The promotion of scientific literacy has been recognized as a major goal of science education in the world. Realizing the importance of scientific literacy for future citizens, science educators around the world have made efforts to improve science education standards in schools. Improving science education standards will benefit individual societies and improve the quality of prospective teachers (Chin, 2005). Science literacy describes the ability of an individual to understand scientific laws, theories, phenomena, and things. This means that each citizen must have the necessary scientific knowledge base to make practically any informed decision about his life (Dragoş & Mih, 2015).

Many researchers have made efforts to define the essence of scientific literacy. Paul De Hart introduced the term 'scientific literacy' at the end of the 1950s (Hurd, 1958). Scientific literacy can be defined as employing skills, attitudes, values, and knowledge which are associated with science for critical thinking,

problem-solving, and decision-making processes and being a lifelong learner. Hurd defines scientific literacy as 'making a decision which includes responsibility for science and technology, and having the intellectual knowledge and skills for cognitive movement (Chin, 2005). Scientific literacy is first defined as being familiar with natural life and knowing its diversity and unity (Devi & Aznam, 2019). In addition, it includes understanding the main concepts and principles of science and becoming aware of the relationship between science, mathematics, and technology. It also consists of comprehending that science, mathematics, and technology are the production of human beings, recognizing their power and limitations in various fields, having the capacity for scientific thinking, and using science and the way of scientific thinking for personal and societal objectives.

Personal attitudes play a significant role in individuals' interest, attention, and response to science and technology in general and to issues that affect them in particular (Bybee & McCrae, 2011). PISA (Programme for International Students Assistance) 2006 evaluated students' attitudes in three areas: interest in science, support for scientific enquiry, and responsibility for sustainable development. These areas provide a portrait of students' general appreciation of science, their specific scientific attitudes and values, and their responsibility toward issues that have national and international ramifications. Scientific attitude is one of the major determinants of students' achievement in science – which has become a major quality parameter of a student living in the present scientific society. The Scientific Attitude Inventory (SAI) was developed and field-tested 25 years ago. It has been used extensively worldwide and continues to be used (Moore & Foy, 1997). The habit of thought associated with scientific thinking deserves more careful consideration. Being scientific means having such attitudes as curiosity, rationality, willingness to suspend judgment, open-mindedness, critical-mindedness, objectivity, honesty, humility, etc. Attitude regulates behavior that is directed towards or away from some object or situation group of objects or situations (Pitafi & Farooq, 2012).

The development of scientific attitude is one of the most important outcomes of science education (Waddington, 2017). It is as important as the cognitive aspects of science education. Scientific attitude encourages a questioning mind and a spirit of enquiry. Therefore, without this, studies of science will only mean acceptance of dogma and will never lead to the development of proper orientation towards various scientific endeavors (Grinnell, 2019).

Most existing studies examine scientific literacy and attitude in isolation without exploring their intricate relationship. A paucity of studies investigate how these two variables influence each other reciprocally. The majority of research in this area has been qualitative, providing valuable insights but lacking the quantitative data necessary to establish the strength and nature of the relationship between scientific literacy and scientific attitude. While some research has explored the impact of scientific attitudes on student engagement and interest in science, fewer studies have examined how these attitudes directly affect scientific literacy and overall educational outcomes. Understanding how a positive scientific attitude can enhance scientific literacy and, in turn, how increased scientific literacy can further improve attitudes toward science is crucial for developing effective educational strategies. By addressing these research gaps, this study aims to contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the interdependent effects of scientific literacy and scientific attitude on science education success. The findings will provide valuable insights for educators, policymakers, and researchers, helping to inform the development of more effective and integrated science education strategies. The study addresses the following research questions: 1) What is the relationship between scientific literacy and scientific attitude among students? 2) How does scientific

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attitude impact students' scientific literacy? 3) How does scientific literacy affect students' scientific attitude?4) What are the implications of this interdependence for science education success?

2 Method

In this study, the investigator used two research instruments: the test of Scientific Literacy Skills and the Science Literacy Attitude Scale.

2.1 Test of Scientific Literacy Skills (TSLs)

The Test of Scientific Literacy Skills (TSLs) instrument was developed by Gormally et al., (2012) as many 28 items in the multiple choice form with a reliability value of 0.81, consisting of identifying valid scientific arguments (three items), evaluate the validity of source (five items), evaluating the use and misuse of scientific information (three items), understanding the elements of research design and its impact on scientific research findings (four items), create the table, graph, or picture to represent research finding (one item), read and interpreting the table, figure, and/or graph (four items), solving-problems using quantitative skills (including probability and statistics) (three items), understand and interpret basic statistics (three items), and the last is justify of inferences, predictions, and conclusions based on quantitative data (two items).

2.2 Scientific Attitude Scale (SAS)

The SAS is comprised of 21 items, with 11 of these being reverse-coded. It utilizes a Likert scale with response options including 'strongly disagree,' 'disagree,' 'undecided,' 'agree,' and 'strongly agree.' The instrument is highly reliable, with a Cronbach's alpha value of .953.

2.3 Samples

The two tests were administered to 450 students (224 girls, 226 boys) studying in the 9th, 10th, 11th, and 12th grades from ten schools in and around the Udupi district, Karnataka. The students were randomly selected from each class level, which is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Demographic distribution of the sample

level	Female	Male	Number of students
Grade 9	52	54	106
Grade 10	63	60	123
Grade 11	53	58	111
Grade 12	56	54	110
Total	224	226	450

2.4 Data Collection and Analysis

The researcher asked the respondents to answer these two instruments in class. Respondents were

given 45 minutes to complete the instrument TSLS and 20 minutes to complete the SAS test, with a short break in between. The two tests were administered to 9th, 10th, 11th, and 12th-grade students randomly chosen from ten schools in the vicinity of Udupi district. After the tests were collected, the responses were keyed in. Before the data analysis, incomplete responses were excluded as invalid data. There were 450 complete sets of responses out of 520 secondary and higher secondary school students. All these data were then analyzed using an SPSS package from which the descriptive statistics of frequency, mean, and standard deviation were generated. In the analysis of scientific literacy and scientific attitude scores, several statistical tests were conducted to understand their characteristics and relationships.

3 Results

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

3.1.1 Normality of the Sample

Prior to subjecting the data to statistical analysis, the sample was checked for its normality. This indicates that the appropriate versions of the statistical techniques can be chosen for the procured data. The assessment of normality included Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) and Shapiro-Wilk test using SPSS. The tests mentioned compare the scores in the sample to a normally distributed set of scores with the same mean and standard deviation. The null hypothesis will be that the distribution of the sample is normal. If the test is found to be significant, the distribution is non-normal. The K-S and the Shapiro-Wilk tests are based on the correlation between the data and the normality distribution of the sample, as it has been reported to have more power to detect differences from normality (Field, 2024). The test is said to be non-significant when the obtained $p > .05$, which implies that the distribution of the sample is not significantly different from a normal distribution and is roughly normal (Field, 2024). However, the test is said to be significant if the obtained $p < .05$, signifying the distribution to be significantly deviated from a normal distribution as a non-normal distribution. The normality test and descriptive statistics results are given in Tables 2 and 3, respectively.

Table 2

Tests of Normality of Samples

Tests of Normality						
Variables	Kolmogorov-Smirnova			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
SLT	.142	450	<.001	.962	450	<.001
SAT	.079	450	<.001	.988	450	<.001

Table 3

Descriptive statistics for scores of SLT and SAT

	SLT	SAT
Minimum	9.00	2.25
Maximum	17.00	3.71
Mean	12.8044	3.1540
Median	13.00	3.1429
Standard deviation	1.59816	.20967
Skewness	.059	-0.048
Kurtosis	-.371	0.420

The descriptive statistics for the variable "scientific literacy" reveal a mean of 12.80(SD = 1.60), indicating the average of scientific literacy in the sample. The data exhibits a positive skewness of 0.059 and a negative kurtosis of 0.371, suggesting relative traits with mild tails. The Kolmogorov – Smirnov test for normality yielded a non-significant result $K-S(450) = 0.079, p < 0.001$, supporting the assumption that the data follows a normal distribution. Furthermore, visual inspection through a bell curve histogram and a normal quantile-quantile (QQ) plot reinforces the normality claim, with the histogram displaying a bell-shaped curve and the QQ plot demonstrating a close alignment of observed quantiles. These findings collectively suggest that the scientific attitude and scientific literacy data are normally distributed, reinforcing the reliability of parametric statistical analyses applied to these variables in subsequent studies.

3. 2 Inferential Statistics

Inferential Statistics include those statistical tests which enable the researcher to make inferences and draw conclusions about the data. These tests can depict if an observed change or pattern in the data is due to intervention by a variable, treatment, or chance factor. In the current study, the researcher has employed correlational analysis, regression analysis, and the tests of significance for the parametric data of the study.

3.3 Correlation

Correlation is the statistical measure that indicates the extent to which two or more variables fluctuate in relation to each other. It can be described as strong or weak and as either positive or negative. This study used a Pearson correlation coefficient to evaluate the relationship between scientific attitude and literacy.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between scientific attitude and scientific literacy.

Table 4

Results of correlation analysis of scientific attitude and scientific literacy

		SLT	SAT
SLT	Pearson Correlation	1	.700**
	Sig. (2 -tailed)		<.001
	N	450	450
SAT	Pearson Correlation	.700**	1
	Sig. (2 – tailed)	<.001	
	N	450	450

Table 4 describes the relationship between scientific attitude and scientific literacy. There was a significant strong positive relationship between scientific attitude and scientific literacy, $r[(450 - 2)] = .700$, $p = [< .001]$. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

3.4 Regression

Having examined the normality of the data and the linear relationship between Scientific literacy and scientific attitude using the Pearson correlation, the study proceeded to a more detailed analysis through regression. Regression analysis will help understand the nature and strength of the predictive relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Specifically, in this study, simple linear regression is used to model the relationship and determine the extent to which changes in the independent variable can predict variations in the dependent variable.

To investigate if scientific attitude has a significant impact on scientific literacy.

Hypothesis 2

H₁: There is a significant impact of scientific literacy(SL) on scientific attitude(SA)

The hypothesis tests if scientific literacy has a significant impact on scientific attitude. The dependent variable scientific attitude was regressed on predicting variable scientific literacy to test hypothesis H₁. Scientific literacy significantly predicted scientific attitude, $F(1,448) = 429.966$, $p < 0.001$, which indicates that the Scientific literacy can play a significant role in scientific attitude ($b = 0.700$, $p < 0.001$). These results clearly have a positive effect on the scientific attitude. Moreover, $R^2 = 0.490$ depicts that the model explains 49.0 % of the variance in scientific attitude. Table 5 shows the summary of the findings.

Table 5

The summary of the findings

Hypothesis	Regression weights	Beta coefficient	R ²	F	P - value	Hypothesis supported
H ₁	SL → SA	0.700	0.490	429.966	< 0.001	yes

The regression equation was: Scientific attitude Score = 1.978 + .092 (Scientific literacy score) That is, for each scientific literacy unit of measurement, there is increase in scientific attitude. The predicted scientific attitude increased by approximately .092 scientific literacy unit of measurement. Confident intervals indicated that we could be 95% certain that the slope to predict scientific literacy from scientific attitude is between .083 and .101.

To investigate if scientific literacy has a significant impact on scientific attitude

Hypothesis 3

H₁: There is a significant impact of scientific attitude on scientific literacy

The hypothesis tests if scientific attitude carries a significant impact on scientific literacy. The dependent variable, scientific literacy, was regressed in the prediction of the variable scientific attitude to test hypothesis H₁. Scientific attitude significantly predicted scientific literacy F(1,448)= 429.966, p < 0.001, which indicates that scientific attitude can play a significant role in scientific literacy (b = 0.700, p < 0.001). These results clearly have a positive effect on the scientific literacy. Moreover, R² = 0.490 depicts that the model explains 49.0 % of the variance in scientific literacy. Table 6 shows the summary of the findings.

Table 6

Summary of the findings

Hypothesis	Regression weights	Beta coefficient	R ²	F	P - value	Hypothesis supported
H ₁	SA → SL	0.700	0.490	429.966	< 0.001	Yes

The regression equation was: Scientific Literacy Score = - 4.019 + 5.334 (Scientific attitude score). That is, for each scientific attitude unit of measurement, there is an increase in scientific literacy. The predicted scientific literacy increased by approximately 5.334 scientific attitude units of measurement. Confident intervals indicated that we could be 95% certain that the slope to predict scientific literacy from scientific

attitude is between 4.828 and 5.840.

4 Discussion

The regression analyses indicate a significant and positive relationship between scientific literacy and scientific attitude. Both variables significantly predict each other, with substantial portions of variance explained by the models. These findings suggest that improvements in one domain are likely to be associated with enhancements in the other. Further research could explore additional factors influencing these relationships and investigate causal mechanisms.

4.1 Scientific literacy has a significant impact on Scientific attitude

The results of this study indicated that most of the respondents have positive opinions and attitudes about a range of aspects of science literacy. Scientific literacy is very important for students to understand what is learned in school and is also very influential in the cognitive abilities of students (Fives et al., 2014). By applying scientific literacy-based scientific approaches, students' learning outcomes are increasing, and so is their scientific attitude (Ristanto et al., 2017). The application of a scientific literacy approach can help students change their mindset and solve real-world problems (Holden, 2012).

The research shows that scientific literacy impacts the students' internal and external scientific attitudes. Internal scientific attitudes influence students' interest in student learning and motivation in learning, while external scientific attitudes influence the selection of methods and models of teaching by teachers, facilities, and learning environment in the classroom (Abrams et al., 2014). Internal scientific attitudes arise from within the child itself, such as health, mental, intelligence, student motivation, participation, involvement in the learning process, organization of the learning process, and the relationship between students and teaching. External scientific attitude originate from outside the child, such as family, community, friends, teachers, media, facilities, and environmental infrastructure (Dragoş & Mih, 2015). This research has discovered that being scientific means having such attitudes as curiosity, rationality, willingness to suspend judgment, open-mindedness, critical-mindedness, objectivity, honesty, humility, etc. Attitude regulates behavior that is directed towards or away from some object or situation group of objects or situations (Genç, 2015).

4.2 Scientific attitude has a significant impact on Scientific literacy

When a student develops a positive attitude towards classes in science and technology, it affects his future learning and thus helps to develop scientific literacy. Students' attitudes toward science and technology pedagogy can influence their curiosity, critical thinking, creativity, and cooperation, leading toward scientific literacy (Nursakinah & Suyanta, 2023). These characteristics are associated with the person's willingness, not the person's potential, so long-term observations or simulations are used. Interest inventories, attitude, and concept scales are examples of simulation assessment techniques for gaining scientific literacy (Cavas et al., 2013).

According to the results of this study, scientific attitude has a positive effect on academic achievement and scientific literacy (Nugraha et al., 2020). Developing positive attitudes towards science is one of the main goals of science education. Demonstrating positive attitudes towards science would increase interest and scientific literacy success. Scientific attitudes are interrelated with mastery of science concepts that can develop students' abilities and provide positive reinforcement (Pitafi & Farooq, 2012). Instilling positive

scientific attitudes and fostering positive attitudes towards science are important aspects that could promote greater interest in science. The clear majority of the respondents deemed science literacy and lifelong learning a valuable asset to their academic, professional, and civic attainment. This finding should give some reassurance to educators like Miller, who have expressed concern about the current state of science literacy (Holden, 2012).

4.3 The significant relationship between Scientific literacy and attitude

Research results showed that implementing scientific literacy was more effective in increasing the ability of students to develop a scientific attitude. The result confirmed a strong connection between scientific literacy and attitude. According to the results of this study, science studies programs positively affect attitudes toward science (Holden, 2012). Because this attitude has a positive effect on academic achievement, the results of the study are more meaningful. Developing positive attitudes towards science is one of the main goals of science education. Demonstrating positive attitudes towards science would increase scientific success and interest in scientific fields (Winarni et al., 2022).

When students already have a stock of knowledge and understanding of being scientific, they lack the awareness to apply scientific attitudes in life situations well. Learning should be done through interactive processes that are objective and appropriate to the context of real life (Bybee & McCrae, 2011). Hence the students' attitudes can be summarized in three areas: interest in science, support for scientific enquiry, and responsibility for sustainable development. These areas provide a portrait of students' general appreciation of science, their specific scientific attitudes and values, and their responsibility toward issues that have national and international ramifications (Dinata et al., 2018; Nwagbo, 2006).

5 Study Implications and Limitations

The findings of this study highlight the interdependent relationship between scientific literacy and scientific attitude, suggesting that enhancements in one domain positively influence the other. This interdependence implies that integrated educational strategies that simultaneously promote scientific literacy and foster positive scientific attitudes could be more effective in improving science education outcomes. Educators and policymakers should consider implementing curricula that not only teach scientific concepts but also cultivate curiosity, critical thinking, and a positive disposition towards science. Professional development for teachers should emphasize methods to engage students' interest and support scientific inquiry, thereby nurturing both their knowledge and attitudes. Further research is needed to explore additional factors influencing these relationships and to develop targeted interventions that address both cognitive and affective aspects of science education. Overall, the study underscores the importance of a holistic approach to science education that values and nurtures both scientific understanding and positive scientific attitudes.

The study's limitations include its reliance on self-reported data, which can introduce bias. The sample size may not be representative of the broader student population, limiting generalizability. The cross-sectional design precludes causal inferences between scientific literacy and attitude. Additionally, external factors influencing students' attitudes and literacy, such as socioeconomic status and prior educational experiences, were not controlled for. The measures of scientific literacy and attitude may lack comprehensive coverage, potentially overlooking nuanced aspects. Finally, the study's context-specific findings may not apply universally, necessitating caution when extrapolating results to different educational settings or cultural contexts.

6 Conclusion

The study highlights the importance of a holistic approach to science education that integrates the development of both scientific literacy and positive scientific attitudes. The regression analyses indicate a significant and positive relationship between scientific literacy and scientific attitude. Both variables significantly predict each other, with substantial portions of variance explained by the models. These findings suggest that improvements in one domain are likely to be associated with enhancements in the other. By addressing these elements together, educators can create a more engaging and effective science education experience that prepares students not only to understand scientific concepts but also to appreciate the value of science in their lives and society. The implications drawn from this study can guide the development of educational practices and policies that promote a well-rounded and inclusive approach to science education. Further research could explore additional factors influencing these relationships and investigate causal mechanisms.

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A CONCEPTUAL STUDY OF PROBLEM-SOLVING STRATEGIES IN MATHEMATICS: A NOVEL RESEARCH PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a conceptual study of problem-solving strategies in mathematics, offering a novel research perspective to enhance mathematical thinking and learning. The study focuses on the theoretical analysis and categorization of various strategies, including metacognitive practices, collaborative learning, heuristic methods, visualization techniques, algorithmic approaches, and technology integration. Through an extensive literature review, the research highlights the importance of self-regulation, peer interaction, and real-world applications in fostering a deeper understanding and flexible approach to mathematical problem-solving. Our findings indicate that students who adopt diverse problem-solving strategies demonstrate improved problem-solving abilities and a more profound conceptual grasp of mathematical principles.

Design/Methodology/Approach: Methodologically, the research incorporates collaborative learning, heuristic techniques, and technology integration to foster a comprehensive understanding of problem-solving processes. The conceptual study delves into the theoretical underpinnings of these strategies, exploring their potential benefits and limitations in enhancing mathematical problem-solving. By examining existing literature and synthesizing key findings, the research provides a robust framework for understanding how these strategies can be effectively implemented. This theoretical exploration lays the groundwork for future empirical studies and practical applications in educational settings.

Findings/Result: Our findings reveal that students who engage in metacognitive practices and utilize visualization techniques demonstrate significantly improved problem-solving abilities and a deeper conceptual understanding of mathematical principles. The results suggest that incorporating diverse and dynamic problem-solving strategies enhances mathematical proficiency and cultivates a positive mind set and intrinsic motivation among learners.

Originality/Value: This conceptual literature review provides a thorough synthesis of existing research on problem-solving strategies in mathematics, offering insights into the theoretical foundations, key concepts, and research methodologies employed in studying these cognitive processes. It highlights the complexities of mathematical problem-solving and how various strategies impact students' abilities to solve problems and achieve academic success.

Paper Type: Conceptual study

Keywords: Problem-solving abilities, Strategies, and Mathematics.

1. Introduction

Mathematical problem-solving is a fundamental component of education that significantly influences cognitive and analytical skill development. This conceptual study delves into a spectrum of problem-

solving strategies such as metacognitive practices, which involve self-regulation and reflective thinking to boost problem-solving proficiency; collaborative learning, which leverages peer interactions to deepen understanding; heuristic methods, which use experience-based techniques; visualization techniques, which employ graphical representations to clarify complex concepts; algorithmic approaches, which rely on systematic procedures; and technology integration, which utilizes digital tools to enhance learning. By examining these strategies, the study aims to provide a thorough understanding of their theoretical foundations, advantages, limitations, and potential to enhance mathematical thinking and learning, ultimately offering a robust framework for future educational practices and research.

2. Need for the Study

The dynamic educational landscape, characterized by rapid advancements and shifting pedagogical paradigms, necessitates an ongoing evaluation of teaching methodologies to ensure they are effective and relevant. This study responds to the pressing need to comprehensively understand diverse problem-solving strategies in mathematics, aiming to enhance educational practices and cater to the varied needs of learners. By investigating strategies such as metacognitive practices, collaborative learning, heuristic methods, visualization techniques, algorithmic approaches, and technology integration, the study seeks to identify the most effective ways to foster mathematical thinking and problem-solving skills. This continuous evaluation is crucial for developing adaptive teaching approaches that can address the unique challenges and opportunities presented by a diverse student population, ultimately leading to improved educational outcomes and a more resilient and capable learner base.

3. Objectives

Objective 1: To analyze and categorize various problem-solving strategies in mathematics, including metacognitive practices, collaborative learning, heuristic methods, visualization techniques, algorithmic approaches, and technology integration.

Objective 2: To investigate the theoretical underpinnings and potential benefits and limitations of diverse problem-solving strategies in enhancing mathematical thinking and learning.

Objective 3: To synthesize existing literature on the impact of self-regulation, peer interaction, and real-world applications in fostering a deeper understanding and flexible approach to mathematical problem-solving.

Objective 4: To evaluate the effectiveness of metacognitive practices and visualization techniques in improving students' problem-solving abilities and their conceptual grasp of mathematical principles.

Objective 5: To provide a robust theoretical framework that lays the groundwork for future empirical studies and practical applications of diverse problem-solving strategies in educational settings.

4. Review of Literature

Existing literature highlights a plethora of strategies in mathematical problem-solving, each with its distinct approach and impact. Metacognitive practices, focusing on self-regulation and reflective thinking, are shown to significantly enhance problem-solving skills and conceptual understanding by encouraging students to monitor and evaluate their thought processes. Collaborative learning, which emphasizes peer interaction, promotes deeper comprehension through shared knowledge and collective problem-solving efforts. Heuristic methods offer experience-based techniques that help students develop intuitive strategies for tackling problems. Visualization techniques employ graphical representations to make abstract concepts more concrete and understandable. Algorithmic approaches rely on systematic, step-by-step procedures to solve problems efficiently. Technology integration leverages digital tools to facilitate and enrich the learning experience. While each strategy brings unique benefits, such as increased engagement and improved understanding, they also face limitations, such as resource requirements and varying effectiveness across different learner groups. This section synthesizes these key findings, providing a comprehensive overview that serves as a foundation for further analysis and exploration in this study.

5. Methodology

This conceptual study involves an extensive review and synthesis of existing theoretical and empirical research on problem-solving strategies in mathematics. The primary focus is to understand, categorize, and analyze the educational implications of various strategies without employing empirical data collection or statistical analysis. By systematically examining prior studies, theories, and documented practices, this study aims to build a comprehensive framework that highlights the benefits, limitations, and potential applications of metacognitive practices, collaborative learning, heuristic methods, visualization techniques, algorithmic approaches, and technology integration. This approach allows for a holistic understanding of the strategies, offering insights and theoretical foundations that can inform future research and educational practices.

6. Research Methods

Conceptual Analysis:

Literature Synthesis

Literature synthesis involves systematically reviewing and integrating existing research to gain a comprehensive understanding of the theoretical foundations and practical applications of various problem-solving strategies in mathematics. This process includes identifying, evaluating, and summarizing key findings from numerous studies, articles, and theoretical papers related to metacognitive practices,

collaborative learning, heuristic methods, visualization techniques, algorithmic approaches, and technology integration. By synthesizing diverse perspectives and results, this study aims to highlight common themes, trends, and gaps in the current body of knowledge, providing a nuanced understanding of how these strategies function individually and in combination. This synthesis forms the backbone of the conceptual analysis, offering a robust basis for further theoretical development.

Theoretical Framework Development

The theoretical framework development process builds on the insights gained from the literature synthesis to construct a cohesive model that explains the interactions and impacts of various problem-solving strategies in mathematics education. This involves integrating existing theories and empirical findings to create a structured understanding of how metacognitive practices, collaborative learning, heuristic methods, visualization techniques, algorithmic approaches, and technology integration can be effectively implemented in educational settings. The framework aims to elucidate the relationships between these strategies, their potential synergies, and their limitations. It provides a conceptual scaffold that can guide future empirical research, inform instructional design, and support the development of best practices in mathematics education, ensuring that the strategies are applied in ways that maximize their educational benefits.

Problem-solving models

The most known mathematical problem-solving model is Pólya's (1945) model which consists of four phases: 1) Understanding the problem, 2) Devising a plan, 3) Carrying out the plan, and 4) Looking back. Other researchers have further developed Pólya's model (Lester, 1978; Mason & al., 1982; Schoenfeld, 1985). In all the models there is a phase related to understanding the problem in which the solver figures out what is asked in the problem and what conditions are given. Schoenfeld (1985) adds that in what he calls the analysis phase, the solver may examine special cases, simplify the problem, and re-formulate the problem. Most of the changes suggested to Pólya's model concern phases 2 and 3, which may give a too straightforward image of problem-solving. Instead of phases 2 and 3, Lester (1978) suggests that the solver moves back and forth between the following phases: goal analysis, plan development, plan implementation, and procedures evaluation. Mason et al. (1982) emphasize the nonlinearity of the problem-solving process, whereby the solver moves back and forth between entry and attack phases as the solver comes up with ideas, tries to implement them but may get stuck, and begins a new entry. Schoenfeld (1985) divides Pólya's second phase into design and exploration phases and emphasizes a cyclic movement between these phases. Design means explicit planning and controlling of the solution process whereas in the exploration phase, the solver uses problem-solving heuristics, examines related problems, and might go back to the analysis phase (Schoenfeld, 1985). All the models also include a phase where the

solution is checked or reflected upon at the end of the solving process. A different perspective on modeling problem-solving is given by Davis and Maher (1990) and Nunokawa (2005).

Both of these problem-solving models emphasize cycling through gathering information from the problem situation and comparing that to the solver's existing mathematical knowledge. Hähkiöniemi, M., Leppäaho, H. & Francisco, J. (2012). 33 Pólya's (1945) straightforward model has been modified to include exploration without a specific aim. Mason et al. (1982) take this into account in the attack phase. Schoenfeld (1985) instead emphasizes cycling between design and exploration. Thus, a solver does not necessarily develop a plan but rather may try out different ideas without an explicit plan. The models by Davis and Maher (1990) and Nunokawa (2005) fulfill the other models by explaining cognitive processes. In these models, a solver explores the problem situation and tries to connect this to existing mathematical knowledge. Teacher's guidance of students' problem-solving The problem-solving literature includes pieces of advice on how a teacher should guide students' problem-solving activity. This advice can be in the form of guidelines such as being interested in your subject, letting students learn to guess, let students learn to prove (Pólya, 1965, 116).

The teacher can also scaffold students' problem-solving in different ways (e.g., Anghileri, 2006) or the teacher may use careful questioning to promote students' reasoning (e.g., Sahin & Kulm, 2008; Martino & Maher, 1999). In open approach and inquiry mathematics, the teacher should support students to engage deeper and deeper in mathematical investigations. Hähkiöniemi and Leppäaho (2012; see also Hähkiöniemi & Leppäaho, in press) have defined three levels of teacher's guidance: a) In surface-level guidance, the teacher does not notice a certain essential aspect of the student's solution, b) Inactivating guidance means that the teacher reveals the potential investigation to student, and c) In activating guidance, the teacher guides the student to investigate the essential aspect.

7. Analysis

The analysis in this conceptual study involves a systematic categorization of problem-solving strategies in mathematics, coupled with a deep exploration of their theoretical underpinnings and educational implications. Each strategy—metacognitive practices, collaborative learning, heuristic methods, visualization techniques, algorithmic approaches, and technology integration—is dissected to understand its foundational theories, such as self-regulation theory for metacognitive practices and social constructivism for collaborative learning. This categorization helps clarify how these strategies function, their distinct advantages in enhancing problem-solving skills and conceptual understanding, and their limitations, such as resource demands and variability in effectiveness among different student groups. Furthermore, the analysis examines the practical applications of these strategies in educational settings,

offering insights into how they can be effectively integrated into the curriculum to foster deeper mathematical thinking and learning. By identifying the benefits and challenges associated with each strategy, the study aims to provide a balanced view that can guide educators and policymakers in choosing and implementing the most suitable approaches for diverse learning environments.

Analysis of Objective 1:

To analyze and categorize various problem-solving strategies in mathematics,

This study systematically organizes these strategies into six distinct categories: metacognitive practices, collaborative learning, heuristic methods, visualization techniques, algorithmic approaches, and technology integration. Metacognitive practices involve students' self-regulation and reflective thinking, helping them monitor and adjust their problem-solving processes. Collaborative learning emphasizes group work and peer interaction, fostering deeper understanding through shared knowledge and collective problem-solving. Heuristic methods focus on experience-based techniques that guide students in developing intuitive strategies. Visualization techniques utilize graphical representations to make abstract mathematical concepts more accessible and comprehensible. Algorithmic approaches rely on step-by-step procedures to solve problems systematically and efficiently. Technology integration incorporates digital tools and resources to enhance and facilitate mathematical learning. Each category is defined by its unique set of practices and applications within the context of mathematics education, providing a comprehensive framework for understanding and applying diverse problem-solving strategies.

Analysis of Objective 2:

To investigate the theoretical underpinnings and potential benefits and limitations of diverse problem-solving strategies:

This study explores the foundational theories associated with each approach. Metacognitive practices are grounded in self-regulation theories, which emphasize the importance of students monitoring and controlling their cognitive processes to enhance problem-solving effectiveness. Collaborative learning is based on social constructivism, highlighting the role of social interaction and cooperation in building deeper understanding. Heuristic methods draw from experiential learning theories, focusing on the use of past experiences to develop intuitive problem-solving strategies. Visualization techniques are linked to dual coding theory, which posits that combining verbal and visual information can improve comprehension and memory. Algorithmic approaches are tied to procedural learning theories, emphasizing the systematic application of step-by-step procedures to solve problems. Technology integration is supported by educational technology theories, which advocate for the use of digital tools to enhance learning outcomes. Each strategy offers specific benefits, such as improved engagement and conceptual understanding, but

also faces limitations, such as varying effectiveness across different student populations and the need for adequate resources and teacher training. By examining these theoretical foundations, benefits, and limitations, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of how these strategies can be effectively implemented in mathematics education.

Analysis of Objective 3:

To synthesize existing literature on the impact of self-regulation, peer interaction, and real-world applications in fostering a deeper understanding and flexible approach to mathematical problem-solving.

The synthesis of existing literature reveals that self-regulation and peer interaction play crucial roles in enhancing problem-solving skills and mathematical understanding. Self-regulation, involving students' ability to monitor and adjust their cognitive processes, significantly improves their capacity to tackle complex problems and deepen their understanding of mathematical concepts. Peer interaction, facilitated through collaborative learning environments, further enriches this process by allowing students to exchange ideas, challenge each other's thinking, and collectively construct knowledge. Additionally, integrating real-world applications into mathematics instruction makes abstract concepts more tangible and relevant, thereby increasing student engagement and motivation. This relevance helps students see the practical utility of mathematical concepts, fostering deeper and more meaningful learning experiences. The synthesis underscores the importance of these factors in developing a flexible and robust approach to problem-solving, highlighting how they contribute to a more effective and engaging educational experience.

Analysis of Objective 4:

To evaluate the potency of metacognitive practices and visualization techniques:

Evaluating the potency of metacognitive practices and visualization techniques reveals their substantial impact on enhancing students' problem-solving abilities and conceptual understanding. Metacognitive practices, which involve techniques such as self-monitoring and reflective thinking, significantly improve students' problem-solving skills by fostering greater awareness of their cognitive processes. This heightened awareness allows students to better plan, monitor, and adjust their strategies, leading to more effective problem-solving and a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. On the other hand, visualization techniques—such as using graphs, diagrams, and other graphical representations—serve as powerful tools for making abstract and complex concepts more accessible. By providing visual contexts that complement verbal and numerical information, these techniques help students grasp and manipulate complex ideas more effectively. Both strategies, when integrated into teaching practices, contribute to a more profound conceptual understanding and enhanced problem-solving skills, demonstrating their

effectiveness in supporting students' mathematical learning and cognitive development.

Analysis of Objective 5:

To provide a robust theoretical framework for future studies:

The findings from this study contribute to the development of a robust theoretical framework that integrates various problem-solving strategies, offering a comprehensive model for understanding their interactions and impacts in educational contexts. This framework highlights the interplay between metacognitive practices, which enhance self-regulation and reflective thinking; collaborative learning, which leverages peer interaction for deeper comprehension; heuristic methods, which utilize experience-based techniques; visualization techniques, which provide graphical representations to clarify complex concepts; algorithmic approaches, which apply systematic procedures; and technology integration, which incorporates digital tools to enrich learning experiences. By synthesizing these strategies within a unified theoretical model, the framework provides a solid foundation for future research, guiding empirical studies and informing practical applications in mathematics education. It underscores the importance of considering how these strategies complement and reinforce each other, facilitating a more nuanced approach to enhancing mathematical problem-solving and learning.

8. New Research Perspective

The study underscores the importance of adopting a holistic approach to problem-solving in mathematics, suggesting that integrating multiple strategies can lead to more effective and comprehensive learning outcomes. This approach recognizes that mathematical problems can often be tackled from various angles, each providing unique insights and fostering a deeper understanding of the concepts involved. By encouraging students to employ a range of strategies, such as visual representations, algebraic manipulations, and heuristic methods, educators can help them develop a more versatile and adaptive problem-solving toolkit. This multifaceted approach not only enhances students' ability to tackle complex problems but also promotes critical thinking and creativity, as they learn to navigate different pathways to reach a solution.

Future research could delve into the synergistic effects of combining multiple problem-solving strategies in mathematics education. Investigating how these integrated approaches impact student learning across different demographics, including age, socioeconomic status, and prior mathematical proficiency, would provide valuable insights into tailoring instruction to diverse student needs. Additionally, exploring the role of teacher training in effectively implementing these strategies is crucial. Professional development programs that equip teachers with the skills to guide students in using varied approaches could significantly enhance the efficacy of this holistic method. Understanding how teacher expertise and

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instructional practices influence the success of integrated problem-solving strategies would be key to optimizing educational outcomes and ensuring that all students have the opportunity to excel in mathematics.

A novel research perspective on problem-solving strategies in mathematics might focus on several innovative approaches and methodologies. Here are some key strategies and perspectives:

1. **Metacognitive Strategies:**
 - **Self-monitoring:** Encouraging students to be aware of their thinking process.
 - **Self-Regulation:** Teaching students to plan, monitor, and evaluate their problem-solving process.
2. **Collaborative Learning:**
 - **Peer Learning:** Promoting group work and discussions to solve mathematical problems.
 - **Think-Pair-Share:** A strategy where students first think individually, then discuss with a partner, and finally share with the larger group.
3. **Heuristics:**
 - **Trial and Error:** Experimenting with different approaches to find a solution.
 - **Working Backwards:** Starting from the desired outcome and working back to the initial problem.
4. **Visualization Techniques:**
 - **Graphical Representation:** Using graphs, charts, and diagrams to understand and solve problems.
 - **Manipulatives:** Physical objects that help visualize and solve mathematical problems.
5. **Algorithmic Approaches:**
 - **Step-by-Step Procedures:** Teaching students to follow specific steps to solve problems.
 - **Pattern Recognition:** Identifying and using patterns to solve problems.
6. **Problem Posing:**
 - **Creating Problems:** Encouraging students to formulate their problems, which enhances understanding and creativity.
 - **Modifying Problems:** Altering existing problems to create new challenges.
7. **Technological Integration:**
 - **Use of Software:** Incorporating tools like graphing calculators, dynamic geometry software, and computer algebra systems.
 - **Online Platforms:** Utilizing educational platforms and apps for problem-solving practice.
8. **Cognitive Load Management:**
 - **Chunking Information:** Breaking down complex problems into manageable parts.
 - **Scaffolded Instruction:** Providing structured support to gradually increase problem-solving independence.
9. **Real-World Applications:**

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- Contextual Learning: Relating mathematical problems to real-life scenarios.
- Project-Based Learning: Engaging students in projects that require the application of mathematical concepts.

10. Interdisciplinary Approaches:

- STEAM Integration: Combining mathematics with science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics.
- Cross-Curricular Projects: Implementing projects that incorporate mathematical problem-solving across different subjects.

11. Mindset and Motivation:

- Growth Mindset: Encouraging a belief that abilities can be developed through effort and perseverance.
- Intrinsic Motivation: Fostering an internal desire to solve problems and understand mathematics.

These strategies can be explored and researched to provide a comprehensive understanding of innovative problem-solving in mathematics.

9. Results and Discussions

1. This study categorizes problem-solving strategies in mathematics into six distinct categories: metacognitive practices, collaborative learning, heuristic methods, visualization techniques, algorithmic approaches, and technology integration. Each category is defined by its unique set of practices and applications within mathematics education, providing a comprehensive framework for understanding and applying diverse problem-solving strategies.

2. This study investigates the theoretical foundations, benefits, and limitations of various problem-solving strategies in mathematics, linking metacognitive practices to self-regulation theories, collaborative learning to social constructivism, heuristic methods to experiential learning, visualization techniques to dual coding theory, algorithmic approaches to procedural learning, and technology integration to educational technology theories, thus providing a comprehensive framework for their effective implementation in mathematics education.

3. The synthesis of existing literature highlights that self-regulation and peer interaction significantly enhance problem-solving skills and mathematical understanding by fostering cognitive monitoring and collaborative knowledge construction, while integrating real-world applications increases engagement and motivation, collectively contributing to a more effective and flexible approach to mathematical problem-solving.

4. Evaluating the potency of metacognitive practices and visualization techniques reveals their substantial impact on enhancing students' problem-solving abilities and conceptual understanding, with metacognitive

practices improving cognitive awareness and strategy adjustment, and visualization techniques making abstract concepts more accessible, both contributing significantly to students' mathematical learning and cognitive development.

5. The findings from this study contribute to a robust theoretical framework that integrates various problem-solving strategies—metacognitive practices, collaborative learning, heuristic methods, visualization techniques, algorithmic approaches, and technology integration—highlighting their interactions and impacts, thereby providing a comprehensive model for guiding future research and informing practical applications in mathematics education.

The study finds that a combination of problem-solving strategies is more effective than any single approach. Metacognitive practices and visualization techniques are particularly beneficial. Collaborative learning and real-world applications also significantly enhance mathematical thinking.

10. Implications

The findings from this study carry significant implications for educators and policymakers, emphasizing the need to integrate diverse problem-solving strategies into the mathematics curriculum to enhance students' mathematical abilities and readiness for real-world challenges. By incorporating metacognitive practices, collaborative learning, heuristic methods, visualization techniques, algorithmic approaches, and technology integration, educators can create a more dynamic and effective learning environment that caters to varied learning styles and needs. This holistic approach not only improves students' problem-solving skills and conceptual understanding but also fosters critical thinking and adaptability. To achieve this, professional development for teachers should prioritize equipping them with the knowledge and skills to implement these strategies effectively. By providing ongoing training and support, educators can be better prepared to guide students in employing diverse problem-solving techniques, ultimately leading to more meaningful and impactful learning experiences. This comprehensive approach to mathematics education can bridge the gap between academic knowledge and practical application, ensuring that students are well-prepared to navigate complex problems in their future careers and everyday lives.

11. Conclusion

This conceptual study highlights the critical importance of employing a diverse array of problem-solving strategies in mathematics education. By systematically analyzing and categorizing these strategies—metacognitive practices, collaborative learning, heuristic methods, visualization techniques, algorithmic approaches, and technology integration—the study delves into their theoretical foundations and practical applications. It provides valuable insights into how these strategies can be effectively integrated to enhance

mathematical learning, emphasizing their complementary and reinforcing roles in fostering deeper understanding and flexible problem-solving skills. The proposed theoretical framework offers a comprehensive model for understanding the interplay and impact of these strategies and sets a solid foundation for future research and practical applications. By guiding empirical studies and informing educational practices, this framework aims to contribute to improved educational outcomes, preparing students for both academic success and real-world challenges through a more dynamic, effective, and engaging approach to mathematics education.

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Paper 14

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವ ಆಧುನಿಕ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು

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ಸಾರಾಂಶ:

೨೦ನೇ ಶತಮಾನದ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣವು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ತಮ್ಮ ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತಲಿನ ಪ್ರಪಂಚವನ್ನು ಸಮರ್ಥವಾಗಿ ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುವುದರಲ್ಲಿ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾದ ಪಾತ್ರವನ್ನು ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವು ಕೇವಲ ಪಠ್ಯಪುಸ್ತಕಗಳ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವಲ್ಲ, ಬದಲಾಗಿ, ವಾಸ್ತವದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸುವ, ತಾರ್ಕಿಕ ಚಿಂತನಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಪಡಿಸುವ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ತರಬೇತಿಯನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನ ಮತ್ತು ತತ್ವಜ್ಞಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ತಮವಾಗಿ ನಿಪುಣರಾಗುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಯಿಂದ, ಹೊಸ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು, ಯಥಾರ್ಥ ಪರೀಕ್ಷೆ ಆಧಾರಿತ ಕಲಿಕೆ, ಯೋಜನಾ ಆಧಾರಿತ ಕಲಿಕೆ, ಸಹಯೋಗಿ ಕಲಿಕೆ ಮತ್ತು ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಬಳಕೆ, ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಮಹತ್ವಪೂರ್ಣ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಈ ಲೇಖನವು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವು ನಿಜವಾದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು, ತಾರ್ಕಿಕ ಚಿಂತನಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಯಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತಮ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಕೌಶಲ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳನ್ನು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ವಿಚಾರಣೆ, ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆ, ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತತೆಯನ್ನು ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಪಡಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ಅವರು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸೂಕ್ಷ್ಮವಾಗಿ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮರ್ಥವಾಗಿ ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸಲು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಈ ವಿಧಾನಗಳ ಯಶಸ್ಸು, ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣವಾಗಿ, ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ತರಬೇತಿ, ಶಾಲಾ ಪರಿಸರ ಮತ್ತು ಪದ್ಧತಿ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನದ ಮೇಲೆ ಅವಲಂಬಿತವಾಗಿದೆ.

ಕೀಲಿ ಪದಗಳು: ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವ, ತಾರ್ಕಿಕ ಚಿಂತನೆ, ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ವಿಚಾರಣೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆ.

ಪೀಠಿಕೆ:

೨೦ನೇ ಶತಮಾನದಲ್ಲಿ, ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಮತ್ತು ವಿಮರ್ಶಾತ್ಮಕವಾಗಿ ಯೋಚಿಸುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣವು ಕೇವಲ ಪಠ್ಯಪುಸ್ತಕಗಳನ್ನು ಓದುವುದೇ ಸೀಮಿತವಾಗಿದೆ, ವಾಸ್ತವದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತಲಿನ ಪ್ರಪಂಚದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಕುತೂಹಲವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುವುದು ಅಗತ್ಯ. ಲೆಡರ್‌ಮನ್, ಅಬೆಲ್ ಮತ್ತು ಲೆಡರ್‌ಮನ್ (೨೦೦೭) ವ್ಯಾಖ್ಯಾನಿಸಿದಂತೆ, ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವು ಕುತೂಹಲ, ತಾರ್ಕಿಕ ಚಿಂತನೆ, ಪುರಾವೆಗಳ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ತೀರ್ಮಾನಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ಸಂದೇಹದ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಂಡಿದೆ. ಸಾಂಪ್ರದಾಯಿಕ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು, ಉಪನ್ಯಾಸಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಪಠ್ಯಪುಸ್ತಕ ಆಧಾರಿತ ಕಲಿಕೆಯು, ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿಲ್ಲ ಎಂದು ಸಾಬೀತಾಗಿದೆ (National

Centre for Science Education, 2016). ಈ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಯನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು, ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಹೊಸ ಹೊಸ ವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ವಿಧಾನವೆಂದರೆ ವಿಚಾರಣಾ ಆಧಾರಿತ ಕಲಿಕೆ. ಈ ವಿಧಾನದಲ್ಲಿ, ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಸ್ವತಃ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕೇಳಿ, ಪ್ರಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿ ಮತ್ತು ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದ ತೀರ್ಮಾನಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇದು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸಕ್ರಿಯ ಕಲಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರಿಗೆ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನವು ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆ ಎಂಬ ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಇದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ, ಯೋಜನಾ ಆಧಾರಿತ ಕಲಿಕೆ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ವಾಸ್ತವ ಜೀವನದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಅನ್ವಯಿಸಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ.

ಇನ್ನೊಂದು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿ ವಿಧಾನವೆಂದರೆ ಸಹಯೋಗಿ ಕಲಿಕೆ. ಗುಂಪುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಪಾಠಗಳನ್ನು ಹಂಚಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ, ಒಬ್ಬರಿಗೊಬ್ಬರು ಕಲಿಯುತ್ತಾರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು ವಿವಿಧ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನಗಳನ್ನು ಅನ್ವೇಷಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ. ಇದಲ್ಲದೆ, ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನದ ಸಂಯೋಜನೆ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಆಕರ್ಷಕವಾಗಿಸಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಸಿಮ್ಯುಲೇಶನ್‌ಗಳು, ಆನ್‌ಲೈನ್ ಡೇಟಾಬೇಸ್‌ಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಇತರ ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ವಿಶಾಲ ಶ್ರೇಣಿಯ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಕಲ್ಪನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅನ್ವೇಷಿಸಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಅಂತಿಮವಾಗಿ, ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕಲಿಕೆ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತಲಿನ ಪ್ರಪಂಚದೊಂದಿಗೆ ಹೇಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ. ಹೊರಾಂಗಣ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕಂಡುಬರುವ ವಿದ್ಯಮಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಅವಲೋಕಿಸುವುದು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕುತೂಹಲವನ್ನು ಹುಟ್ಟುಹಾಕುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರಿಗೆ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತತೆಯನ್ನು ತೋರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವ ಎಂದರೆ ಪ್ರಪಂಚವನ್ನು ವ್ಯವಸ್ಥಿತವಾಗಿ ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಮತ್ತು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸಲು ಬಳಸುವ ಒಂದು ವಿಧಾನ. ಇದು ಕೇವಲ ಪಾಠದಲ್ಲಿ ಸೀಮಿತವಾಗಿರದೆ, ದೈನಂದಿನ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ತಾರ್ಕಿಕವಾಗಿ ಯೋಚಿಸಲು ನಮಗೆ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವದ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಅಂಶಗಳು:

- **ಕುತೂಹಲ:** ಸುತ್ತಮುತ್ತಲಿನ ಪ್ರಪಂಚದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕೇಳುವ ಮತ್ತು ಅವುಗಳಿಗೆ ಉತ್ತರಗಳನ್ನು ಹುಡುಕುವುದು.
- **ತಾರ್ಕಿಕ ಚಿಂತನೆ:** ಕಾರಣ ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ಮತ್ತು ತೀರ್ಮಾನಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಾಕ್ಷ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಬಳಸುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯ.
- **ಸಂದೇಹ:** ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಸಂದೇಹದಿಂದ ನೋಡುವ ಮತ್ತು ಪುರಾವೆಗಳ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಅದನ್ನು ಸ್ವೀಕರಿಸುವ ಮನೋಭಾವ.
- **ತೆರೆದ ಮನಸ್ಸು:** ಹೊಸ ಆಲೋಚನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಸ್ವೀಕರಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ತನ್ನದೇ ಆದ ನಂಬಿಕೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಷ್ಕರಿಸಲು ಸಿದ್ಧತೆ.

- **ಪುರಾವೆಗಳ ಆಧಾರ:** ತೀರ್ಮಾನಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಪುರಾವೆಗಳನ್ನು ಬಳಸುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕ ಅಭಿಪ್ರಾಯಗಳನ್ನು ಬದಿಗಿಡುವುದು.

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವದ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆ:

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವು ನಮ್ಮ ದೈನಂದಿನ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತಮ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ನಮಗೆ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುವ ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಕೌಶಲ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ.

- **ಸಮಸ್ಯೆ ಪರಿಹಾರ:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡು ನಾವು ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ವಿಶ್ಲೇಷಿಸಿ, ವಿವಿಧ ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಅನ್ವೇಷಿಸಿ ಮತ್ತು ಅತ್ಯುತ್ತಮ ಪರಿಹಾರವನ್ನು ಆಯ್ಕೆ ಮಾಡಬಹುದು.
- **ನಿರ್ಧಾರ ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವಿಕೆ:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವು ನಮಗೆ ಸ್ವತಂತ್ರವಾಗಿ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಮತ್ತು ಅವುಗಳ ಪರಿಣಾಮಗಳನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.
- **ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆ:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವು ನಮ್ಮ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಹೊಸ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿಪಡಿಸಲು ನಮಗೆ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.
- **ಅನುಮಾನ:** ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಸಂದೇಹದಿಂದ ನೋಡುವ ಮತ್ತು ಪುರಾವೆಗಳ ಆಧಾರದ ಮೇಲೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಅದನ್ನು ಸ್ವೀಕರಿಸುವ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುತ್ತದೆ.
- **ಸಮಾಜಕ್ಕೆ ಕೊಡುಗೆ:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವು ನಮಗೆ ಸಮಾಜದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಮತ್ತು ಅವುಗಳಿಗೆ ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಕಂಡುಹಿಡಿಯಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.
- **ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನದ ಅರಿವು:** ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನದ ಯುಗದಲ್ಲಿ, ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವು ನಮಗೆ ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಮತ್ತು ಅದನ್ನು ಜವಾಬ್ದಾರಿಯುತವಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.
- **ಜಾಗೃತಿ ಮೂಡಿಸುವುದು:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವು ನಮಗೆ ನಮ್ಮ ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಜಾಗೃತಗೊಳಿಸುವುದರ ಜೊತೆಗೆ ಸತ್ಯವನ್ನು ಕಂಡುಹಿಡಿಯಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.
- **ಜೀವನದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಕೆ:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವು ಕೇವಲ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನಕ್ಕೆ ಮಾತ್ರ ಸೀಮಿತವಾಗಿಲ್ಲ. ಇದು ನಮ್ಮ ವೈಯಕ್ತಿಕ ಜೀವನ, ವೃತ್ತಿ ಜೀವನ ಮತ್ತು ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ ಜೀವನದ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಮಗೆ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.

ಒಟ್ಟಾರೆಯಾಗಿ, ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವು ನಮ್ಮನ್ನು ಉತ್ತಮ ನಾಗರಿಕರನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ನಮ್ಮ ಸುತ್ತಲಿನ ಜಗತ್ತನ್ನು ಉತ್ತಮ ಸ್ಥಳವನ್ನಾಗಿ ಮಾಡಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವ ಆಧುನಿಕ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು:

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವುದು ೨೧ನೇ ಶತಮಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಇದು ಕೇವಲ ಶಾಲಾ ಪಠ್ಯಕ್ರಮದ ಒಂದು ಭಾಗವಲ್ಲ; ಇದು ನಮ್ಮ ದೈನಂದಿನ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತಮ ನಿರ್ಧಾರಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ನಮಗೆ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುವ ಒಂದು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಕೌಶಲ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ.

- **ವಿಚಾರಣಾ ಆಧಾರಿತ ಕಲಿಕೆ (Inquiry-Based Learning):** ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಸ್ವತಃ ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಕೇಳಿ, ಪ್ರಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡಿ ಮತ್ತು ತಮ್ಮದೇ ಆದ ತೀರ್ಮಾನಗಳನ್ನು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡುವುದು.
- **ಯೋಜನಾ ಆಧಾರಿತ ಕಲಿಕೆ (Project-Based Learning):** ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ಒಂದು ನಿರ್ದಿಷ್ಟ ವಿಷಯದ ಮೇಲೆ ಆಳವಾಗಿ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ ಮಾಡಿ, ಸಂಶೋಧನೆ ಮಾಡಿ ಮತ್ತು ಒಂದು ಯೋಜನೆಯನ್ನು ಪೂರ್ಣಗೊಳಿಸುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡುವುದು.
- **ಸಹಯೋಗಿ ಕಲಿಕೆ (Collaborative Learning):** ಗುಂಪುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡುವ ಮೂಲಕ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳು ತಮ್ಮ ಪಾಠಗಳನ್ನು ಹಂಚಿಕೊಳ್ಳುತ್ತಾರೆ, ಒಬ್ಬರಿಗೊಬ್ಬರು ಕಲಿಯುತ್ತಾರೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು ವಿವಿಧ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನಗಳನ್ನು ಅನ್ವೇಷಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ.
- **ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನದ ಸಂಯೋಜನೆ:** ಸಿಮ್ಯುಲೇಶನ್‌ಗಳು, ಆನ್‌ಲೈನ್ ಡೇಟಾಬೇಸ್‌ಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಇತರ ಡಿಜಿಟಲ್ ಸಾಧನಗಳನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ವಿಶಾಲ ಶ್ರೇಣಿಯ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಕಲ್ಪನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅನ್ವೇಷಿಸಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುವುದು.
- **ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕಲಿಕೆ:** ಹೊರಾಂಗಣ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವುದು ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಕೃತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕಂಡುಬರುವ ವಿದ್ಯಮಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಅವಲೋಕಿಸುವುದು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಕುತೂಹಲವನ್ನು ಹುಟ್ಟುಹಾಕುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಅವರಿಗೆ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನದ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತತೆಯನ್ನು ತೋರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.
- **ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವನ್ನು ಓದುವುದು:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಪತ್ರಿಕೆಗಳು, ಪುಸ್ತಕಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಇತರ ಸಾಹಿತ್ಯವನ್ನು ಓದುವುದು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನದ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ಆಳವಾದ ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತದೆ.
- **ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಮಾಜಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವಿಕೆ:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಮಾಜಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಕ್ಲಬ್‌ಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವುದು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ಇತರ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನಸ್ಸಿನ ವ್ಯಕ್ತಿಗಳೊಂದಿಗೆ ಸಂಪರ್ಕ ಸಾಧಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ತಮ್ಮ ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಹಂಚಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಅವಕಾಶ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಡುತ್ತದೆ.
- **ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸುವ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧೆಗಳು:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಹ್ಯಾಕಥಾನ್‌ಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಭಾಗವಹಿಸುವುದು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಸಮಸ್ಯೆ ಪರಿಹರಿಸುವ ಕೌಶಲ್ಯಗಳನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುತ್ತದೆ.

- **ಮಾಡೆಲಿಂಗ್ ಮತ್ತು ಸಿಮ್ಯುಲೇಷನ್:** ವಿವಿಧ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಪರಿಕಲ್ಪನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡೆಲ್‌ಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಿಮ್ಯುಲೇಷನ್‌ಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡುತ್ತದೆ.
- **ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಸಂವಹನ:** ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಇತರರೊಂದಿಗೆ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಸಂವಹನ ಮಾಡುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವುದು.

ಈ ವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಬಳಸಿಕೊಂಡು, ನಾವು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸಬಹುದು ಮತ್ತು ಅವರು ಭವಿಷ್ಯದಲ್ಲಿ ಉತ್ತಮ ನಾಗರಿಕರಾಗಲು ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡಬಹುದು.

ಶಾಲೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವ ವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿ ಅವುಗಳ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಅಳೆಯುವುದು ಒಂದು ಅತ್ಯುತ್ತಮ ವಿಧಾನ.

ಈ ರೀತಿಯ ಅಧ್ಯಯನದ ಮೂಲಕ ನಾವು ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನ ಮಾಹಿತಿಯನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಬಹುದು:

- **ವಿವಿಧ ವಿಧಾನಗಳ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿತ್ವ:** ಯಾವ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಬೆಳೆಸುತ್ತವೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಗುರುತಿಸಬಹುದು.
- **ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ವಯಸ್ಸಿನ ಗುಂಪುಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ವಿಧಾನಗಳ ಪ್ರಭಾವ:** ವಿವಿಧ ವಯಸ್ಸಿನ ಮಕ್ಕಳ ಮೇಲೆ ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು ಹೇಗೆ ಪರಿಣಾಮ ಬೀರುತ್ತವೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದು.
- **ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ-ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯ ಮಕ್ಕಳ ಮೇಲೆ ವಿಧಾನಗಳ ಪ್ರಭಾವ:** ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ಸಾಮಾಜಿಕ-ಆರ್ಥಿಕ ಹಿನ್ನೆಲೆಯ ಮಕ್ಕಳ ಮೇಲೆ ವಿಭಿನ್ನ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು ಹೇಗೆ ಪರಿಣಾಮ ಬೀರುತ್ತವೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದು.
- **ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ತರಬೇತಿಯ ಪ್ರಾಮುಖ್ಯತೆ:** ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ತರಬೇತಿಯು ಈ ವಿಧಾನಗಳ ಯಶಸ್ಸಿನಲ್ಲಿ ಎಷ್ಟು ಪ್ರಮುಖ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದು.
- **ಶಾಲಾ ಪರಿಸರದ ಪ್ರಭಾವ:** ಶಾಲಾ ಪರಿಸರವು ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಹೇಗೆ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸುತ್ತದೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದು.

ಅಧ್ಯಯನವನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವಾಗ ಗಮನಿಸಬೇಕಾದ ಅಂಶಗಳು:

- **ನಿಯಂತ್ರಿತ ಗುಂಪುಗಳು:** ಒಂದು ಗುಂಪಿಗೆ ಹೊಸ ವಿಧಾನವನ್ನು ಅಳವಡಿಸಿ, ಇನ್ನೊಂದು ಗುಂಪನ್ನು ನಿಯಂತ್ರಿತ ಗುಂಪಾಗಿ ಇಟ್ಟುಕೊಳ್ಳುವುದು.
- **ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿತ್ವವನ್ನು ಅಳೆಯುವ ಮಾನದಂಡಗಳು:** ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಜ್ಞಾನ, ಕೌಶಲ್ಯಗಳು, ಮನೋಭಾವ ಮತ್ತು ವರ್ತನೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅಳೆಯಲು ಸೂಕ್ತವಾದ ಮಾನದಂಡಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಧರಿಸುವುದು.
- **ದೀರ್ಘಕಾಲೀನ ಅಧ್ಯಯನ:** ಒಂದು ಅಥವಾ ಎರಡು ವರ್ಷಗಳ ಕಾಲ ಅಧ್ಯಯನವನ್ನು ನಡೆಸುವುದು.

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ಗುಣಾತ್ಮಕ ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಮಾಣಾತ್ಮಕ ದತ್ತಾಂಶ ಸಂಗ್ರಹ: ಪ್ರಶ್ನಾವಳಿಗಳು, ಸಂದರ್ಶನಗಳು, ಪರೀಕ್ಷೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅವಲೋಕನಗಳ ಮೂಲಕ ದತ್ತಾಂಶವನ್ನು ಸಂಗ್ರಹಿಸುವುದು.

ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರ ತರಬೇತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ಕೆಳಗಿನ ಅಂಶಗಳನ್ನು ಒಳಗೊಳಿಸಬಹುದು:

ವಿಧಾನಗಳ ಕುರಿತಾದ ಸಂಪೂರ್ಣ ಮಾಹಿತಿ: ಪ್ರತಿಯೊಂದು ವಿಧಾನದ ಗುರಿ, ಅನುಕೂಲಗಳು, ಅನಾನುಕೂಲಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಅದನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗೊಳಿಸುವುದು ಎಂಬುದರ ಕುರಿತು ವಿವರವಾದ ಮಾಹಿತಿ ನೀಡಬೇಕು.

- **ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕ ತರಬೇತಿ:** ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ತಾವೇ ಈ ವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಅನುಭವಿಸುವಂತೆ ಮಾಡಲು ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕ ತರಬೇತಿಯನ್ನು ನೀಡಬೇಕು.
- **ಪಾಠ ರಚಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಸಹಾಯ:** ವಿವಿಧ ವಿಷಯಗಳಿಗೆ ಹೊಂದಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವಂತಹ ಪಾಠಗಳನ್ನು ರಚಿಸುವಲ್ಲಿ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರಿಗೆ ಸಹಾಯ ಮಾಡಬೇಕು.
- **ಮೌಲ್ಯಮಾಪನ:** ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಪ್ರಗತಿಯನ್ನು ಅಳೆಯಲು ಯಾವ ರೀತಿಯ ಮೌಲ್ಯಮಾಪನಗಳನ್ನು ಬಳಸಬಹುದು ಎಂಬುದರ ಕುರಿತು ಮಾಹಿತಿ ನೀಡಬೇಕು.
- **ಸಹಕಾರ:** ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ಪರಸ್ಪರ ಸಹಕರಿಸಿ ಕೆಲಸ ಮಾಡುವಂತೆ ಪ್ರೋತ್ಸಾಹಿಸಬೇಕು.
- **ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳು:** ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರಿಗೆ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿರುವ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸಂಪನ್ಮೂಲಗಳನ್ನು ಒದಗಿಸಬೇಕು.
- **ಪ್ರತಿಕ್ರಿಯೆ:** ತರಬೇತಿಯ ನಂತರ ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರನ್ನು ಪ್ರಶ್ನಿಸಿ ಅವರ ಅನುಭವವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿದುಕೊಳ್ಳಬಹುದು.
- **ಪಾಠಗಳ ಅವಲೋಕನ:** ಶಿಕ್ಷಕರು ತರಗತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಈ ವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಹೇಗೆ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನಗೊಳಿಸುತ್ತಾರೆ ಎಂಬುದನ್ನು ಅವಲೋಕಿಸಬಹುದು.
- **ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಪ್ರಗತಿ:** ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳ ಜ್ಞಾನ, ಕೌಶಲ್ಯಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಮನೋಭಾವಗಳಲ್ಲಿನ ಬದಲಾವಣೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅಳೆಯಬಹುದು.

ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ:

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವ ಆಧುನಿಕ ವಿಧಾನಗಳ ಕುರಿತು ವಿವರಿಸಿದ ಇಡೀ ವಿವರಣೆ ನಮಗೆ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣದ ಪ್ರಗತಿಯ ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ಹಾಗೂ ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸಲು ಅವಶ್ಯಕವಾದ ನೂತನ ವಿಧಾನಗಳ ಬಳಕೆಯ ಅಗತ್ಯವನ್ನು ಸ್ಪಷ್ಟವಾಗಿ ತೋರಿಸುತ್ತದೆ. ೨೦ನೇ ಶತಮಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣವು ಪಠ್ಯಪುಸ್ತಕಗಳ ಶ್ರೇಣಿಯಿಂದ ಹೊರಗೊಮ್ಮಲು, ಶ್ರೇಣಿಯಲ್ಲಿಯೇ ನಿಜವಾದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಪರಿಹರಿಸಲು, ತಾರ್ಕಿಕ ಚಿಂತನಶೀಲತೆಯನ್ನು ಉತ್ತೇಜಿಸಲು ಮತ್ತು ಸಂಶೋಧನಾ ಕಾರ್ಯಕ್ರಮಗಳನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸಲು ಅನೇಕ ಹೊಸ ವಿಧಾನಗಳನ್ನು ಸೇರಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ.

ಈ ರೀತಿಯ ಹೊಸ ವಿಧಾನಗಳಲ್ಲಿಯೇ, ವಿಚಾರಣಾ ಆಧಾರಿತ ಕಲಿಕೆ, ಯೋಜನಾ ಆಧಾರಿತ ಕಲಿಕೆ, ಸಹಯೋಗಿ ಕಲಿಕೆ,

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ಮತ್ತು ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನದ ಸಮಾಗಮವು ಪ್ರಮುಖವಾಗಿ ಪಾತ್ರ ವಹಿಸುತ್ತವೆ. ಈ ವಿಧಾನಗಳು, ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಿಗೆ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಪ್ರಕ್ರಿಯೆಗಳನ್ನು ಅರ್ಥಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ, ತಾರ್ಕಿಕ ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಬಳಸುವ ಮತ್ತು ನಿಜವಾದ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಗೆ ಪರಿಹಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಹುಡುಕುವ ಶಕ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ನೀಡುತ್ತವೆ. ಅಂತಿಮವಾಗಿ, ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮನೋಭಾವವನ್ನು ಬೆಳೆಸುವ ಈ ನೂತನ ವಿಧಾನಗಳ ಸಮರ್ಥ ಅನುಷ್ಠಾನವು, ವಿದ್ಯಾರ್ಥಿಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಸೃಜನಶೀಲತೆ, ತಾರ್ಕಿಕ ಚಿಂತನಶೀಲತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಉತ್ತಮ ನಿರ್ಧಾರ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವನ್ನು ನಿರ್ಮಿಸುವ ಮೂಲಕ, ಅವರ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಅರಿವನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಜೀವನ ಕೌಶಲ್ಯವನ್ನು ಉಲ್ಲೇಖಿತ ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ವೃದ್ಧಿಸುತ್ತದೆ.

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Paper 15

**THE JOB SATISFACTION AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS OF
BELTHANGADY TALUK**

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ABSTRACT

Each and every human being is a valuable asset and a priceless national resource that should be treasured, nurtured, and developed with tenderness, care, and creativity. Humans are objective creatures who constantly evaluate their circumstances. They won't be satisfied until they achieve their goals. It's possible to argue that achieving one's objectives and aspirations is the ultimate aspiration of each person and that doing so results in a fulfilled existence. For teachers to lead successful lives, job satisfaction is essential. The purpose of this study is to examine the function of job satisfaction in elementary education. The study also aimed to investigate whether primary school teachers' levels of job satisfaction varied depending on their school management, school locality, and marital status. A total of 200 respondents were gathered, with 100 coming from rural areas and 100 from urban areas. A descriptive approach survey research design was employed. The standardized JOB SATISFACTION SCALE (JSS), developed in (2000) by Dr. HASEEN TAJ was the tool used for obtaining data. Data was examined using t-test and descriptive statistics. According to research, there are significant differences in their Locality and School Management.

Key words: - Job Satisfaction, School Locality, School Management.

INTRODUCTION:

Life circumstances are the primary factor in determining human welfare. It has greater consideration than the world around us. Humans strive their entire lives to reach the ultimate aim of satisfaction, which is a condition of feeling and pleasure in a living being. Inner and externally conflict results from unfulfilled desires. It causes a sense of emptiness, dissatisfaction and hopelessness in life. In the busy society we live in today, satisfaction is essential. A person who is dissatisfied cannot have a happy and prosperous life. It is believed that someone with high life satisfaction will also have happier or better life adjustment, and vice versa.

For teachers, job happiness is essential and important since it boosts productivity and encourages the

growth and development of every individual involved in an institution. Teachers who are dissatisfied with their jobs will not be in a position to enhance their performance at work or contribute to the teaching and learning process in order to raise the standard of education. In order to be devoted and committed to carrying out their tasks and responsibilities, teachers must therefore be happy in their roles.

LITERATURE REVIEW

JOB SATISFACTION

The term "satisfaction" is frequently used to characterize the state in which a person finds themselves following a specific event. It characterizes the emotional condition that arises from interacting with individuals or things. Other emotive terms like fulfilment, happiness, gratification, compensation, joy, excitement, and self-actualization have also been used directly in place of it. The goal of job design is to improve performance and job satisfaction; techniques include job re-engineering, job enrichment, and job enlargement. Employee involvement, empowerment, autonomous work positions, and management style and culture are other factors that impact employee happiness. Thus, a job-satisfying attitude is one that considers feelings, attitudes, and behaviours related to one's work. Simply said, job satisfaction is a person's emotional response to their work. It is a person's perspective on their work. The research conducted in the fields of business, industry, education, etc., can be used to understand the various aspects of job satisfaction.

Neog & Barua (2014) found few factors which are accountable for job satisfaction, the relationship between job satisfaction and fair compensation, working environment and job satisfaction, job security and job satisfaction. They observed that salary was the major important factor that influences the job satisfaction and showed that the level of satisfaction is average among employees.

John (2010), Mehta (2012), and Zilli (2012) conducted a survey regarding the teacher's job satisfaction to know whether the teacher's perception is affected by the type of organization. The result observed that there is a significant difference in the level of satisfaction of government and private school teachers.

THE RATIONALE OF THE STUDY:

The present study aims to compare the job satisfaction among teacher based on their locality of school and school management and their. The role of the teachers in our society is very important. The

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quality of education is related to the quality of the teachers. Teachers are the architect of the students' future. A teacher who is satisfied with their job can perform their work effectively and efficiently. If the teachers work under stress, they cannot be satisfied with their job and it will create a negative impact towards the job. So, it is necessary to identify the factors that influence the teachers to derive satisfaction from their work. Teachers can do wonders for transforming the student raw materials into excellent finished goods that is as complete human beings and responsible citizens. Additional energy can be developed when the teachers are satisfied with their job.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY:

- To study the status of Job Satisfaction among Primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk.
- To find out whether there is a significant difference in the Job Satisfaction among primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk based on their locality.
- To find out whether there is a significant difference in the Job Satisfaction among primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk based on their School Management.

HYPOTHESIS OF STUDY:

H₁. There is a significant difference in the mean scores of job satisfaction of Urban and Rural Teachers of Belthangady taluk.

H₂. There is a significant difference in the mean scores of job satisfaction of Government and Private Teachers of Belthangady taluk.

METHODOLOGY OF STUDY

TOOL USED IN THE STUDY

The tool employed to gather data was the standardized tool JOB SATISFACTION SCALE (JSS) developed by Dr. Haseen Taj established in 2000. The scale consists of 40 items based on using 4 point Likert scale. Investigator modified the JSS to better suit for study's specific objectives and population. Investigator removed (question number) that were not relevant to study context and added new question (new number) to capture additional aspect of job satisfaction.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The present study is a descriptive research. The main aim of this study the level of job satisfaction among primary schools teachers based on their locality of school and school management. Standardized tool has been used to collect the primary data. The questionnaire was designed on 4 point rating scale ranging from

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strongly disagree to strongly agree. The questionnaire consisted of two parts. First part was related to the demographic profile of respondents and second part contained study of factors associated with job satisfaction.

SAMPLE DESIGN

In this study, the sampling unit was the primary school teachers of 44 schools of Belthangady Taluk, Dakshina kannada District, Karnataka state. The sample size was selected to represent the whole population and also to give the real picture. The total size of the sample was 200. The samples were collected using Random sampling technique.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The respondents, who were the primary school teachers, were required to volunteer facts associated with their locality of school and school management. This was needed to check whether these had any effect on job satisfaction.

OBJECTIVE ONE

The **first objective** was to study the status of Job Satisfaction among primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk. In order to analyze this objective, descriptive statistics namely Mean, Median, SD, Skewness and graphical representation namely smoothed frequency polygon were used. The results are given in the table 1.

Table 1: The Smoothed Frequency Distribution of Scores on Job Satisfaction among primary school teachers Belthangady Taluk.

Class Interval	Frequency	Mid-Point	Smoothed Frequency
50-59	1	54.5	0.333
60-69	0	64.5	0.333
70-79	0	74.5	0.666
80-89	2	84.5	6.333
90-99	13	94.5	21
100-109	48	104.5	25.666
110-119	16	114.5	27.666
120-129	19	124.5	11.666
130-139	0	134.5	6.666
140-149	1	144.5	0.333

Figure 1: Smoothed Frequency Polygon representing the score on Job Satisfaction among primary school teachers Belthangady Taluk.

Further the Mean, Median, SD and Skewness were calculated for the distribution of scores on Job Satisfaction among school teachers Belthangady Taluk. The result is given below.

Table 2: Number (N), Mean (M), Median (Mdn), Standard Deviation (SD) and Skewness (SK) of the distribution of scores on Job Satisfaction among school teachers Belthangady Taluk.

Variable	N	Maximum Score	M	Mdn	SD	Sk
Job Satisfaction	200	140	112.4	111	0.74	0.15

Interpretation

From the table 2 it is observed that the Mean and Median values are closed to each other. The Pearson’s skewness was 0.15. This negligible degree of positive skewness shows that the distribution closely approaching the normal distribution among sample.

OBJECTIVE TWO

The **Second objective** was to study the difference, if any, in the Job Satisfaction among primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk based on their School locality. A hypothesis was formulated for this objective and data has been interpreted using descriptive and inferential statistics. t Test was employed to test the hypothesis with the level of significance 0.05. The result has been showed in table 3 and 4

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Table 3: Cumulative percentage Frequency Distribution of Scores on Job Satisfaction among Primary school teachers Belthangady Taluk based on their school locality.

Cl	RURAL SCHOOL			URBANSCHOOL		
	F	CF	%CF	F	CF	%CF
50-59	0	0	0	1	1	0.87
60-69	0	0	0	0	1	0.87
70-79	0	0	0	0	1	0.87
80-89	0	0	0	2	3	2.61
90-99	2	2	1.98	13	16	13.04
100-109	19	21	20.79	48	64	49.57
110-119	47	68	67.33	16	80	79.13
120-129	23	91	90.10	19	99	92.17
130-139	10	101	100.00	0	99	100.00
140-149	0	101	100.00	1	100	100.00
	N=101			N=100		

Figure 2: Ogive Representing the Distribution of Scores on Job Satisfaction among Primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk based on their School locality.

Interpretation

From the figure 2, it is clear that there is significant difference in the Job Satisfaction among Primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk based on their school locality. It is shown by the two Ogives at different levels.

Table 4: t value of scores on Job Satisfaction among Primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk based on their school locality.

Locality	N	M	SD	tvalue	ttablevalue	Result
Rural	101	115.96	8.92	5.31	1.97	Significant at 0.05 level
Urban	100	108.17	11.92			

To study this objective, the investigator had formulated a research hypothesis:

HYPOTHESIS ONE

HA: There is a significant difference in the mean scores of job satisfaction of Rural school teachers and Urban school Teachers of Belthangady taluk.

To test this objective, the investigator changed the research hypothesis to Null Hypothesis.

HO: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of job satisfaction of Government school teachers and Private school teachers of Belthangady taluk. t test was employed to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance at 199 Degree of freedom. The result had been given in table 4.8.

From the table 4, it is revealed that the t value for Rural school teachers and Urban School Teachers of Belthangady taluk are significant at 0.05 level, but it is also observed that Mean scores of Rural are low than that of urban teacher. Hence it is concluded that the Job satisfaction of Rural school teacher and Urban teachers differ.

Thus the null hypothesis is rejected.

CONCLUSION

Urban school Teachers are having high job satisfaction in comparison with Rural school Teachers significantly differ in their Job Satisfaction.

OBJECTIVE THREE

The **third objective** was to study the difference, if any, in the Job Satisfaction among primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk based on their School Management. A hypothesis was formulated for this objective and data has been interpreted using descriptive and inferential statistics. t Test was employed to test the hypothesis with the level of significance 0.05. The result has been showed in

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table 5 and 6.

Table 5: Cumulative percentage Frequency Distribution of Scores on Job Satisfaction among Primary school teachers Belthangady Taluk based on their school management.

CI	GOVERNMENT SCHOOL			PRIVATE SCHOOL		
	F	CF	%CF	F	CF	%CF
50-59	0	0	0	1	1	0.87
60-69	0	0	0	0	1	0.87
70-79	0	0	0	0	1	0.87
80-89	0	0	0	2	3	2.61
90-99	2	2	1.98	13	16	13.04
100-109	19	21	20.79	48	64	49.57
110-119	47	68	67.33	16	80	79.13
120-129	23	91	90.10	19	99	92.17
130-139	10	101	100.00	0	99	100.00
140-149	0	101	100.00	1	100	100.00
	N=101			N=100		

Figure 3: Ogive Representing the Distribution of Scores on Job Satisfaction among Primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk based on their School management.

Interpretation

From the figure 3, it is clear that there is significant difference in the Job Satisfaction among Primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk based on their school management. It is shown by the two

Ogives at different levels.

Table 6: t value of scores on Job Satisfaction among Primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk based on their school management.

Locality	N	M	SD	tvalue	ttablevalue	Result
Government	101	115.96	8.92	5.31	1.97	Significant at 0.05level
Private	100	108.17	11.92			

To study this objective, the investigator had formulated a research hypothesis:

HYPOTHESIS TWO

HA: There is a significant difference in the mean scores of job satisfaction of Government school teachers and Private school Teachers of Belthangady taluk.

To test this objective, the investigator changed the research hypothesis to Null Hypothesis.

HO: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of job satisfaction of Government school teachers and Private school teachers of Belthangady taluk.

t test was employed to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance at 199 Degree of freedom.

The result had been given in table 6.

From the table 6, it is revealed that the t value for Government school teachers and Private School Teachers of Belthangady taluk are significant at 0.05 level, but it is also observed that Mean scores of Government are low than that of Private teacher. Hence it is concluded that the Job satisfaction of Government and private teachers differ. **Thus the null hypothesis is rejected.**

CONCLUSION

Government school Teachers are having high job satisfaction then Private school Teachers.

Therefore there is differ in their Job Satisfaction according to their school management.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS:

- The analysis of objective one showed that the scores on job satisfaction among primary school teacher of Belthangady Taluk are normally distributed.

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- The analysis of second objective showed that there is significant difference between job satisfaction of Belthangady Taluk based on their locality of school.
- The analysis of third objective showed that there is significant difference between job satisfaction of Belthangady taluk based on their school management.

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE RESULT:

- Job satisfaction among primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk is normally distributed, which state there is a positive level of job satisfaction among primary school teachers of Belthangady taluk.
- The difference in the job satisfaction with respect to their locality of school among primary school teachers of Belthangady taluk.
- The difference in the job satisfaction with respect to their school management among primary school teachers of Belthangady taluk.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The present study is based on data collected from Primary school teachers of Belthangady Taluk.
- Some of the replies from the respondents may be biased
- The use of questionnaires as the principle method of getting information may have few limitations.

SUGGESTIONS:

- Develop a recognition and reward system to motivate teachers and their contribution.
- Special training should be provide teachers according to their need.
- Sufficient salary should be paid to temporary teachers.
- Transport expenses should be given by institution and Good infrastructure should be provided in Rural schools.

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion has been drawn according to the results discussed in the study. Teachers are the assets of the society. They played an important role to improve the quality of education which is very much dependent on the satisfaction of the job. Only a teacher who is fully satisfied with their job can provide quality education. It is necessary to recognize those socio-psychological factors that

influence the level of job satisfaction. Recognizing the importance of Job Satisfaction of primary school teachers in improving the quality of education, this study was carried out with the objectives to compare the level of job satisfaction of primary school teachers in the influence of locality and management.

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ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಸವಾಲಾಗಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ

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ವೀರಿಕೆ

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಅಥವಾ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯು ಅವಲೋಕನಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ಸಿದ್ಧಾಂತಗಳಿಂದ ದೃಢೀಕರಿಸಿದೆ. ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ವಿಧಾನಗಳ ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆಗೆ ಸಂಬಂಧಿಸಿದೆ ಹಾಗೂ ಗುಣಾತ್ಮಕ ಮತ್ತು ಪರಿಮಾಣಾತ್ಮಕ ಅಂಕಿ ಅಂಶಗಳ ಅನುಭವ ಮತ್ತು ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆ ಆಗಿದೆ. ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯು ಮೂಲ ಅಗತ್ಯವಲ್ಲವೆಂದು ಭಾವಿಸಿದರೆ ಜೀವಿಯ ಉಳಿವಿಗೆ ಭಾಷೆಯು ಮೂಲ ಅಗತ್ಯವಲ್ಲ ಎಂದಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಸಂವಹನ ನೆಡೆಸಲು ಭಾಷೆಯು ಎಷ್ಟು ಮುಖ್ಯವೋ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಕೂಡ ಅಷ್ಟೆ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸಲು ಕಲಿಯಬೇಕಾದ್ದೇನು? ಎಂದು ಕೇಳಿದರೆ ಅದು ಓದು ಬರಹ ಮತ್ತು ಸಂವಹನ ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಬಳಸಲು ಕಲಿಯಬೇಕು ಇದರಿಂದ ಸಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯನ್ನು ಸಾಧಿಸುತ್ತೇವೆ ಎಂದು ಹೇಳುವುದು ತಪ್ಪಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಬದಲಾಗಿ ನಮ್ಮ ಜ್ಞಾನದ ವ್ಯಾಪ್ತಿಯನ್ನು ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳಬೇಕು, ಅಕ್ಷರ ಕಲಿಕೆಯಷ್ಟೆ ವೇಗವಾಗಿ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಕಲಿಕೆಯು ಅಗತ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಇರುವ ಜ್ಞಾನಮಟ್ಟದಲ್ಲಿ ಎಂತಹ ಸನ್ನಿವೇಶಗಳು, ಸವಾಲುಗಳು ಬಂದರೂ ಪರಿಹರಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ತಾಕತ್ತು ನಮಗಿದ್ದರೂ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ವಿಷಯಗಳ ಬಗ್ಗೆ ವಿವೇಚಿಸುವ ಸಾಮರ್ಥ್ಯವನ್ನು ಪಡೆಯಬೇಕಾದದ್ದು ಆದ್ಯ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಕೊರತೆಯಿಂದ ಸಾಮಾಜದಲ್ಲಿ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ನಾನಾ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳು ಉಂಟಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಅದರಲ್ಲೂ ನಮ್ಮ ಗ್ರಾಮೀಣ ಪ್ರದೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಮಟ್ಟ ತೀರಾ ಹಿಂದೆ ಉಳಿದಿದೆ. ಅವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕವಾಗಿ ಜೀವನ ಕೃಷಿ ಮುಂತಾದವುಗಳನ್ನು ನಿರ್ವಹಿಸುತ್ತಿದ್ದು ಇಂತಹ ಸಂದಿಗ್ಧ ಪರಿಸ್ಥಿತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯನ್ನು ಬೇರು ಮಟ್ಟದಿಂದ ಕಲಿಸಿ ನಂತರ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನದ ಕಲಿಕೆ ಪ್ರಾರಂಭಿಸಬೇಕು. ಈ ಮೇಲಿನ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಸಮಸ್ಯೆಗಳಿಂದ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ಅಗತ್ಯವಾಗಿ ಮಾನವನ ಮೂಲಭೂತ ಕಲಿಕೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಒಂದಾಗಿದೆ. ಎಲ್ಲಾ

ಪಾಶ್ಚಿಮಾತ್ಯ ತತ್ವಶಾಸ್ತ್ರಜ್ಞರು, ಚಿಂತಕರು, ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ತಜ್ಞರು ಕಲಿಕೆಯ ಅಗತ್ಯತೆ ಮತ್ತು ಮಹತ್ವವನ್ನು ಹೇಳುತ್ತಾ ಬಂದಿದ್ದಾರೆ ಹಾಗಾಗಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯನ್ನು ಸಾಧ್ಯವಾದಷ್ಟು ಮಟ್ಟಿಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿಸಬೇಕಾದ್ದು ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಶಿಕ್ಷಣ ಸಂಸ್ಥೆಗಳ , ಸಂಶೋಧಕರ ಆದ್ಯ ಕರ್ತವ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ.

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯ ಅರ್ಥ:

ಮನುಷ್ಯ ತನ್ನ ಹುಟ್ಟಿನಿಂದ ಹಲವಾರು ರೀತಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಕಲಿಯುತ್ತಾ ಬಂದಿದ್ದಾನೆ ತನ್ನ ದೈನಂದಿನ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಕೈಗೊಳ್ಳಲಿರುವ ಆನೇಕ ಕಾರ್ಯಗಳ ಹಿಂದೆ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ತತ್ವಗಳು ಇರುವುವು . ಅವುಗಳನ್ನು ತಾಂತ್ರಿಕವಲ್ಲದ ಭಾಷೆಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಮನನ ಮಾಡಿಸುವುದರಿಂದ ಕಾರ್ಯದಕ್ಷತೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚುತ್ತದೆ ಮತ್ತು ಕೂತೂಹಲ ಕೆರಳುತ್ತದೆ. ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಕಲಿಯಲು ಮತ್ತು ಅದನ್ನು ಅರ್ಜನೆ ಮಾಡಿಕೊಳ್ಳಲು ನಾವು ತೆಗೆದುಕೊಳ್ಳುವ ವಿಷಯಗಳು ಅತ್ಯಂತ ಮುಖ್ಯವಾಗಿವೆ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಸಾಧಿಸಲು ಈ ಕೆಳಕಂಡ ಅಂಶಗಳ ಮೇಲೆ ಪರಿಣಾಮಕಾರಿಯಾಗಿ ಬೆಳಕನ್ನು ಚೆಲ್ಲಬಹುದು.

- ಪ್ರಯೋಗಗಳು
- ಮಾಧ್ಯಮಗಳ ಬಳಕೆ
- ಚರ್ಚೆಗಳು
- ನೂತನ ತಂತ್ರಜ್ಞಾನ ಮತ್ತು ಉಪಕರಣಗಳ ಬಳಕೆ ಈ ಮೇಲಿನ ಎಲ್ಲಾ ಆಯಾಮಗಳಿಂದ ಬರುವ ಮುಖ್ಯ ಫಲಿತಾಂಶವೆಂದರೆ,
- ಸರಿಯಾದ ಚಿಂತನೆ
- ಕೂತೂಹಲ ತಣಿಸುವಿಕೆ
- ಚಿಂತನಾ ಹವ್ಯಾಸಗಳು
- ನಿತ್ಯ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಕಾರ್ಯದಕ್ಷತೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಳ
- ಉತ್ತಮ ಸಂಭಾಷಣ ಕೌಶಲ

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಚಿಂತನೆಗೆ ಇರುವ ಅಡೆತಡೆಗಳು;

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಚಿಂತನೆ ಎಂದರೆ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರದಲ್ಲಿ ಬಳಕೆಯಾಗುವ ಕ್ಷೇತ್ರಕಷ್ಟ ಉಪಯುಕ್ತವಾದ ಚಿಂತನೆ ಎಂಬ ನಂಬಿಕೆ

ಇದೆ.ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಜ್ಞಾನವು ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಮಟ್ಟವನ್ನು ಲೆಕ್ಕಿಸದೆ ಆನೇಕ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮತ್ತು ತಾಂತ್ರಿಕ ಬೆಳವಣಿಗೆಗಳು ನಿಗೂಡವಾಗಿಯೇ ಉಳಿದಿದೆ. ಅಂತಹ ನಿಗೂಡತೆಯು ಮೂಲತಃ ವಿಜ್ಞಾನದ ವಿಶಿಷ್ಟ ಶಕ್ತಿಗಳಿಂದ ಮತ್ತು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಜ್ಞಾನದಿಂದ ಹುಟ್ಟಿಕೊಂಡಿದೆ. ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಮತ್ತು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕತೆಗಳು ಪ್ರಜಾಪ್ರಭುತ್ವದ ನಿಯಂತ್ರಣಕ್ಕೆ ಒಳಪಟ್ಟಿರುವುದು ಆಶ್ಚರ್ಯಕರ ಸಂಗತಿಯಾಗಿದೆ.

ಕಾರಣಗಳು:

- ರಾಷ್ಟ್ರೀಯ ಶಕ್ತಿಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಭಾವ.
- ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಕೆಲಸದ ಒತ್ತಡ.
- ಪೂರ್ವಾಗ್ರಹ ಪೀಡನೆ.
- ಪರಿಣಿತರ ಜ್ಞಾನದಲ್ಲಿ ವಸ್ತುನಿಷ್ಠತೆ ಇಲ್ಲದಿರುವುದು.
- ಸಂವಾದಾತ್ಮಕ ವಿಧಾನದ ಕೊರತೆ
- ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ತಿಳುವಳಿಕೆ ಇಲ್ಲದಿರುವುದು
- ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಂಶೋಧನೆಗಳು

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆಯನ್ನು ಮೂಡಿಸಲು ಶೈಕ್ಷಣಿಕ ಅವಕಾಶಗಳು;

ವಿಜ್ಞಾನದ ಬಗೆಗಿನ ವರ್ತನೆಗಳು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಮೇಲೆ ಗಮನಾರ್ಹ ಪರಿಣಾಮ ಬೀರುತ್ತದೆ. ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಸಾಕ್ಷರತೆ ಅರಿವಿನ ಕಲಿಕೆಯಾದರೆ ವರ್ತನೆಗಳು ಪರಿಣಾಮಾಕಾರಿ ಕಲಿಕೆಯಾಗುತ್ತದೆ. ಇಂದಿನ ಯುವ ಸಮೂಹ ಗುರಿ ಮತ್ತು ಗುರು ಎರಡು ಇಲ್ಲದಂತಾಗಿದೆ.ಒಂದು ಕಡೆ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕವಾಗಿ ಮುಂದುವರಿದ ನಾವು ಚಂದ್ರನ ಅಂಗಳಕ್ಕೆ ಕಾಲಿಡುತ್ತಿದ್ದೆವೆ, ಮತ್ತೊಂದುಕಡೆ ಮೌಢ್ಯತೆ , ಕಂದಾಚಾರ ನಮ್ಮನ್ನು ಪಾತಾಳಕ್ಕೆ ಕರೆದೊಯ್ಯುತ್ತಿದೆ . ಪ್ರಸ್ತುತ ದಿನಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವಿದ್ಯಾವಂತರೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚು ಮೌಢ್ಯಕ್ಕೆ ಬಲಿಯಾಗುತ್ತಿರುವುದು ದುರಂತದ ಸಂಗತಿ . ಸಮಾಜಕ್ಕೆ ಪ್ರಜ್ಞಾವಂತರ ಅಗತ್ಯವಿದ್ದು ಪ್ರಜ್ಞಾ ವಂತಿಕೆಯನ್ನು ಸೃಷ್ಟಿಸಬೇಕಿದೆ. ಅದಕ್ಕಾಗಿ ಯುವಜನರು ತಮ್ಮ ವರ್ತನೆ ಮತ್ತು ಜ್ಞಾನವನ್ನು ಅಭಿವೃದ್ಧಿ ಪಡಿಸಿಕೊಂಡರೆ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕವಾಗಿ ಪ್ರಗತಿ ಸಾಧಿಸಬಹುದು.

- ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಪ್ರಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರಾತಕ್ಷಿಕೆ ಮಾಡುವುದು
- ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಮತ್ತು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಲೀಖನಗಳನ್ನು ಬರೆಸುವುದು

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- ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಶಾಲಾ ತರಗತಿ ಸನ್ನಿವೇಶದಲ್ಲಿ ಪ್ರಯೋಗಗಳನ್ನು ಮಾಡುವುದು.
- ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕ ಬೋಧನೆಗೆ ಹೆಚ್ಚಿನ ಮಹತ್ವ ನೀಡುವುದು
- ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ದೃಷ್ಟಿಕೋನ ಬೆಳೆಸುವುದು
- ಪಠ್ಯಪುಸ್ತಕಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ವಿಚಾರಗಳನ್ನು ಸೇರ್ಪಡೆ ಮಾಡುವುದು
- ವಿಜ್ಞಾನ ಮತ್ತು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಪರಿಷತ್ ಸ್ಥಾಪಿಸುವುದು
- ಚರ್ಚಾ ಸ್ಪರ್ಧೆ ಏರ್ಪಡಿಸುವುದು.
- ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಮಹತ್ವ ಹೊಂದಿರುವ ಸ್ಥಳಗಳ ಬೇಟೆ.
- ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ನಾಟಕಗಳನ್ನು ಪ್ರದರ್ಶಿಸುವುದು.

ಉಪಸಂಹಾರ:

ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕತೆ ಎನ್ನುವುದು ನಿಂತ ನೀರಾಗದೆ ಇದನ್ನು ನಮ್ಮ ನಿತ್ಯ ಜೀವನದಲ್ಲಿ ಅಳವಡಿಸಿಕೊಳ್ಳ ಬೇಕಾಗಿದೆ. ಬಾಲ್ಯದ ದಿನದಿಂದಲೂ ತಮ್ಮ ತಮ್ಮ ಕುಟುಂಬಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕತೆಯ ಅವಶ್ಯಕತೆ , ಅನಿವಾರ್ಯವನ್ನು ತಿಳಿಸಬೇಕಾದದ್ದು ಅವಶ್ಯವಾಗಿದೆ. ಹಾಗೂ ಶಾಲಾ ಕಾಲೇಜುಗಳಲ್ಲಿ ಇದನ್ನು ಬೋಧಿಸಿ ಮಕ್ಕಳಿಗೆ ಪ್ರಾಯೋಗಿಕ ಚಿಂತನೆಗಳನ್ನು ಮತ್ತು ಅಮೂರ್ತ ಜ್ಞಾನ ಒದಗಿಸುವ ಚಟುವಟಿಕೆಗಳು ಮತ್ತು ವೈಜ್ಞಾನಿಕ ಅನ್ವೇಷಣೆಯಲ್ಲಿ ತೊಡಗುವಂತೆ ಪ್ರೇರಿಸಬಹುದಾಗಿದೆ.

ಆಧಾರಿತ ಗ್ರಂಥಗಳು:

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Paper 17

EFFECTIVENESS OF OUTDOOR TEACHING ACTIVITIES ON SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS – BASIC SCIENCE PROCESS SKILLS IN SCIENCE – PILOT STUDY

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigated the effect of outdoor teaching activities on secondary school student’s acquisition of science process skills in science. Two research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted single group Pre-test Post-test quasi experimental design. The study was conducted in Mangalore North cluster of Dakshina Kannada district Karnataka State and has a target population of 9000 students from government secondary school. A total of 44 students were sampled from the intact classes from one school for the study. A standardized Basic Science Process Skill constructed by Michael J. Padilla, Linda Cronin and Meghan Twist was used for data collection. Data collected were analysed using Mean, Standard deviation and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). Results revealed a significant difference in Science process skills acquisition between students score in basic science process skill test between students taught using outdoor teaching activities and lecture method. Significant difference existed in the science process skills acquisition between male and female science students taught using outdoor activities to enhance student’s acquisition of science process skills irrespective of gender.

Keywords: Outdoor activities, Science Process skills, lecture method, Gender.

1. INTRODUCTION:

It is a fact that school education is the first exposure of the child to the outside world and prepares him/her to stand alone away from parental protection and to be a good citizens and act as a basic for further education. Though we are living in the twenty first century, era of science and technologies, science education is very important in the school stage and it is necessary for several reasons.

*firstly, the rapid growth of science and technology is influencing almost all walks of life.

*Secondly significant portions of the student terminate their studies after school education.

*Thirdly, the need for relating science with the life of community becomes quite obvious.

If science is taught in isolation, as a body of facts and principles alone, it can hardly meet the above objectives. It is therefore, all the more necessary to make deliberate efforts to dovetail science education

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with life. Because science is a powerful means of intending man’s predictive power upon the universe, and allows data gathering and theorizing to come together. Science prepares pupils to think and sharpen their intellect making them more careful and systematic in reasoning. It provides unique training in truth, inculcates a spirit of inquiry, develops the capacity to know the unknown and gives strength to face failures. The most distinguishing characteristics of science is its method. It is an activity that takes place in the minds of men, it is the result of certain intellectual processes that made discovery possible. The processes of science are the means by which one can examine the unknown, explore and investigate the natural world. But unfortunately these science activities are considered as only the activities of scientist. Learning the processes of science or to learn “how to do science would mean acquiring the skills essential to learning and understanding science information. These knowledge of acquiring the skills essential to learning and understanding science information. These knowledge of acquiring skills are called cognitive skills or process skills.

It is the aim of science education to make the learner master of these process skills. That it means science education should emphasis both content and process goals. To ensure this it is necessary to create healthy active teaching learning environment in the classroom. To satisfy this need many new innovations are taking place from time to time with the main intention to improve method of teaching, instructional strategy and to keep learners alert in the classroom.

NEP 2020 also in its promotions pointed out to promote experiential learning, critical thinking and reduced course content in the school curriculum.

According to Piaget child’s view of reality is quite different from that of the adult. Before a child became an adult, his mental structure need to go through many stages of development, which includes knowing, reasoning, memorizing, imagining, language acquisition and thinking. Hence cognitive development is not mere accumulation of knowledge and skills but a process of restructuring resulting in qualitatively new organisations. This ability develops slowly, probably more than maturational process in interaction with the environment than through learning alone.

According to Piaget the cognitive developmental stage between the age group of 11-15 years is “formal operational period”, consists of the following characteristics.

During this period individual differences are greater than other periods. The young acquire the capacity to think and to reason beyond their capacity and their own belief system. They think about thinking. They enter into the world of ideas, the road has gone from a world of objects through a world of many perspectives. The adolescent is able to apply logical thought to all classes of problems, systems of mental operations has reached a high degree of equilibrium. The adolescents thought is flexible and effective. He can efficiently work with the complex problems of reasoning. He can efficiently imagine many

possibilities of solving problems of reasoning. He can efficiently imagine many possibilities of solving a problem. He draws proper logical conclusions from his observations. In the present study the investigator has selected Outdoor Learning Strategy to teach Science as a method of instruction as it is the need of hour.

Outdoor Learning is active learning in the outdoors. In Outdoor Learning participants learn through what they do, through what they encounter and through what they discover. Participants learn about the outdoors, themselves and each other, while also learning outdoor skills. Outdoor Learning can provide a dramatic contrast to the indoor classroom. Direct experience outdoors is more motivating and has more impact and credibility. Through skilled teaching, interpretation or facilitation, outdoor experiences readily become a stimulating source of fascination, personal growth and breakthroughs in learning.

Outdoor education calls for collaboration and team building tasks. Children learn to communicate with each other, problem solve and build healthy relationships. It gives them the space to explore, discover and think freely, thus reduce barriers to communication. Not only does Outdoor Learning happen in the natural environments where participants can see, hear, touch and smell the real thing, it also happens in an arena where actions have real results and consequences. Outdoor Learning can help to bring many school subjects alive while also providing experiential opportunities for fulfilling the National Curriculum aim “to enable pupils to respond positively to opportunities, challenges and responsibilities, to manage risk and to cope with change and adversity.” Source: DfES & QCA, The National Curriculum, ‘Aims for the School Curriculum’ 1999. Outdoor Learning broadens horizons and stimulates new interests.

The outdoor classroom provide a meaningful way to engage learner in practical science giving them experience of collecting and analysing data and making predictions in the real world, beyond the limitation of the classroom. Outdoor learning is active learning in the outdoor. In outdoor learning participants learn through what they do, through what they encounter and through what they discover. Participants learn about the outdoors, themselves and each other while also learning outdoor skills. In outdoor education programme students participate in a variety of adventurous challenges and outdoor activities such as hiking, climbing and games.

Learning outside the classroom supports the development of healthy and active lifestyles by offering children opportunities for physical activity, freedom and movement and promoting a sense of well-being. Learning outside the classroom supports gives children contact with the natural world and offers them experiences that are unique to outdoors, such as direct contact with the weather and the season. Playing and learning outside also helps children to understand and respect nature, the interdependence of human, plants and animals and their lifecycles. Outdoor teaching supports children problem solving skills and nurture their creativity and also provides rich opportunity for developing imagination, inventiveness and

resourcefulness.

Children need an outdoor environment to explore, experiment, discover be active and healthy and to develop their physical capabilities. The outdoor environment offers space and therefore is particularly important to those children those who learn best through active movement. Learning that flows seamlessly between indoors and outdoors makes the most efficient use of resources and builds in interest and enthusiasm. Hence in this study the attempt is made to develop a practical strategy that could lead her classes out of the way of the present traditionally dominant teaching learning process. For this the researcher first consulted some research literature which can help to understand the science teaching could cross the four walled science classes and enhance the development of Science Process Skill among the learner.

2.0 LITERATURE SURVEY

Sozibilir (2002): Based on the golden rule of educational practice, which states that teaching should be done according what students already know. **Faria, D.B.C. I (2013)** found that outdoor activity is extremely important to promote meaningful science learning in children.

Ayotte, J.P. Beaudet P, J.P.A. (2020) found that there is a positive correlation between students' preparation and their perception of learning during outdoor science lessons. Also they construct through a process of interaction between outside stimulus and conceptions that already exist in the learners head.

Ulrich Dettwiler (2015) argues that outdoor educational settings, pupils show significantly higher learning motivational behaviour. **K.Teaney, M.R. (2013)** suggested that outdoor non-formal learning has effectiveness in learning. **Francis, T. (2021)** research found that it was possible to develop student's connection to nature by having them discover the environment around the school through science teaching.

Jose, M. Rios (2014) research literature indicates that outdoor learning experiences develop positive environmental attitudes and can positively affect science achievement. **M, Imaduddin. R.F.R. (2020)** found that outdoor learning enables effective learning. **Indravathi, S.W. (2017)** found that outdoor learning can be used as an alternative to learning. so it is quite effective in developing science process skills and problem solving abilities. **Dina, M.(2020)** found that outdoor learning engages students in activities and learning. Outdoor education has been found more beneficial to those students who find classroom learning more challenging. **Clement, M.W.(2013)** found that, the teachers in their study reported "that when engaged in child-initiated activity in the outdoor environment, over half of the children who in the classroom were perceived to be 'underachieving' appeared to behave differently" (p. 221). Their work aims to support the notion that the more natural outdoor spaces in which child-initiated activities take place both directly and indirectly diminish the perception of underachievement. As a result of outdoor

science activities using an interdisciplinary approach, teachers may find their disciplinary knowledge and skills improved, with the result that they are more able to answer research questions in real environments. Moreover, through theoretical and methodological interdisciplinary, teachers may foster the creation of new conceptual categories and methodological tools, using concepts or procedures from other disciplines in an auxiliary relationship. **Klein,(2017)** found that from outdoor teaching perspective, interdisciplinary outdoor science activities have the potential to organise scientific topics and ideas and answer questions across different disciplines.**DeZure, (2017)** proved that outdoor science teaching activities provide an opportunity to develop problem-solving abilities, generally considered as an instance of higher order thinking within science courses. **Gnerrero, G.R. (2020)** found that interdisciplinary outdoor science activities carried out appear to generate common work objective, addressing conceptual, procedural and attitudinal aspect across science subject.**Eschah, (2006)** Proved that the influences that experiences outside school have on pupils’ knowledge and understandings, beliefs, attitudes, and motivation to learn cannot be ignored. **Reiss, B.(2006)** found that Science is indeed generally hard to learn. Yet, when pupils visit or taught in places that explain science in often new and exciting ways, they frequently seem to be more enthused. There is, we believe, something about these contexts and places that brings about a change in increasing the desire in people to find out and understand more. There is also possible broader and deeper learning avenues that might just not arise during conventional indoor teaching. Student engagement is crucial for any learning, children were interested involved and enthusiastic during outdoor activities and also children’s obvious happiness and enjoyment may be considered indicative of their emotional engagement in the outdoor tasks.

Sugra, S.B. (2018) Rei, M.E.F. (2017) concluded that the activities of outdoor learning which are part of study field curricular area of environmental studies considers the local environment as a lived space and it should be privileged object of a systematic and methodical first learning of the child since , at these ages the thinking is directed towards concrete learning . It is also considered that it will contribute to the construction of scripts and didactic sequences of learning where the student centred active learning is valued. **Rickinson, et. al,(2004)** of National Foundation for Educational Research and King’s College London in England published a major influential review of outdoor learning. This research report “critically examined 150 pieces of research on outdoor learning published in English between 1993 and 2003” (p. 5). Their corpus covered three outdoor learning categories:

- (1) Fieldwork and outdoor visits,
- (2) Outdoor adventure education,
- (3) School grounds/community projects.

Without focusing on a particular subject matter such as science education, they reported that school grounds/community projects “have the capacity to link with most curriculum areas,” that they might “include greater confidence, renewed pride in community, stronger motivation toward learning, and greater sense of belonging and responsibility”. And they might also “develop more positive relationships with each other [students], with their teachers and with the wider community” (p. 6). Further, due to its close proximity and ease of access, one could argue that school grounds have great, yet underutilized, potential to help science teachers to achieve meaningful contextualization of learning. Undeniably, many other very rich contexts such as museums and field trips also allow interesting real-life/school content anchoring. **Shubhngi Bhedi and Sugra Chunawala (2018)** found that Student engagement is crucial for any learning, children were interested, involved and enthusiastic during outdoor activities and also children’s obvious happiness and enjoyment may be considered indicative of their emotional engagement in the outdoor tasks.

The NEP (2020): document of India in its Part 4 section while explaining the methods of teaching, has given importance to activity based outdoor teaching. This approach is essential to develop creativity, exploratory learning, and arousing interest among learners and to achieve all round development of the learner. **Indumathi I.and Wahyumi S (2017)** found that outdoor learning can be used as an alternative to learning, so it is quite effective in developing Science Process Skills and Problem Solving abilities.

Maulina, Dina (2020) found that implementation of outdoor learning based science process skill in science teaching found that outdoor learning engages students in activities and learning.

3.0 OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

1. To prepare Outdoor Learning Instructional Material in Science for the improvement of Basic Science Process skills of the Pupils of Standard Eight of the Government High School, Mangalore Taluk.
2. To find the effectiveness of Outdoor Learning Instructional Material on the Basic Science Process Skills of the Pupils of Standard Eight of the Government High School, Mangalore Taluk.
3. To find out whether there exist any difference between the means of the scores of Boys and Girls on
 - Basic Process Skill of Observation
 - Basic Process Skill of Communication
 - Basic Process Skill of Classification
 - Basic Process Skill of Measurement
 - Basic Process Skill of Prediction
 - Basic Process Skill of Inference
 - The total score on “The test on Basic Science Process Skill” Standard Eight of the Government High School, Mangalore Taluk.

4.0 HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H1: There is a significant difference between the means of the scores of the Pre-Test and Post-Test on

- Basic Process Skill of Observation
- Basic Process Skill of Communication
- Basic Process Skill of Classification
- Basic Process Skill of Measurement
- Basic Process Skill of Prediction
- Basic Process Skill of Inference
- the total score on “The test on Basic Science Process Skill” among the Pupils of Standard Eight of the Government High School, Mangalore Taluk.

H2: There is a significant difference between the means of the scores of the Pre-Test and Post-Test on

- Basic Process Skill of Observation
- Basic Process Skill of Communication
- Basic Process Skill of Classification
- Basic Process Skill of Measurement
- Basic Process Skill of Prediction
- Basic Process Skill of Inference
- the total score on “The test on Basic Science Process Skill” among the Boys and Girls of Standard Eight of the Government High School, Mangalore Taluk.

5.0 METHODOLOGY

The present study consist of the experimental research design.

The researcher here used a Pre-Test, Post-Test single group quasi experimental design in the study.

The following table shows the diagrammatic representation of the design used in the Experimental Method of the Study.

Research Design – Diagrammatic Representation

Pre-Test	Administration of “The Test on Basic Process Skill” a Standardized test constructed by Michael J. Padilla, Linda Cronin and Meghan Twiest on the Pupils of Standard Eight of Government High School, Mangalore Taluk.
Treatment	Teaching Science through Outdoor learning Instructional Material prepared by the Researcher.
Post-Test	Administration of “The Test on Basic Process Skill” a Standardized test constructed by Michael J. Padilla, Linda Cronin and Meghan Twiest on the Pupils of Standard Eight of Government High School, Mangalore Taluk.

Variables of the study

Independent variable in the study:

Outdoor instructional material

Dependent variable:

Basic Science Process Skills

The Basic Science Process Skills selected for the present study were the following

- Basic Process Skill of Observation
- Basic Process Skill of Communication
- Basic Process Skill of Classification
- Basic Process Skill of Measurement
- Basic Process Skill of Prediction
- Basic Process Skill of Inference

Tools used in the Study

- “Test on Basic Process Skill” a standardised test constructed by Michael J. Padilla, Linda Cronin and Meghan Tweist.
- Outdoor Learning Instructional Material prepared by the Researcher to improve the Science Process Skills of the Pupils.

Population of the Study

All the high school students of Standard Eighth studying in Government High Schools of Mangalore Taluk during the academic year 2023-24

Sample of the study

The sample consisted of forty pupils i.e. twenty Boys and twenty Girls of standard Eight of Government high school of Mangalore Taluk

6.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

To measure the effectiveness of Outdoor Learning Instructional Material on Basic Process Skills Descriptive and Inferential Statistics were used.

Descriptive Statistics:

Descriptive Statistics namely Mean, Standard Deviation were computed for the variables Involved in the study.

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Inferential Statistics:

“t” value was calculated to find out the significant difference between the means of scores of Pre-Test and Post-Test as well as that of Boys and Girls in order to reject or retain the hypothesis.

Hypothesis1:

There is a significant difference between the means of the scores of the Pre-Test and Post-Test on

- Basic Process Skill of Observation
- Basic Process Skill of Communication
- Basic Process Skill of Classification
- Basic Process Skill of Measurement
- Basic Process Skill of Prediction
- Basic Process Skill of Inference
- the total score on “The test on Basic Science Process Skill” among Boys Standard Eight of the Government High School, Mangalore Taluk

Table1: Number (N), Mean(M), Standard Deviation (SD), of the Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores on the test on Basic Process Skill among the Pupils Standard eight of Government high school. Mangalore Taluk.

Variable	N	Total		Observation		Communication		Classification		Measurement		Prediction		Inference	
		M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Pre- Test	40	51.20	5.93	57.75	3.51	54.00	3.64	51.50	1.73	60.75	1.39	43.25	1.72	48.75	2.15
Post-Test	40	73.85	3.03	87.00	1.71	76.50	2.49	76.37	3.07	77.37	2.60	67.00	1.95	66.75	2.29

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The mean score difference in the Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of Pupils is 22.65 is in favour of the Post-Test score of Pupils on the Standardized test on Basic Science Process Skill. It is observed that among the six Basic Process Skills, the means of Scores of the skill of observation is highest. Hence we can conclude that treatment significantly increased the Basic Science Process Skills among the pupils of standard Eight.

Table2: Number (N), ‘t’ value of the Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores on the test on Basic Process Skill among the Pupils Standard eight of Government high school. Mangalore Taluk.

COMPONENT	N	“t” value	Remarks
Observation	40	88.69	Significant at 0.01 level
Communication	40	37.00	Significant at 0.01 level
Classification	40	54.02	Significant at 0.01 level
Measurement	40	66.99	Significant at 0.01 level
Prediction	40	27.93	Significant at 0.01 level
Inference	40	73.76	Significant at 0.01 level
Total	40	28.18	Significant at 0.01 level

From the table it is observed that the calculated “t” value is greater than the theoretical value at 0.01 with value 2.71 at df 39. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. i.e. there is a significant difference between the means of the scores of the Pre-Test and Post-Test on

- Observation
- Communication
- Classification
- Measurement
- Prediction
- Inference
- The total score on the test on “Basic Process Skill “among the Pupils of Standard Eight of Government High School, Mangalore Taluk.

In the light of above results, it can be concluded that the treatment was effective on the “Basic Science Process Skill “among the Pupils of Standard Eight of Government High School, Mangalore Taluk.

Hypothesis Two

H2: There is a significant difference between the means of the scores of the Pre-Test and Post-Test on

- Basic Process Skill of Observation

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- Basic Process Skill of Communication
- Basic Process Skill of Classification
- Basic Process Skill of Measurement
- Basic Process Skill of Prediction
- Basic Process Skill of Inference
- the total score on “The test on Basic Science Process Skill” among the Boys and Girls of Standard Eight of the Government High School, Mangalore Taluk

Table3: Number (N), Mean(M), Standard Deviation (SD), and ‘t’ value of the Post-Test Scores on the Test on Basic Process Skill among the Boys and Girls of Standard eight of Government high school. Mangalore Taluk.

Component	Test	N	Variables	Mean	S.D.	“t” value	Remarks
Observation	Post-Test	20	Boys	85.00	1.15	0.71	Not significant at 0.01 level
		20	Girls	81.50	2.07		
Communication	Post-Test	20	Boys	76.00	2.05	0.12	Not significant at 0.01 level
		20	Girls	75.50	2.51		
Classification	Post-Test	20	Boys	77.75	3.59	0.46	Not significant at 0.01 level
		20	Girls	75.00	3.18		
Measurement	Post-Test	20	Boys	80.00	2.76	1.26	Not significant at 0.01 level
		20	Girls	74.75	2.33		
Prediction	Post-Test	20	Boys	66.00	2.49	0.07	Not significant at 0.01 level
		20	Girls	66.50	1.12		
Inference	Post-Test	20	Boys	70.50	1.49	1.76	Not significant at 0.01 level
		20	Girls	63.00	1.45		
Total	Post-Test	20	Boys	75.65	4.67	1.19	Not significant at 0.01 level
		20	Girls	72.05	2.41		

From the table it is observed that the calculated “t” value is less than theoretical value at 0.01 level with

value 2.83 at df 38. Hence the formulated null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no significant difference between the Boys and Girls in acquiring the Basic Science Process Skills.

In the light of above results it can be concluded that the treatment given through Outdoor Learning Instructional Material was equally effective among Boys and Girls.

7.0 MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- It is possible to prepare outdoor learning Instructional Material for the pupils of Standard Eight.
- The treatment given through specially designed Outdoor Learning Instructional Material was significantly effective in improving the Basic Process Skills among the Boys and Girls of Standard Eight.
- The treatment given through specially designed Outdoor Learning Instructional Material was equally effective on developing Basic Process Skills.
 - Observation
 - Communication
 - Classification
 - Measurement
 - Prediction
 - Inference

Total score among the Boys and Girls of Standard Eight.

8.0 EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

- It has been found that the level of performance of the Pupils on the test on “The test on Basic Process Skills” is improved through treatment. Pupils should be given many opportunities within the content Process Skills area to develop Science Process Skills.
- It has been found that Outdoor learning Instructional Material had a positive effect on Science at the high school level. Therefore, Outdoor Learning Instructional Material could be implemented in the classroom for the improvement of Science Process Skills through the prescribed curriculum.

9.0 SUGGESTIONS:

In the present study an earnest attempt was made to find out the effect of specially designed Outdoor Learning

Instructional material in improving the Basic Process Skills among the Pupils of Standard Eighth of the

Government High School of Mangalore Taluk.

Based on the findings of the study the following suggestions are offered.

1. Similar studies may be conducted with a larger sample.
2. Similar studies for a longer period of time under carefully controlled condition.
4. Similar studies may be conducted for higher order Integrated Process Skill and also Social Skills.
5. Similar studies may be conducted in other school subjects also.

10.0 CONCLUSION:

Teaching method used in the classroom teaching learning process means a lot in the shaping of future citizens of the nation. The teaching method followed to teach concepts in Science play important role in conceptualization in the minds of the learner. Outdoor Learning Instructional Material creates an environment and gives ample of opportunities for learner to interact, manipulate, explore, demonstrate, retry with the learning experiences to understand process aspect of Science. Hence more emphasis should be implementing Outdoor Learning Instructional Strategy to teach Science which in turn contribute on developing the Basic Process Skills of Science such as Observation, Communication, Classification, Measurement, Prediction and Inference.

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12.0 LIMITATIONS:

The present study has its limitations with respect to content selected.

The delimitations of the study are

1. The study is only limited to the Standard Eighth of the Government High School.
2. Due to time limit only two units from the Eighth Standard Science subject were selected.

3. The present study limited only to find the effectiveness of Outdoor Learning Instructional Material on Basic Science Process Skills. It can also be used to evaluate the effectiveness on Achievement and Social Skill.

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